

The problem of errors in vegetation monitoring by field methods to detect temporal trends and assign causes of change: a comprehensive bibliography

Technical report

Virgil Iordache, Aurora Neagoe
University of Bucharest

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Context and objective

To understand the causes of plant cover changes and the functional effects of these changes on the production of various ecosystem services via their aggregated functional traits, one needs not only data on the presence or relative abundance of plant species but also to incorporate measurement errors into hypothesis testing. While in measurements of physical and chemical environmental variables, there is a tradition of describing the errors associated with measurements and often a data quality procedure to ensure the reliability of the data, in botany, such an approach is not yet mainstream. In this context, our objective was to gather all available literature on this issue and examine its impact on scientific publications.

Method

We searched Web of Science for (“vegetation plot” OR “vegetation plots” OR “vegetation survey” OR “vegetation surveys” OR “cover estimates” OR "Braun Blanquet" OR floristic) AND (statistic OR error OR “data quality” OR “accurate data” OR “accurately estimate” OR inaccuracy OR “method comparison” OR precision OR “observer training” OR bias OR “stochastic variation” OR “pseudo-turnover”). We read the abstracts of the 894 resulting documents and selected 193 documents (core set) directly relevant to traditional field methods of vegetation description, providing context or outlining the potential for in-situ replacement with new technologies. We read the core set and categorized the articles into six classes. We supplemented the core set with three additional articles that provided context. Finally, we extracted information on the 4293 articles citing the core set (the extended set) from Web of Science and analyzed the total (core + extended) set using CiteSpace to identify the main clusters of literature.

As our purpose here is not to review in detail the information in each category, we did not make a detailed synthesis for each category. Such an effort is no longer useful given the availability of AI tools. However, we provide to the general ecologist a few details in order to stimulate the in-depth investigations of the methodological aspects in the full literature body by careful inspection and critical analysis of each article.

Results

The bibliographic list (196 articles, Appendix 1) is organized in the following categories:

- General methodology (36 articles). These articles provide the background needed, especially for experts in fields other than plant sciences, to understand the context of the error issue.
- The error issue in traditional field methods (90 articles).
- Comparison between methods (21 articles). These articles do not explicitly address the error problem. Still, they are relevant because they provide the information needed to mix data obtained by different methods, which is often the case in long-term, large-scale analyses.
- Detecting vegetation changes in time (22 files). This literature describes attempts to detect vegetation changes at various time scales. Some of them explicitly account for the error problem (such as pseudo turnover), suggesting how future standards might be developed.
- Influence of the error problem on understanding other processes depending on it (10 articles). Several articles point out the difficulties of integrating vegetation change into a causal chain, either as a dependent, or independent variable.
- New technologies for plant cover description in-situ (17 articles). These articles outline directions for automating in-situ plant monitoring down to the species level.

The CiteSpace analysis (Appendix 2) revealed that the citation impact of the core set is organized in 12 main clusters. None of these clusters, as keywords retained by CiteSpace, included a term describing the error issue, suggesting that this topic has not been approached as an organized research program. We report the content (i.e., articles within with hyperlink to the publisher) of all these clusters to provide an additional knowledge resource for those interested in developing the subject.

Sample of information

A large part of the knowledge in vegetation science is based on non-random, preferentially collected data (Chiarucci, 2007). The reliability of vegetation data is a long-standing issue (Lepš and Hadincová, 2009). The problem is relevant for incorporating measurement error in testing the changes in biodiversity (Mason et al., 2018) and for evaluating the effects in time of external drivers on the vegetation (Begley-Miller et al., 2018). In particular, assessing the vegetation change using vegetation-plot databases is difficult (Chytrý et al., 2014).

There are several studies dedicated to the evaluation of data consistency and repeatability in relation to defoliation (Eickenscheidt and Wellbrock, 2014), pollen productivity (Farrell et al., 2016), alpine plant species (Futschik et al., 2019), vegetation classification and mapping (Hearn et al., 2011), wetland vegetation (Johns et al., 2015). Non-detection errors occur especially in the case of rare or small species (Clarke et al., 2012).

Explicit quality assurance methods is present, according to our knowledge, only in the case of ICP-Forests programme (Allegrini et al., 2009) and a few national monitoring schemes (Bussotti et al., 2009; Sanders et al., 2015)

Observer-driven errors in vegetation monitoring are among the most important (Boch et al., 2022; Milberg et al., 2008; Vittoz and Guisan, 2007), whether of individuals or of sampling teams (Kercher et al., 2003), although using at least two investigators increases the reliability of vegetation analysis (Nilsson, 1992). Relocation errors also matter in the resurveys of historical vegetation plots (Verheyen et al., 2018). Different sampling methods also lead to some extent to different results (Kercher et al., 2003; Laliberté et al., 2010). Knowing how large are these errors is essential for inferring valid conclusions about the change of vegetation.

Morrison and his coworkers dedicated the most substantial effort to review and characterize the errors in vegetation surveys (Morrison, 2016, 2021; Morrison et al., 2020), spatiotemporal differences of the errors (Morrison et al., 2024), as well as their consequences on the diversity indices and species-abundance relationships (Morrison et al., 2023).

The visual estimation can be improved by computer-aided calibration (Gallegos Torell and Glimskär, 2009), and the performance in vegetation records can be compared by efficiency graphs derived from rarefaction curves (Seidling et al., 2020). A combination of probabilistic and integrated approaches is probably optimal for detecting changes in plants diversity (Alessi et al., 2023).

As resurveying studies and permanent plots are among the essential methodological tools expected to play a critical role in solving the emerging challenges of vegetation science (Yannelli et al., 2022), obtaining quantitative information about the errors associated to these tools is essential for both plant science and ecological research directions.

Conclusions and potential impact

The literature on errors in vegetation monitoring by field methods is limited, given the vast body of plant science literature, and is not organized as a research program, except for a few authors who investigated the issue in more detail. However, the efforts of these groups were not followed by many other scientists, resulting in a non-detectable cluster of articles compared to other subjects.

The problem of establishing generally accepted standards for describing errors in vegetation monitoring by field methods remains open.

The impact of this report lies in:

- Its potential to catalyze cooperation between botanists/plant scientists and researchers from other environmental fields interested in understanding [complex processes involving plants](#).
- Its potential to catalyze the development of new plant cover monitoring standards, allowing a quantitative understanding of trends of the plant cover changes at all time scales.
- Its relevance for the development of an [integrated monitoring of soil, water, air, and biodiversity](#) able to inform decisions about complex problems under the current institutional setting, given the key role of plants as a hub coupling biological and abiotic processes.

Appendix 1 Structure bibliography.

General methodology

- Alessi, N., Bonari, G., Zannini, P., Jiménez-Alfaro, B., Agrillo, E., Attorre, F., Canullo, R., Casella, L., Cervellini, M., Chelli, S., Di Musciano, M., Guarino, R., Martellos, S., Massimi, M., Venanzoni, R., Zerbe, S., Chiarucci, A., 2023. Probabilistic and preferential sampling approaches offer integrated perspectives of Italian forest diversity. *Journal of Vegetation Science* 34.
- Allegrini, M.C., Canullo, R., Campetella, G., 2009. ICP-Forests (International Co-operative Programme on Assessment and Monitoring of Air Pollution Effects on Forests): Quality Assurance procedure in plant diversity monitoring. *J Environ Monit* 11, 782–787.
- Biurrun, I., Pielech, R., Dembicz, I., Gillet, F., Kozub, Ł., Marcenò, C., Reitalu, T., Van Meerbeek, K., Guarino, R., Chytrý, M., Pakeman, R.J., Preislerová, Z., Axmanová, I., Burrascano, S., Bartha, S., Boch, S., Bruun, H.H., Conradi, T., De Frenne, P., Essl, F., Filibeck, G., Hájek, M., Jiménez-Alfaro, B., Kuzemko, A., Molnár, Z., Pärtel, M., Pätsch, R., Prentice, H.C., Roleček, J., Sutcliffe, L.M.E., Terzi, M., Winkler, M., Wu, J., Aćić, S., Acosta, A.T.R., Afif, E., Akasaka, M., Alatalo, J.M., Aleffi, M., Aleksanyan, A., Ali, A., Apostolova, I., Ashouri, P., Bátori, Z., Baumann, E., Becker, T., Belonovskaya, E., Benito Alonso, J.L., Berastegi, A., Bergamini, A., Bhatta, K.P., Bonini, I., Büchler, M.O., Budzhak, V., Bueno, A., Buldrini, F., Campos, J.A., Cancellieri, L., Carboni, M., Ceulemans, T., Chiarucci, A., Chocarro, C., Conti, L., Csergő, A.M., Cykowska-Marzencka, B., Czarniecka-Wiera, M., Czarnocka-Cieciura, M., Czortek, P., Danihelka, J., de Bello, F., Deák, B., Demeter, L., Deng, L., Diekmann, M., Dolezal, J., Dolnik, C., Dřevojan, P., Dupré, C., Ecker, K., Ejtehadi, H., Erschbamer, B., Etayo, J., Etzold, J., Farkas, T., Farzam, M., Fayvush, G., Fernández Calzado, M.R., Finckh, M., Fjellstad, W., Fotiadis, G., García-Magro, D., García-Mijangos, I., Gavilán, R.G., Germany, M., Ghafari, S., Giusso del Galdo, G.P., Grytnes, J.A., Güler, B., Gutiérrez-Girón, A., Helm, A., Herrera, M., Hüllbusch, E.M., Ingerpuu, N., Jägerbrand, A.K., Jandt, U., Janišová, M., Jeanneret, P., Jeltsch, F., Jensen, K., Jentsch, A., Kaçki, Z., Kakinuma, K., Kapfer, J., Kargar, M., Kelemen, A., Kiehl, K., Kirschner, P., Koyama, A., Langer, N., Lazzaro, L., Lepš, J., Li, C.F., Li, F.Y., Liendo, D., Lindborg, R., Löbel, S., Lomba, A., Lososová, Z., Lustyk, P., Luzuriaga, A.L., Ma, W., Maccherini, S., Magnes, M., Malicki, M., Manthey, M., Mardari, C., May, F., Mayrhofer, H., Meier, E.S., Memariani, F., Merunková, K., Michelsen, O., Molero Mesa, J., Moradi, H., Moysiyenko, I., Mugnai, M., Naqinezhad, A., Natcheva, R., Ninot, J.M., Nobis, M., Noroozi, J., Nowak, A., Onipchenko, V., Palpurina, S., Pauli, H., Pedashenko, H., Pedersen, C., Peet, R.K., Pérez-Haase, A., Peters, J., Pipenbaher, N., Pirini, C., Pladevall-Izard, E., Plesková, Z., Potenza, G., Rahmanian, S., Rodríguez-Rojo, M.P., Ronkin, V., Rosati, L., Ruprecht, E., Rusina, S., Sabovljević, M., Sanaei, A., Sánchez, A.M., Santi, F., Savchenko, G., Sebastià, M.T., Shyriaieva, D., Silva, V., Škornik, S., Šmerdová, E., Sonkoly, J., Sperandii, M.G., Staniaszek-Kik, M., Stevens, C., Stifter, S., Suchrow, S., Swacha, G., Świerszcz, S., Talebi, A., Teleki, B., Tichý, L., Tölgyesi, C., Torca, M., Török, P., Tsarevskaya, N., Tsiripidis, I., Turisová, I., Ushimaru, A., Valkó, O., Van Mechelen, C., Vanneste, T., Vasheniak, I., Vassilev, K., Viciani, D., Villar, L., Virtanen, R., Vitasović-Kosić, I., Vojtkó, A., Vynokurov, D., Waldén, E., Wang, Y., Weiser, F., Wen, L., Wesche, K., White, H., Widmer, S., Wolfrum, S., Wróbel, A., Yuan, Z., Zelený, D., Zhao, L., Dengler, J., Kreft, H., 2021. Benchmarking plant diversity of Palaearctic grasslands and other open habitats. *Journal of Vegetation Science* 32.
- Botta-Dukát, Z., Kovács-Láng, E., Rédei, T., Kertész, M., Garadnai, J., 2007. Statistical and biological consequences of preferential sampling in phytosociology: Theoretical considerations and a case study. *Folia Geobotanica* 42, 141–152.

- Bussotti, F., Cozzi, A., Cenni, E., Bettini, D., Sarti, C., Ferretti, M., 2009. Quality Assurance and measurement errors in monitoring tree crown conditions in Italy. *J Environ Monit* 11, 769–773.
- Chamberlain, S., Ingram, H., 2012. Developing coefficients of conservatism to advance floristic quality assessment in the Mid-Atlantic region. *Journal of the Torrey Botanical Society* 139, 416–427.
- Cherrill, A., McClean, C., 2001. Between-observer variation in the application of a standard method of habitat mapping by environmental consultants in the UK. *Journal of Applied Ecology* 36, 989–1008.
- Chiarucci, A., 2007. To sample or not to sample? That is the question... For the vegetation scientist. *Folia Geobotanica* 42, 209–216.
- Chytrý, M., Otýpková, Z., 2003. Plot sizes used for phytosociological sampling of European vegetation. *Journal of Vegetation Science* 14, 563–570.
- Chytrý, M., Rafajová, M., 2003. Czech National Phytosociological Database:: basic statistics of the available vegetation-plot data. *Preslia* 75, 1–15.
- De Cáceres, M., Chytrý, M., Agrillo, E., Attorre, F., Botta-Dukát, Z., Capelo, J., Czúcz, B., Dengler, J., Ewald, J., Faber-Langendoen, D., Feoli, E., Franklin, S.B., Gavilán, R., Gillet, F., Jansen, F., Jiménez-Alfaro, B., Krestov, P., Landucci, F., Lengyel, A., Loidi, J., Mucina, L., Peet, R.K., Roberts, D.W., Roleček, J., Schaminée, J.H.J., Schmidtlein, S., Theurillat, J.P., Tichý, L., Walker, D.A., Wildi, O., Willner, W., Wiser, S.K., Scheiner, S., 2015. A comparative framework for broad-scale plot-based vegetation classification. *Applied Vegetation Science* 18, 543–560.
- Dengler, J., Jansen, F., Glöckler, F., Peet, R.K., De Cáceres, M., Chytrý, M., Ewald, J., Oldeland, J., Lopez-Gonzalez, G., Finckh, M., Mucina, L., Rodwell, J.S., Schaminée, J.H.J., Spencer, N., 2011. The Global Index of Vegetation-Plot Databases (GIVD): a new resource for vegetation science. *Journal of Vegetation Science* 22, 582–597.
- Eickenscheidt, N., Wellbrock, N., 2014. Consistency of defoliation data of the national training courses for the forest condition survey in Germany from 1992 to 2012. *Environ Monit Assess* 186, 257–275.
- Farrell, M., Bunting, M.J., Middleton, R., 2016. Replicability of data collected for empirical estimation of relative pollen productivity. *Review of Palaeobotany and Palynology* 232, 1–13.
- Granger, V., Bez, N., Fromentin, J.M., Meynard, C., Jadaud, A., Mérigot, B., Peres-Neto, P., 2015. Mapping diversity indices: not a trivial issue. *Methods in Ecology and Evolution* 6, 688–696.
- Hao, L., Qingdong, S., Imin, B., Kasim, N., 2020. Methodology for optimizing quadrat size in sparse vegetation surveys: A desert case study from the Tarim Basin. *PLoS One* 15, e0235469.
- Hearn, S.M., Healey, J.R., McDonald, M.A., Turner, A.J., Wong, J.L., Stewart, G.B., 2011. The repeatability of vegetation classification and mapping. *J Environ Manage* 92, 1174–1184.
- Irvine, K., Wright, W., Shanahan, E., Rodhouse, T., 2019. Cohesive framework for modelling plant cover class data. *Methods in Ecology and Evolution* 10, 1749–1760.
- Korzeniak, J., 2013. Scope and data set of the phytosociological database ‘Grasslands in the Polish Carpathians’. *Acta Societatis Botanicorum Poloniae* 82, 237–242.
- Landucci, F., Acosta, A.T.R., Agrillo, E., Attorre, F., Biondi, E., Cambria, V.E., Chiarucci, A., Del Vico, E., De Sanctis, M., Facioni, L., Geri, F., Gigante, D., Guarino, R., Landi, S., Lucarini, D., Panfili, E., Pesaresi, S., Prisco, I., Rosati, L., Spada, F., Venanzoni, R., 2012. VegItaly: The Italian collaborative project for a national vegetation database. *Plant Biosystems - An International Journal Dealing with all Aspects of Plant Biology* 146, 756–763.
- Novák, P., Kalníková, V., Szokala, D., Aleksanyan, A., Batsatsashvili, K., Fayvush, G., Kolbaia, S., Nakhutsrishvili, G., Sedláček, V., Štěrbá, T., Zukal, D., 2023. Transcaucasian Vegetation Database – a phytosociological database of the Southern Caucasus. *Vegetation Classification and Survey* 4, 231–240.

- NOVELLIE, P., STRYDOM, G., 1987. MONITORING THE RESPONSE OF VEGETATION TO USE BY LARGE HERBIVORES - AN ASSESSMENT OF SOME TECHNIQUES. *South African Journal of Wildlife Research* 17, 109–117.
- Podani, J., 2005. Multivariate exploratory analysis of ordinal data in ecology: Pitfalls, problems and solutions. *Journal of Vegetation Science* 16, 497–510.
- Robertson, M.P., Cumming, G.S., Erasmus, B.F.N., 2010. Getting the most out of atlas data. *Diversity and Distributions* 16, 363–375.
- Siefert, A., Laughlin, D.C., Sabatini, F.M., 2024. You shall know a species by the company it keeps: Leveraging co-occurrence data to improve ecological prediction. *Journal of Vegetation Science* 35.
- Sivicek, V.A., Taft, J.B., 2011. Functional Group Density as an index for assessing habitat quality in tallgrass prairie. *Ecological Indicators* 11, 1251–1258.
- Skobel, N., Kozub, Ł., Dembicz, I., Boch, S., Bruun, H.H., Chusova, O., Golub, V., Helm, A., Iakushenko, D., Pawlikowski, P., Zaniewski, P., Dengler, J., 2024. Nordic-Baltic Grassland Vegetation Database (NBGVGD) – current state and future prospects. *Vegetation Classification and Survey* 5, 75–84.
- Szymura, T.H., Kassa, H., Swacha, G., Szymura, M., Zając, A., Kački, Z., 2023. Vegetation databases augment but do not replace species distribution atlases in species richness assessment. *Ecological Indicators* 154.
- Taddeo, S., Snyder, E.F., Anderson, E.C., Porter, C.M., Guider, T.M., Havens, K., 2025. Teamwork makes the dream work: combining community science and expert-led surveys to study urban plant richness and composition. *Urban Ecosystems* 28.
- Tuomisto, H., Suominen, L., Alonso, A., Cárdenas, G., Lehtonen, S., Moulatlet, G.M., Pérez, E., Sirén, A., Weigelt, P., Zuquim, G., 2024. Species–soil relationships across Amazonia: Niche specificity and consistency in understory ferns. *Journal of Vegetation Science* 35.
- Vallet, J., Rambaud, M., Coquel, L., Poncet, L., Hendoux, F., 2012. [Sampling effort and floristic atlases: survey completeness of localities and description of knowledge gaps]. *C R Biol* 335, 753–763.
- Vassilev, K., Pedashenko, H., Alexandrova, A., Tashev, A., Ganeva, A., Gavrilova, A., Gradevska, A., Assenov, A., Vitkova, A., Grigorov, B., Gushev, C., Filipova, E., Aneva, I., Knollová, I., Nikolov, I., Georgiev, G., Gogushev, G., Tinchev, G., Pachedjieva, K., Koev, K., Lyubanova, M., Dimitrov, M., Apostolova-Stoyanova, N., Velev, N., Zhelev, P., Glogov, P., Natcheva, R., Tzonev, R., Boch, S., Hennekens, S., Georgiev, S., Stoyanov, S., Karakiev, T., Kalníková, V., Shivarov, V., Russakova, V., Vulchev, V., 2016. Balkan Vegetation Database: historical background, current status and future perspectives. *Phytocoenologia* 46, 89–95.
- Villaseñor, J.L., 2015. ¿La crisis de la biodiversidad es la crisis de la taxonomía? *Botanical Sciences* 93, 3–14.
- Walker, D.A., Breen, A.L., Druckenmiller, L.A., Wirth, L.W., Fisher, W., Raynolds, M.K., Šibík, J., Walker, M.D., Hennekens, S., Boggs, K., Boucher, T., Buchhorn, M., Bültmann, H., Cooper, D.J., Daniëls, F.J.A., Davidson, S.J., Ebersole, J.J., Elmendorf, S.C., Epstein, H.E., Gould, W.A., Hollister, R.D., Iversen, C.M., Jorgenson, M.T., Kade, A., Lee, M.T., MacKenzie, W.H., Peet, R.K., Peirce, J.L., Schickhoff, U., Sloan, V.L., Talbot, S.S., Tweedie, C.E., Villarreal, S., Webber, P.J., Zona, D., 2016. The Alaska Arctic Vegetation Archive (AVA-AK). *Phytocoenologia* 46, 221–229.
- Wörz, A., Thiv, M., 2015. The temporal dynamics of a regional flora—The effects of global and local impacts. *Flora - Morphology, Distribution, Functional Ecology of Plants* 217, 99–108.
- Zelený, D., Chytrý, M., 2019. Ecological specialization indices for species of the Czech flora. *Preslia* 91, 93–116.

The error issue in traditional field methods

- Andersen, D.K., Nygaard, B., Fredshavn, J.R., Ejrnæs, R., Verheyen, K., 2013. Cost-effective assessment of conservation status of fens. *Applied Vegetation Science* 16, 491–501.
- Archaux, F., Bergès, L., Chevalier, R., 2006. Are Plant Censuses Carried Out on Small Quadrats More Reliable than on Larger Ones? *Plant Ecology* 188, 179–190.
- Bergès, L., Gégout, J.-C., Franc, A., 2006. Can understory vegetation accurately predict site index? A comparative study using floristic and abiotic indices in sessile oak (*Quercus petraea* Liebl.) stands in northern France. *Annals of Forest Science* 63, 31–42.
- Bergstedt, J., Westerberg, L., Milberg, P., 2009. In the eye of the beholder: bias and stochastic variation in cover estimates. *Plant Ecology* 204, 271–283.
- Biko'o, A.A., Myburgh, W.J., Reilly, B.K., 2025. The Accuracy of the Step Point Vegetation Sampling Method for Herbaceous Layer Monitoring in South African Savannas. *Diversity* 17.
- Boch, S., Bedolla, A., Ecker, K., Graf, U., Kuchler, H., Kuchler, M., Holderegger, R., Bergamini, A., 2019. Mean indicator values suggest decreasing habitat quality in Swiss dry grasslands and are robust to relocation error. *Tuexenia*, 315–334.
- Boch, S., Kuchler, H., Kuchler, M., Bedolla, A., Ecker, K.T., Graf, U.H., Moser, T., Holderegger, R., Bergamini, A., 2022. Observer-driven pseudoturnover in vegetation monitoring is context-dependent but does not affect ecological inference. *Applied Vegetation Science* 25.
- Bonham, C.D., Reich, R.M., 2009. Influences of transect relocation errors on line-point estimates of plant cover. *Plant Ecology* 204, 173–178.
- Brandon, A., Spyreas, G., Molano-Flores, B., Carroll, C., Ellis, J., 2003. Can volunteers provide reliable data for forest vegetation surveys? *Natural Areas Journal* 23, 254–261.
- Bried, J.T., Jog, S.K., Davis, C.A., Dzialowski, A.R., 2016. Rapid Buffer Assessment Fails to Predict and Classify Wetland Floristic Quality in Oklahoma. *Wetlands* 36, 799–805.
- Bried, J.T., Strout, K.L., Portante, T., 2012. Coefficients of Conservatism for the Vascular Flora of New York and New England: Inter-State Comparisons and Expert Opinion Bias. *Northeastern Naturalist* 19, 101–114.
- Burg, S., Rixen, C., Stöckli, V., Wipf, S., Acosta, A., 2014. Observation bias and its causes in botanical surveys on high-alpine summits. *Journal of Vegetation Science* 26, 191–200.
- Chmura, D., Salachna, A., 2016. THE ERRORS IN VISUAL ESTIMATION OF PLANTS COVER IN THE CONTEXT OF EDUCATION OF PHYTOSOCIOLOGY. *Chemistry-Didactics-Ecology-Metrology* 21, 75–82.
- Chytry, M., 2001. Phytosociological data give biased estimates of species richness. *Journal of Vegetation Science* 12, 439–444.
- Chytry, M., Tichy, L., Hennekens, S., Schaminée, J., 2014. Assessing vegetation change using vegetation-plot databases: a risky business. *Applied Vegetation Science* 17, 32–41.
- Cielo, R., Gneri, M., Martins, F., 2011. Sampling precision and variability of tree species abundance ranks in a semideciduous Atlantic forest fragment. *Community Ecology* 12, 188–195.
- Clarke, K.D., Lewis, M., Brandle, R., Ostendorf, B., 2012. Non-detection errors in a survey of persistent, highly-detectable vegetation species. *Environ Monit Assess* 184, 625–635.
- Critchley, C.N.R., Poulton, S.M.C., 1998. A method to optimize precision and scale in grassland monitoring. *Journal of Vegetation Science* 9, 837–846.
- Cruickshank, M.M., Moles, A.T., Debono, S.A., Xirocostas, Z.A., 2024. COVERater-A Free Application for Training Researchers to Accurately Estimate Species Cover in Terrestrial and Aquatic Ecosystems. *Ecol Evol* 14, e70447.
- D'Antraccoli, M., Bedini, G., Peruzzi, L., 2022. Maps of relative floristic ignorance and virtual floristic lists: An R package to incorporate uncertainty in mapping and analysing biodiversity data. *Ecological Informatics* 67.
- Damgaard, C., 2014. Estimating mean plant cover from different types of cover data: a coherent statistical framework. *Ecosphere* 5, 1–7.
- Dembicz, I., Dengler, J., 2025. Should we estimate plant cover in percent or on ordinal scales? II – Diversity indices. *Vegetation Classification and Survey* 6, 133–140.

- Dengler, J., Dembiczy, I., 2023. Should we estimate plant cover in percent or on ordinal scales? *Vegetation Classification and Survey* 4, 131–138.
- Dengler, J., Löbel, S., Dolnik, C., 2009. Species constancy depends on plot size – a problem for vegetation classification and how it can be solved. *Journal of Vegetation Science* 20, 754–766.
- Divíšek, J., Chytrý, M., 2018. High-resolution and large-extent mapping of plant species richness using vegetation-plot databases. *Ecological Indicators* 89, 840–851.
- Dostál, P., 2005. Is the population turnover of patchy-distributed annuals determined by dormancy dynamics or dispersal processes? *Ecography* 28, 745–756.
- Douda, J., Doudová, J., Holešťová, A., Chudomelová, M., Vild, O., Boublík, K., Černá, M., Havrdová, A., Petřík, P., Pychová, N., Smyčková, M., Šebesta, J., Vaniček, J., Hédl, R., 2023. Historical sampling error: A neglected factor in long-term biodiversity change research. *Biological Conservation* 286.
- Endress, B.A., Averett, J.P., Steinmetz, S., Quaempts, E.J., 2022. Forgotten forbs: Standard vegetation surveys underrepresent ecologically and culturally important forbs in a threatened grassland ecosystem. *Conservation Science and Practice* 4.
- Fiaschi, T., Fanfarillo, E., Maccherini, S., Bacaro, G., Bonari, G., Foggi, B., Peruzzi, L., Pinzani, L., Rosati, L., Scoppola, A., Viciani, D., Angiolini, C., 2023. Effectiveness of different metrics of floristic quality assessment: The simpler, the better? *Ecological Indicators* 149.
- FUNK, V., 1993. USES AND MISUSES OF FLORAS. *Taxon* 42, 761–772.
- García-Roselló, E., González-Dacosta, J., Lobo, J.M., 2023. The biased distribution of existing information on biodiversity hinders its use in conservation, and we need an integrative approach to act urgently. *Biological Conservation* 283.
- Garcia, A.O., Marinho, L.C., Snak, C., Silva, C., 2025. Rediscovery of a rare endangered plant in Santa Catarina, Brazil: implications for conservation of small, overlooked herbaceous species. *Journal of Coastal Conservation* 29.
- Garcillán, P.P., Ezcurra, E., 2011. Sampling procedures and species estimation: testing the effectiveness of herbarium data against vegetation sampling in an oceanic island. *Journal of Vegetation Science* 22, 273–280.
- Goze, L., Ekström, M., Sandring, S., Jonsson, B.-G., Wallerman, J., Ståhl, G., 2024. Estimation of plant density based on presence/absence data using hybrid inference. *Ecological Informatics* 80.
- HALL, J., OKALI, D., 1978. OBSERVER-BIAS IN A FLORISTIC SURVEY OF COMPLEX TROPICAL VEGETATION. *Journal of Ecology* 66, 241–249.
- He, J., Yang, W., You, Q., Hu, Q., Cong, M., Tian, C., Ma, K., 2025. Impacts of road networks on the geography of floristic collections in China. *Plant Divers* 47, 403–414.
- Helm, D.J., Mead, B.R., 2004. Reproducibility of vegetation cover estimates in south-central Alaska forests. *Journal of Vegetation Science* 15, 33–40.
- Herpigny, B., Gosselin, F., 2015. Analyzing plant cover class data quantitatively: Customized zero-inflated cumulative beta distributions show promising results. *Ecological Informatics* 26, 18–26.
- Inouye, R., 2002. Sampling effort and vegetative cover estimates in sagebrush steppe. *Western North American Naturalist* 62, 360–364.
- Jansen, F., Dengler, J., 2010. Plant names in vegetation databases - a neglected source of bias. *Journal of Vegetation Science* 21, 1179–1186.
- Jobe, R.T., White, P.S., 2009. A new cost-distance model for human accessibility and an evaluation of accessibility bias in permanent vegetation plots in Great Smoky Mountains National Park, USA. *Journal of Vegetation Science* 20, 1099–1109.
- Jog, S.K., Bried, J.T., 2024. The “full species list” fallacy in Floristic Quality Assessment. *Ecosphere* 15.
- Kapfer, J., Hedl, R., Jurasinski, G., Kopecky, M., Schei, F.H., Grytnes, J.A., 2016. Resurveying historical vegetation data - opportunities and challenges. *Appl Veg Sci* 20, 164–171.

- KENNEDY, K., ADDISON, P., 1987. SOME CONSIDERATIONS FOR THE USE OF VISUAL ESTIMATES OF PLANT COVER IN BIOMONITORING. *Journal of Ecology* 75, 151–157.
- Kercher, S.M., Frieswyk, C.B., Zedler, J.B., 2003. Effects of sampling teams and estimation methods on the assessment of plant cover. *Journal of Vegetation Science* 14, 899–906.
- Klimeš, L., 2003. Scale-dependent variation in visual estimates of grassland plant cover. *Journal of Vegetation Science* 14, 815–821.
- Körschens, M., Bucher, S., Römermann, C., Denzler, J., 2023. Improving Data Efficiency for Plant Cover Prediction with Label Interpolation and Monte-Carlo Cropping, 45th Annual Conference of the German-Association-for-Pattern-Recognition (DAGM GCPR), Heidelberg, GERMANY, pp. 321–334.
- Landi, S., Chiarucci, A., 2010. Is floristic quality assessment reliable in human-managed ecosystems? *Systematics and Biodiversity* 8, 269–280.
- Larraín, J., Alarcón, D., Ardiles, V., Atala, C., 2019. Hidden in plain sight: how overlooking ephemeral bryophytes can bias biodiversity assessments and conservation actions. *The Bryologist* 122.
- Lawson, B.E., Ferrier, S., Wardell-Johnson, G., Beeton, R.J.S., Pullar, D.V., 2010. Improving the assessment of species compositional dissimilarity in a priori ecological classifications: evaluating map scale, sampling intensity and improvement in a hierarchical classification. *Applied Vegetation Science* 13, 473–484.
- Lepš, J., Hadincová, V., 2009. How reliable are our vegetation analyses? *Journal of Vegetation Science* 3, 119–124.
- Leps, J., Smilauer, P., 2007. Subjectively sampled vegetation data: Don't throw out the baby with the bath water. *Folia Geobotanica* 42, 169–178.
- Liu, Y., Xu, X., Dimitrov, D., Rahbek, C., Wang, Z., 2024. Reply to: Reassessing data quality underlying the recently updated floristic map of the world. *Nat Commun* 15, 3673.
- Marchetto, E., Livornese, M., Sabatini, F., Tordoni, E., Da Re, D., Lenoir, J., Testolin, R., Bacaro, G., Gatti, R., Chiarucci, A., Foody, G., Gábor, L., Groom, Q., Iaria, J., Malavasi, M., Moudry, V., Santovito, D., Šimová, P., Zannini, P., Rocchini, D., 2024. ADDRESSING MULTIPLE FACETS OF BIAS AND UNCERTAINTY IN CONTINENTAL-SCALE BIODIVERSITY DATABASES. *Biodiversity Informatics* 18, 56–77.
- Mason, N.W.H., Holdaway, R.J., Richardson, S.J., Chao, A., 2018. Incorporating measurement error in testing for changes in biodiversity. *Methods in Ecology and Evolution* 9, 1296–1307.
- Matthews, J., Tessene, P., Wiesbrook, S., Zercher, B., 2005. Effect of area and isolation on species richness and indices of floristic quality in Illinois, USA wetlands. *Wetlands* 25, 607–615.
- McNellie, M.J., Dorrrough, J., Oliver, I., Podani, J., 2019. Species abundance distributions should underpin ordinal cover-abundance transformations. *Applied Vegetation Science* 22, 361–372.
- McNellie, M.J., Oliver, I., Gibbons, P., 2015. Pitfalls and possible solutions for using geo-referenced site data to inform vegetation models. *Ecological Informatics* 30, 230–234.
- MELMAN, T., DEHAES, H., VANWIJNGAARDEN, W., 1991. SIZE DEPENDENCE OF PARAMETERS FOR ECOLOGICAL FACTORS AND FOR NATURE CONSERVATION EVALUATION OF GRASSLAND RELEVES. *Biological Conservation* 55, 347–354.
- Meyer, C., Weigelt, P., Kreft, H., 2016. Multidimensional biases, gaps and uncertainties in global plant occurrence information. *Ecol Lett* 19, 992–1006.
- Michalcová, D., Lvončík, S., Chytrý, M., Hájek, O., 2011. Bias in vegetation databases? A comparison of stratified-random and preferential sampling. *Journal of Vegetation Science* 22, 281–291.
- Milberg, P., Bergstedt, J., Fridman, J., Odell, G., Westerberg, L., 2008. Observer bias and random variation in vegetation monitoring data. *Journal of Vegetation Science* 19, 633–644.
- Monzingo, D.S., Shipley, L.A., Cook, R.C., Cook, J.G., 2022. Factors influencing predictions of understory vegetation biomass from visual cover estimates. *Wildlife Society Bulletin* 46.
- Morrison, L.W., 2016. Observer error in vegetation surveys: a review. *Journal of Plant Ecology* 9, 367–379.

- Morrison, L.W., 2021. Nonsampling error in vegetation surveys: understanding error types and recommendations for reducing their occurrence. *Plant Ecology* 222, 577–586.
- Morrison, L.W., Bingham, S.N., Young, C.C., 2019. Inter-Observer Error in Wetland Vegetation Surveys. *Wetlands* 40, 249–258.
- Morrison, L.W., Leis, S.A., DeBacker, M.D., Losapio, G., 2023. Observer error in grassland vegetation surveys: effects on species diversity metrics and species–abundance relationships. *Journal of Plant Ecology* 16.
- Morrison, L.W., Leis, S.A., DeBacker, M.D., Yang, Y., 2020. Interobserver error in grassland vegetation surveys: sources and implications. *Journal of Plant Ecology* 13, 641–648.
- Morrison, L.W., Leis, S.A., Short, M.F., DeBacker, M.D., 2024. A spatiotemporal comparison of interobserver error in vegetation sampling. *Journal of Vegetation Science* 35.
- Morrison, L.W., Young, C.C., 2016. Observer error in sampling a rare plant population. *Plant Ecology & Diversity* 9, 289–297.
- Morsdorf, M.A., Ravolainen, V.T., Stovern, L.E., Yoccoz, N.G., Jonsdottir, I.S., Brathen, K.A., 2015. Definition of sampling units begets conclusions in ecology: the case of habitats for plant communities. *PeerJ* 3, e815.
- NILSSON, C., 1992. INCREASING THE RELIABILITY OF VEGETATION ANALYSES BY USING A TEAM OF 2 INVESTIGATORS. *Journal of Vegetation Science* 3, 565–565.
- ÖZkan, K., 2021. Estimating True Species Richness from Braun Blanquet Scale. *Kastamonu Üniversitesi Orman Fakültesi Dergisi* 21, 306–314.
- Page, M.J., Baxter, G.S., Lisle, A.T., 2006. Evaluating the adequacy of sampling germinable soil seed banks in semi-arid systems. *Journal of Arid Environments* 64, 323–341.
- Peterka, T., Syrovátka, V., Dítě, D., Hájková, P., Hrubanová, M., Jiroušek, M., Plesková, Z., Singh, P., Šimová, A., Šmerdová, E., Hájek, M., Roberts, D., 2020. Is variable plot size a serious constraint in broad-scale vegetation studies? A case study on fens. *Journal of Vegetation Science* 31, 594–605.
- Qian, H., 2024. Reassessing data quality underlying the recently updated floristic map of the world. *Nat Commun* 15, 3674.
- Ristow, M., Panitsa, M., Meyer, S., Bergmeier, E., 2022. Factors of Detection Deficits in Vascular Plant Inventories—An Island Case Study. *Diversity* 14.
- Sandel, B., Gutiérrez, A.G., Reich, P.B., Schrod, F., Dickie, J., Kattge, J., Schmidlein, S., 2015. Estimating the missing species bias in plant trait measurements. *Journal of Vegetation Science* 26, 828–838.
- Seidling, W., 2005. Ground floor vegetation assessment within the intensive (Level II) monitoring of forest ecosystems in Germany: chances and challenges. *European Journal of Forest Research* 124, 301–312.
- Seidling, W., Hamberg, L., Máliš, F., Salemaa, M., Kutnar, L., Czerepko, J., Kompa, T., Buriánek, V., Dupouey, J.-L., Vodálová, A., Canullo, R., 2020. Comparing observer performance in vegetation records by efficiency graphs derived from rarefaction curves. *Ecological Indicators* 109.
- Smart, S.M., Scott, W.A., 2004. Bias in Ellenberg indicator values — problems with detection of the effect of vegetation type. *Journal of Vegetation Science* 15, 843–846.
- Ståhl, G., Ekström, M., Dahlgren, J., Esseen, P.A., Grafström, A., Jonsson, B.G., Molofsky, J., 2017. Informative plot sizes in presence-absence sampling of forest floor vegetation. *Methods in Ecology and Evolution* 8, 1284–1291.
- Ståhl, G., Ekström, M., Dahlgren, J., Esseen, P.A., Grafström, A., Jonsson, B.G., Molofsky, J., 2020. Presence–absence sampling for estimating plant density using survey data with variable plot size. *Methods in Ecology and Evolution* 11, 580–590.
- SYKES, J., HORRILL, A., MOUNTFORD, M., 1983. USE OF VISUAL COVER ASSESSMENTS AS QUANTITATIVE ESTIMATORS OF SOME BRITISH WOODLAND TAXA. *Journal of Ecology* 71, 437–450.

- Tierney, D.A., Fletcher, A.T., Erskine, P.D., 2015. Standard survey designs drive bias in the mapping of upland swamp communities. *Austral Ecology* 40, 782–793.
- Verheyen, K., Bažány, M., Čečko, E., Chudomelová, M., Closset-Kopp, D., Czortek, P., Decocq, G., De Frenne, P., De Keersmaecker, L., Enríquez García, C., Fabšičová, M., Grytnes, J.A., Hederová, L., Hédl, R., Heinken, T., Schei, F.H., Horváth, S., Jaroszewicz, B., Jermakowicz, E., Klinerová, T., Kolk, J., Kopecký, M., Kuras, I., Lenoir, J., Macek, M., Máliš, F., Martinussen, T.C., Naaf, T., Papp, L., Papp-Szakály, Á., Pech, P., Petřík, P., Prach, J., Reczyńska, K., Sætersdal, M., Spicher, F., Standovár, T., Świerkosz, K., Szczeńniak, E., Tóth, Z., Ujházy, K., Ujházyová, M., Vangansbeke, P., Vild, O., Wołkowycki, D., Wulf, M., Baeten, L., Rocchini, D., 2018. Observer and relocation errors matter in resurveys of historical vegetation plots. *Journal of Vegetation Science* 29, 812–823.
- Vittoz, P., Bayfield, N., Brooker, R., Elston, D.A., Duff, E.I., Theurillat, J.-P., Guisan, A., 2010. Reproducibility of species lists, visual cover estimates and frequency methods for recording high-mountain vegetation. *Journal of Vegetation Science* 21, 1035–1047.
- Vittoz, P., Guisan, A., 2007. How reliable is the monitoring of permanent vegetation plots? A test with multiple observers. *Journal of Vegetation Science* 18, 413–422.
- Yang, W., Liu, D., You, Q., Chen, B., Jian, M., Hu, Q., Cong, M., Ma, K., 2021. Taxonomic bias in occurrence information of angiosperm species in China. *Sci China Life Sci* 64, 584–592.
- Zhou, W., Cadenasso, M.L., 2012. Effects of patch characteristics and within patch heterogeneity on the accuracy of urban land cover estimates from visual interpretation. *Landscape Ecology* 27, 1291–1305.

Comparison between methods

- Bourdôt, G.W., Noble, A., Neal, J.C., 2024. Step-point sampling for broadleaved species' ground cover estimation in pastures – an evaluation of Cockayne's point on a boot toecap method. *New Zealand Journal of Agricultural Research* 68, 1017–1031.
- BRAKENHIELM, S., LIU, Q., 1995. COMPARISON OF FIELD METHODS IN VEGETATION MONITORING. *Water Air and Soil Pollution* 79, 75–87.
- Bürger, J., Kůzmič, F., Šilc, U., Jansen, F., Bergmeier, E., Chytrý, M., Cirujeda, A., Fogliatto, S., Fried, G., Dostatny, D.F., Gerowitt, B., Glemnitz, M., González-Andújar, J.L., Hernández Plaza, E., Izquierdo, J., Kolářová, M., Lososová, Z., Metcalfe, H., Nečajeva, J., Petit, S., Pinke, G., Rašomavičius, V., von Redwitz, C., Schumacher, M., Ulber, L., Vidotto, F., Jiménez-Alfaro, B., 2022. Two sides of one medal: Arable weed vegetation of Europe in phytosociological data compared to agronomical weed surveys. *Applied Vegetation Science* 25.
- Byrne, K.M., Lauenroth, W.K., Adler, P.B., Byrne, C.M., 2011. Estimating Aboveground Net Primary Production in Grasslands: A Comparison of Nondestructive Methods. *Rangeland Ecology & Management* 64, 498–505.
- Camiz, S., Torres, P., Pillar, V.D., 2017. Recoding and multidimensional analyses of vegetation data: a comparison. *Community Ecology* 18, 260–279.
- D'Antraccoli, M., Bacaro, G., Tordoni, E., Bedini, G., Peruzzi, L., 2020. More species, less effort: Designing and comparing sampling strategies to draft optimised floristic inventories. *Perspectives in Plant Ecology, Evolution and Systematics* 45.
- de Bello, F., Fibich, P., Zeleny, D., Kopecky, M., Mudrak, O., Chytry, M., Pysek, P., Wild, J., Michalcova, D., Sadlo, J., Smilauer, P., Leps, J., Partel, M., 2016. Measuring size and composition of species pools: a comparison of dark diversity estimates. *Ecol Evol* 6, 4088–4101.
- FLOYD, D., ANDERSON, J., 1987. A COMPARISON OF 3 METHODS FOR ESTIMATING PLANT COVER. *Journal of Ecology* 75, 221–228.

- Furman, B.T., Leone, E.H., Bell, S.S., Durako, M.J., Hall, M.O., 2018. Braun-Blanquet data in ANOVA designs: comparisons with percent cover and transformations using simulated data. *Marine Ecology Progress Series* 597, 13–22.
- Godínez-Alvarez, H., Herrick, J.E., Mattocks, M., Toledo, D., Van Zee, J., 2009. Comparison of three vegetation monitoring methods: Their relative utility for ecological assessment and monitoring. *Ecological Indicators* 9, 1001–1008.
- Hájek, M., Peterka, T., Hájková, P., Hinterlang, D., Zechmeister, H., Chytrý, M., 2024. Proposal (36) to conserve the name *Philonotidion seriatae* Hinterlang 1992 for the species-poor, bryophyte-dominated, non-calcareous arctic-alpine spring vegetation of Europe. *Vegetation Classification and Survey* 5, 11–15.
- Hijbeek, R., Koedam, N., Khan, M.N., Kairo, J.G., Schoukens, J., Dahdouh-Guebas, F., 2013. An Evaluation of Plotless Sampling Using Vegetation Simulations and Field Data from a Mangrove Forest. *PLoS One* 8, e67201.
- Killeffer, C.R., Raphael, J., Ries, L., Underwood, H.B., 2019. A rapid assessment method for ground layer coastal vegetation. *Journal of Coastal Conservation* 23, 1047–1055.
- Kutcher, T.E., Forrester, G.E., 2018. Evaluating how variants of floristic quality assessment indicate wetland condition. *J Environ Manage* 217, 231–239.
- Laliberté, E., Norton, D.A., Tylianakis, J.M., Scott, D., 2010. Comparison of Two Sampling Methods for Quantifying Changes in Vegetation Composition Under Rangeland Development. *Rangeland Ecology & Management* 63, 537–545.
- Lewis, R.J., Szava-Kovats, R., Pärtel, M., Isaac, N., 2015. Estimating dark diversity and species pools: an empirical assessment of two methods. *Methods in Ecology and Evolution* 7, 104–113.
- Reisch, C., Schmid, C., Hartig, F., 2018. A comparison of methods for estimating plant population size. *Biodiversity and Conservation* 27, 2021–2028.
- Riedel, S., Widmer, S., Bringuier, O., Dengler, J., 2024. Cover vs. biomass sampling in grassland vegetation plots. *Tuexenia*.
- Tavernia, B.G., Lyons, J.E., Loges, B.W., Wilson, A., Collazo, J.A., Runge, M.C., 2015. An evaluation of rapid methods for monitoring vegetation characteristics of wetland bird habitat. *Wetlands Ecology and Management* 24, 495–505.
- Weber, K.T., Chen, F., Booth, D.T., Raza, M., Serr, K., Gokhale, B., 2013. Comparing Two Ground-Cover Measurement Methodologies for Semiarid Rangelands. *Rangeland Ecology & Management* 66, 82–87.
- Wilcox, R.C., Baniaga, A.E., Hill, A.P., Young, A., Johnson, R.F., Jacobs, S.J., 2025. Documenting biodiversity with digital data: comparing and contrasting the efficacy of specimen-based and observation-based approaches. *New Phytol.*

Detecting vegetation changes in time

- Bertin, R.I., Searcy, K.B., Motzkin, G., Hickler, M.G., Grima, P.P., 2022. Two Centuries of Change in the Native Flora of Franklin County, Massachusetts, U.S.A. *Rhodora* 123.
- Bowles, M., Jones, M., 2006. Testing the efficacy of species richness and floristic quality assessment of quality, temporal change, and fire effects in tallgrass prairie natural areas. *Natural Areas Journal* 26, 17–30.
- Buldrini, F., Alessandrini, A., Muzzi, E., Krebs, P., Conedera, M., Pezzi, G., 2022. Historical Floras: addressing their genesis in order to be viewed from a modern-day perspective. A case study from Northern Italy. *Rendiconti Lincei. Scienze Fisiche e Naturali* 34, 143–167.
- Chytrý, M., Tichý, L., Hennekens, S., Schaminée, J., 2014. Assessing vegetation change using vegetation-plot databases: a risky business. *Applied Vegetation Science* 17, 32–41.
- Dagnachew, S., Teketay, D., Demissew, S., Awas, T., Kindu, M., 2022. Herbarium-based study of flowering and fruiting phenology of twelve indigenous and endemic plant species from Ethiopia. *South African Journal of Botany* 150, 260–274.

- Durak, T., Bugno-Pogoda, A., Durak, R., 2021. Application of forest inventories to assess the forest developmental stages on plots dedicated to long-term vegetation studies. *Forest Ecology and Management* 489.
- Eichenberg, D., Bowler, D.E., Bonn, A., Bruelheide, H., Grescho, V., Harter, D., Jandt, U., May, R., Winter, M., Jansen, F., 2020. Widespread decline in Central European plant diversity across six decades. *Glob Chang Biol*.
- Goury, R., Thuiller, W., Abdulhak, S., Pache, G., Van Es, J., Bowler, D.E., Renaud, J., Violle, C., Münkemüller, T., 2025. Recent vegetation shifts in the French Alps with winners outnumbering losers. *Journal of Ecology*.
- Haveman, R., Janssen, J.A.M., 2008. The analysis of long-term changes in plant communities using large databases: The effect of stratified resampling. *Journal of Vegetation Science* 19, 355–362.
- Huwer, A., Wittig, R., 2012. Changes in the species composition of hedgerows in the Westphalian Basin over a thirty-five-year period. *Tuexenia*, 31–53.
- Johns, C.V., Brownstein, G., Blick, R.A.J., Erskine, P.D., Fletcher, A.T., 2015. Testing the Power of a Wetland Vegetation Monitoring Survey Design to Detect Change Based on Visual Cover Estimates. *Wetlands* 35, 1055–1064.
- Kambach, S., Jandt, U., Acosta, A., Álvarez-Martínez, J., Bazzichetto, M., Bergmeier, E., Bernhardt-Römermann, M., Carboni, M., Carlucci, M., Carranza, M., 2025. Habitat-specific trends in taxonomic, functional, and phylogenetic diversity in European plant communities during the last 100 years.
- KETCHLEDGE, E., LEONARD, R., 1984. A 24-YEAR COMPARISON OF THE VEGETATION OF AN ADIRONDACK MOUNTAIN SUMMIT. *Rhodora* 86, 439–444.
- Klinkovská, K., Glaser, M., Danihelka, J., Kaplan, Z., Knollová, I., Novotný, P., Pyšek, P., Řezníčková, M., Wild, J., Chytrý, M., 2024. Dynamics of the Czech flora over the last 60 years: Winners, losers and causes of changes. *Biological Conservation* 292.
- Muller, S., 2015. Relevance of herbaria for the knowledge of the spatiotemporal dynamics of the biological invasions. *Revue D Ecologie-La Terre Et La Vie* 70, 229–235.
- Newton, A.C., Walls, R.M., Golicher, D., Keith, S.A., Diaz, A., Bullock, J.M., 2011. Structure, composition and dynamics of a calcareous grassland metacommunity over a 70-year interval. *Journal of Ecology* 100, 196–209.
- Nguyen, V., Greenville, A.C., Dickman, C.R., Wardle, G.M., 2015. On the validity of visual cover estimates for time series analyses: a case study of hummock grasslands. *Plant Ecology* 216, 975–988.
- Sabatini, F.M., Musciano, M.D., Chiarucci, A., 2025. Using Yearly-Resolved Time Series to Disentangle Interannual Variability, Directional Change, and Pseudoturnover in Plant Community Composition. *Journal of Vegetation Science* 36.
- Sanders, A., Childs, M., Traub, E., Jones, J., 2015. An Analysis of Long-term Data Consistency and a Proposal to Standardize Flower Survey Methods for the EISI Pollinator Project.
- Stroh, P.A., Pescott, O.L., Mountford, J.O., 2017. Long-term changes in lowland calcareous grassland plots using *Tephrosia integrifolia* subsp. *integrifolia* as an indicator species. *Plant Ecology* 218, 1269–1281.
- Török, K., Szitár, K., 2010. Long-term changes of rock grassland communities in Hungary. *Community Ecology* 11, 68–76.
- Yannelli, F.A., Bazzichetto, M., Conradi, T., Pattison, Z., Andrade, B.O., Anibaba, Q.A., Bonari, G., Chelli, S., Čuk, M., Damasceno, G., Fantinato, E., Geange, S.R., Guuroh, R.T., Holle, M.J.M., Kuzmič, F., Lembrechts, J.J., Mosyafiani, A., Šikuljak, T., Teixeira, J., Tordoni, E., Pérez-Valladares, C.X., Sperandii, M.G., de Bello, F., 2022. Fifteen emerging challenges and opportunities for vegetation science: A horizon scan by early career researchers. *Journal of Vegetation Science* 33.

- Begley-Miller, D.R., Diefenbach, D.R., McDill, M.E., Rosenberry, C.S., Just, E.H., 2018. Evaluating Inter-Rater Reliability and Statistical Power of Vegetation Measures Assessing Deer Impact. *Forests* 9.
- Cirkel, D.G., Witte, J.P.M., van Bodegom, P.M., Nijp, J.J., van der Zee, S.E.A.T.M., 2012. The influence of spatiotemporal variability and adaptations to hypoxia on empirical relationships between soil acidity and vegetation. *Ecohydrology* 7, 21–32.
- Diekmann, M., Kühne, A., Isermann, M., 2007. Random its non-random sampling:: Effects on patterns of species abundance, species richness and vegetation-environment relationships. *Folia Geobotanica* 42, 179–190.
- Futschik, A., Winkler, M., Steinbauer, K., Lamprecht, A., Rumpf, S.B., Barančok, P., Palaj, A., Gottfried, M., Pauli, H., Bartha, S., 2019. Disentangling observer error and climate change effects in long-term monitoring of alpine plant species composition and cover. *Journal of Vegetation Science* 31, 14–25.
- Grange, M., Munoz, F., Moretti, M., Varona-Y-Varona, S., Renaud, J., Colace, M., Gueguen, M., Gallien, L., 2021. Designing sampling protocols for plant-pollinator interactions-timing, meteorology, flowering variations and failed captures matter. *Botany Letters* 168, 324–332.
- Krahner, A., Dietzsch, A.C., Jutte, T., Pistorius, J., Everaars, J., 2024. Standardising bee sampling: A systematic review of pan trapping and associated floral surveys. *Ecol Evol* 14, e11157.
- Tichý, L., Hájek, M., Zelený, D., 2010. Imputation of environmental variables for vegetation plots based on compositional similarity. *Journal of Vegetation Science* 21, 88–95.
- van Cauter, A., Kerley, G., Cowling, R., 2005. The consequence of inaccuracies in remote-sensed vegetation boundaries for modelled mammal population estimates. *South African Journal of Wildlife Research* 35, 155–161.
- Vernham, G., Bailey, Joseph J., Field, R., Schrod, F., 2024. What is the Relationship Between Plant Trait Diversity and Geodiversity? A Plot-Based, Pan-European Analysis. *Global Ecology and Biogeography* 33.
- Zhang, J., Xiao, C., Duan, X., Gao, X., Zeng, H., Dong, R., Feng, G., Ma, K., 2024. Species' geographical range, environmental range and traits lead to specimen collection preference of dominant plant species of grasslands in Northern China. *Plant Divers* 46, 353–361.

New technologies for plant cover description in-situ

- Belcore, E., Latella, M., Piras, M., Camporeale, C., 2024. Enhancing precision in coastal dunes vegetation mapping: ultra-high resolution hierarchical classification at the individual plant level. *International Journal of Remote Sensing* 45, 4527–4552.
- Broussard, W.P., Visser, J.M., Brooks, R.P., 2020. Quantifying Vegetation and Landscape Metrics with Hyperspatial Unmanned Aircraft System Imagery in a Coastal Oligohaline Marsh. *Estuaries and Coasts* 45, 1058–1069.
- Černá, L., Chytrý, M., 2005. Supervised classification of plant communities with artificial neural networks. *Journal of Vegetation Science* 16, 407–414.
- de Simone, L., Fanfarillo, E., Maccherini, S., Fiaschi, T., Alfonso, G., Angelini, F., Garabini, M., Angiolini, C., 2024. One small step for a robot, one giant leap for habitat monitoring: A structural survey of EU forest habitats with Robotically-mounted Mobile Laser Scanning (RMLS). *Ecological Indicators* 160.
- Elvekjaer, N., Martinez-Sanchez, L., Bonnet, P., Joly, A., Paracchini, M.L., van der Velde, M., 2024. Detecting flowers on imagery with computer vision to improve continental scale grassland biodiversity surveying. *Ecological Solutions and Evidence* 5.
- Gallegos Torell, Å., Glimskär, A., 2009. Computer-aided calibration for visual estimation of vegetation cover. *Journal of Vegetation Science* 20, 973–983.
- Hu, Y., Si-Moussi, S., Thuiller, W., 2024. Introduction to deep learning methods for multi-species predictions. *Methods in Ecology and Evolution* 16, 228–246.

- Luscier, J.D., Thompson, W.L., Wilson, J.M., Gorham, B.E., Dragut, L.D., 2006. Using digital photographs and object-based image analysis to estimate percent ground cover in vegetation plots. *Frontiers in Ecology and the Environment* 4, 408–413.
- Mahecha, M.D., Rzanny, M., Kraemer, G., Mäder, P., Seeland, M., Wäldchen, J., 2021. Crowd-sourced plant occurrence data provide a reliable description of macroecological gradients. *Ecography* 44, 1131–1142.
- Marcenò, C., Padullés Cubino, J., Chytrý, M., Genduso, E., Salemi, D., La Rosa, A., Gristina, A.S., Agrillo, E., Bonari, G., Giusso del Galdo, G., Ilardi, V., Landucci, F., Guarino, R., 2021. Facebook groups as citizen science tools for plant species monitoring. *Journal of Applied Ecology* 58, 2018–2028.
- Müller, P., Puliti, S., Breidenbach, J., 2025. Towards enhancing field-based vegetation monitoring: A deep learning approach for species coverage estimation from ground-level imagery. *Methods in Ecology and Evolution* 16, 949–957.
- Rucinska, A., Olszak, M., Swierszcz, S., Nobis, M., Zubek, S., Kusza, G., Boczkowska, M., Nowak, A., 2021. Looking for Hidden Enemies of Metabarcoding: Species Composition, Habitat and Management Can Strongly Influence DNA Extraction while Examining Grassland Communities. *Biomolecules* 11.
- Rucińska, A., Świerszcz, S., Nobis, M., Zubek, S., Boczkowska, M., Olszak, M., Kosiński, J.G., Nowak, S., Nowak, A., 2022. Is it possible to understand a book missing a quarter of the letters? Unveiling the belowground species richness of grasslands. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment* 324.
- Sellers, H.L., Vargas Zesati, S.A., Elmendorf, S.C., Locher, A., Oberbauer, S.F., Tweedie, C.E., Witharana, C., Hollister, R.D., 2023. Can Plot-Level Photographs Accurately Estimate Tundra Vegetation Cover in Northern Alaska? *Remote Sensing* 15.
- Silva, C.M., Azevedo, A.M.s., Mozelli, L.A., Almeida, E.F.A., Brandão Junior, D.d.S., 2025. Deep learning in flower quantification of *Catharanthus roseus* (L.) G. Don. *Acta Scientiarum. Technology* 47.
- Sookhan, N., Sookhan, S., Grewal, D., MacIvor, J.S., 2024. Automating field-based floral surveys with machine learning. *Ecological Solutions and Evidence* 5.
- Woźniak, G., Dyderski, M.K., Kompała-Bąba, A., Jagodziński, A.M., Pasierbiński, A., Błońska, A., Bierza, W., Magurno, F., Sierka, E., 2020. Use of remote sensing to track postindustrial vegetation development. *Land Degradation & Development* 32, 1426–1439.

Appendix 2 Results of the CiteSpace mapping.

Appendix 2 Figure 1 Clusters of the total set of articles with citation network in 2015.

Appendix 2 Figure 2 Clusters timeline of the total set of articles with citation network in 2025.

Appendix 2 Table 1 Clusters summary.

Appendix 2 Table 2 Cluster 0.

Appendix 2 Table 3 Cluster 1.

Appendix 2 Table 4 Cluster 2.

Appendix 2 Table 5 Cluster 3.

Appendix 2 Table 6 Cluster 4.

Appendix 2 Table 7 Cluster 5.

Appendix 2 Table 8 Cluster 6.

Appendix 2 Table 9 Cluster 7.

Appendix 2 Table 10 Cluster 8.

Appendix 2 Table 11 Cluster 9.

Appendix 2 Table 12 Cluster 10.

Appendix 2 Table 13 Cluster 11.

Appendix 2 Table 14 Cluster 12.

Appendix 2 Figure 1 Clusters of the total set of articles with citation network in 2015.

Appendix 2 Figure 2 Clusters timeline of the total set of articles with citation network in 2025.

Appendix 2 Table 1 Clusters summary.

ClusterID	Size	Silhouette	mean(Year)	Label (LSI)	Label (LLR)	Label (MI)
0	197	0.82	2020	genomic resource; hill number; deriving indicator; endothermic species; iberian dung beetle tree species; coverage gap; genomic resource; overcoming sampling biases; hill number	species occurrence data (1055.9, 1.0E-4); terrestrial fauna (813.32, 1.0E-4); community science (745.98, 1.0E-4); global distribution (648.39, 1.0E-4); big data (648.09, 1.0E-4)	northwestern coast (1.76); field study (1.76); hie
1	169	0.877	2004	representative plot network; shrubland communities; actual stage; trebon basin; species pool urban vegetation; different cultivation type; plant communities; diagnostic species; heterogeneity-constrained random resampling	czech republic (2415.44, 1.0E-4); alien plant (1586.01, 1.0E-4); weed vegetation (1067, 1.0E-4); global index (943.51, 1.0E-4); man-made habitat (697.81, 1.0E-4)	northwestern coast (0.59); field study (0.59); hie
2	127	0.841	2015	reproductive phenology; global inventory; floristic change; plant communities; local extinction global inventory; floristic change; historic phenology; local extinction; central role	phenological research (843.9, 1.0E-4); neotropical biodiversity (819.74, 1.0E-4); extinction risk (795.58, 1.0E-4); digital accessible knowledge (791.56, 1.0E-4); survey effort (755.33, 1.0E-4)	northwestern coast (1.22); field study (1.22); hie
3	124	0.879	2009	desert mammal; mapping continuous field; light work-but; plant name; variable environment land management; recording species number; tree species; forest plant community change; urban ecology	citizen science (1460.53, 1.0E-4); bavarian alp (1426.38, 1.0E-4); mountain forest (886.18, 1.0E-4); atlas data (517.3, 1.0E-4); occupancy modelling (455.18, 1.0E-4)	investigating recommendation (0.39); northwestern
4	121	0.859	2018	slow decrease; grassland biodiversity hotspot; chiprovská planina; parasitic plant; class alnetea glutinosae slow decrease; chiprovská planina; nordic-baltic grassland vegetation database; large-extent mapping; hierarchical expert system	expert system (2238.17, 1.0E-4); vegetation classification (1128.12, 1.0E-4); alien plant invasion (952.25, 1.0E-4); fine-grain beta diversity (910.59, 1.0E-4); megadiverse country (862.74, 1.0E-4)	northwestern coast (1.72); field study (1.72); hie
5	110	0.845	2011	polish carpathian; agricultural matrix; hybrid ecosystem; spatial pattern; ecological indicator value lowland heath plant metacommunity; plant communities;	dry grassland vegetation (866.53, 1.0E-4); syntaxonomy ecology (803.66, 1.0E-4); vegetation diversity (479.88, 1.0E-4); classic vegetation ecology journal	disturbed site (0.47); quantifying species coloniz

				consistent classification; spatial scale; ecosystem mapping	(474.76, 1.0E-4); new profile (474.76, 1.0E-4)	
6	108	0.883	2020	dynamic habitat mosaic; directional turnover; farmland bird; terrestrial national park; common agricultural policy common plant species; floristic change; dynamic habitat mosaic; directional turnover; land use history	czech flora (792.68, 1.0E-4); biodiversity loss (758.56, 1.0E-4); modern research (733.47, 1.0E-4); open habitat (721.82, 1.0E-4); directional change (600.9, 1.0E-4)	northwestern coast (1.56); field study (1.56); hie
7	92	0.866	2014	directional turnover; plant communities; pre-fire vegetation drive; re-visitation study; using red list species loamy soil; historical charcoal burning; directional turnover; plant communities; conservation condition	tatra mt (1273.55, 1.0E-4); mountain summit (1047.33, 1.0E-4); nitrogen deposition (809.58, 1.0E-4); temporal change (754.79, 1.0E-4); agricultural landscape (740.71, 1.0E-4)	nanda devi (0.85); long-term forest vegetation dyn
8	91	0.914	2003	northern great plains vegetation; plant communities; testacean assemblage; vascular plant; regional species pool northern great plains vegetation; plant communities; vascular plant; regional species pool; natural fir-beech forest	fen terminology (265.51, 1.0E-4); habitat diversity (265.51, 1.0E-4); central european fen (265.51, 1.0E-4); testacean assemblage (260.26, 1.0E-4); complete base-richness gradient (260.26, 1.0E-4)	regional species pool (0.07); northwestern coast (
9	52	0.947	2010	habitat requirement; taxonomic challenges for; right target; standardized set; large-scale species distribution dataset ochrana prirody; vascular plant; czech republic; invasion pattern; checklist update	czech republic (438.19, 1.0E-4); plant invasion (213.47, 1.0E-4); taxonomic diversity (213.44, 1.0E-4); invasion pattern (213.44, 1.0E-4); checklist update (213.44, 1.0E-4)	field study (0.02); short-term population dynamics
10	46	0.966	2013	niche ecology; floristic richness; pollen-assemblage richness; plant diversity; recent development using decoy rare plant; explicit plant trait database; temporal plant cover; weed distribution; conservation value	wetland condition (757.29, 1.0E-4); functional ecology (431.01, 1.0E-4); floristic quality assessment (431.01, 1.0E-4); assessing among-lineage variability (423.43, 1.0E-4); functional trait dataset (423.43, 1.0E-4)	northwestern coast (0.17); ecological quality (0.1
11	39	0.958	2014	plant communities; biotic interaction; fragmented grassland; predicting species establishment; driving community composition pollen-assemblage richness;	dark diversity (720.01, 1.0E-4); species pool (403.7, 1.0E-4); community completeness (366.89, 1.0E-4); biotic	fragmented grassland (0.04); patch management isol

				plant diversity; multiple-study comparison; dark diversity concept; dry grassland	resource (262.84, 1.0E-4); empirical assessment (252.69, 1.0E-4)	
12	33	0.936	2021	dark host specificity; south africa; chinese native useful vascular plant; diversity hotspot; in-situ conservation typical forest; potential mechanism; complex environmental stress; alien species success; vegetation survey	dark diversity (617.07, 1.0E-4); post-industrial vegetation (279.18, 1.0E-4); same coin (279.18, 1.0E-4); habitat conservation status (279.18, 1.0E-4); drive community completeness (269.84, 1.0E-4)	spatial mismatch (0.06); in-situ conservation (0.0)
13	25	0.99	2006	forest road cutbank; rangeland mapping; landsat data; scale parameter; southern mongolian mountain range sage-grouse centrocercus urophasianus; nesting ecology; historic distribution; eastern edge; rangeland mapping	sage-grouse centrocercus urophasianus (314.65, 1.0E-4); historic distribution (314.65, 1.0E-4); eastern edge (314.65, 1.0E-4); nesting ecology (314.65, 1.0E-4); digital photograph analysis (136.06, 1.0E-4)	hierarchical object-based classification (0); rang
14	15	0.995	1998	association between lowland grassland plant communities and soil properties	association (22.19, 1.0E-4); lowland grassland plant communities (22.19, 1.0E-4); soil properties (22.19, 1.0E-4); vegetation classification (0.05, 1.0); citizen science (0.05, 1.0)	czech republic (0.01); vegetation classification (
15	13	1	2003	participatory forest monitoring; natural resource use; montane forest; forest quality; miombo woodland montane forest; natural resource use; participatory forest monitoring; forest quality; miombo woodland	monitoring matter (55.61, 1.0E-4); locally-based approaches (55.61, 1.0E-4); miombo woodland (36.95, 1.0E-4); natural resource use (36.95, 1.0E-4); forest quality (36.95, 1.0E-4)	czech republic (0.01); vegetation classification (
16	10	0.994	2004	tallgrass prairie; great lake; floristic quality index; coastal wetland; landscape v vegetation-based indicator; landscape v; plant community assembly; tallgrass prairie; relative influence	vegetation-based indicator (70.31, 1.0E-4); wetland restoration progress (70.31, 1.0E-4); local factor (52.61, 1.0E-4); relative influence (52.61, 1.0E-4); landscape v (52.61, 1.0E-4)	czech republic (0.01); vegetation classification (
18	9	0.978	1999	cover assessment; scale-dependent variation; vegetation monitoring; grassland plant cover; absence sampling long-term forest monitoring program; design concept; cover	design concept (57.41, 1.0E-4); long-term forest monitoring program (57.41, 1.0E-4); scale-dependent variation (38.1, 1.0E-	czech republic (0.01); vegetation classification (

				assessment; vegetation monitoring; absence sampling	4); grassland plant cover (38.1, 1.0E-4); absence sampling (18.96, 1.0E-4)	
19	8	0.977	2008	short-term variation; altitudinal gradient; wetland vegetation; vegetation resurvey; monitoring survey design weighting abundance; western balkan; semi-natural grassland; elevational gradient; forest species	weighting abundance (119.31, 1.0E-4); clonal trait (119.31, 1.0E-4); meadow management (119.31, 1.0E-4); plant trait-environment relationship (105.24, 1.0E-4); forest succession chronosequence (105.24, 1.0E-4)	czech republic (0.01); vegetation classification (
21	6	1	2000	conservation of lowland semi-natural grasslands in the uk: a review of botanical monitoring results from agri-environment schemes	botanical monitoring result (20.6, 1.0E-4); agri-environment scheme (20.6, 1.0E-4); conservation (20.6, 1.0E-4); lowland (20.6, 1.0E-4); review (20.6, 1.0E-4)	czech republic (0.01); vegetation classification (

Appendix 2 Table 2 Cluster 0

Coverage	GCS	LCS	Bibliography
19	66	0	Dengler, J (2023-JAN) Ecological indicator values for europe (eive) 1.0. VEGETATION CLASSIFICATION AND SURVEY DOI 10.3897/VCS.98324
17	140	0	Chytry, M (2021-JAN) Pladias database of the czech flora and vegetation. PRESLIA, V93, P87 DOI 10.23855/preslia.2021.001
16	11	0	Yannelli, FA (2022-JAN) Fifteen emerging challenges and opportunities for vegetation science: a horizon scan by early career researchers. JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V33, P18 DOI 10.1111/jvs.13119
15	220	0	Heberling, JM (2021-JAN) Data integration enables global biodiversity synthesis. PROCEEDINGS OF THE NATIONAL ACADEMY OF SCIENCES OF THE UNITED STATES OF AMERICA DOI 10.1073/pnas.2018093118
15	62	0	Biurrun, I (2021-JAN) Benchmarking plant diversity of palaeartic grasslands and other open habitats. JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V32, P21 DOI 10.1111/jvs.13050
14	84	0	Sabatini, FM (2021-JAN) Splotopen - an environmentally balanced, open-access, global dataset of vegetation plots. GLOBAL ECOLOGY AND BIOGEOGRAPHY, V30, P25 DOI 10.1111/geb.13346
14	4	0	Alfaro, E (2023-JAN) Rasgos-cl: a functional trait database of chilean woody plants. GLOBAL ECOLOGY AND BIOGEOGRAPHY, V32, P13 DOI 10.1111/geb.13755
13	21	0	Keppel, G (2021-JAN) Synthesizing tree biodiversity data to understand global patterns and processes of vegetation. JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V32, P14 DOI 10.1111/jvs.13021
13	8	0	Daru, BH (2025-JAN) Tracking hidden dimensions of plant biogeography from herbaria. NEW PHYTOLOGIST DOI 10.1111/nph.70002
13	8	0	Folk, RA (2021-JAN) Biodiversity at the global scale: the synthesis continues. AMERICAN JOURNAL OF BOTANY, V108, P13 DOI 10.1002/ajb2.1694
12	19	0	Arle, E (2021-JAN) Bracatus: a method to estimate the accuracy and biogeographical status of georeferenced biological data. METHODS IN ECOLOGY AND EVOLUTION, V12, P11 DOI 10.1111/2041-210X.13629
12	10	0	Ronquillo, C (2023-JAN) Exploring the impact of data curation criteria on the observed geographical distribution of mosses. ECOLOGY AND EVOLUTION, V13, P14 DOI 10.1002/ece3.10786
12	51	0	Ondo, I (2024-JAN) Plant diversity darkspots for global collection priorities. NEW PHYTOLOGIST, V244, P15 DOI 10.1111/nph.20024
12	2	0	Lopez-tobar, R (2023-JAN) Botanical collection patterns and conservation categories of the most traded timber species from the ecuadorian amazon: the role of protected areas. PLANTS-BASEL, V12, P20 DOI 10.3390/plants12183327

11	5	0	Craven, D (2021-JAN) Niche properties constrain occupancy but not abundance patterns of native and alien woody species across hawaiian forests . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V32, P15 DOI 10.1111/jvs.13025
11	45	0	Daru, BH (2023-JAN) Mass production of unvouchered records fails to represent global biodiversity patterns . NATURE ECOLOGY & EVOLUTION DOI 10.1038/s41559-023-02047-3
11	118	0	Sabatini, FM (2022-JAN) Global patterns of vascular plant alpha diversity . NATURE COMMUNICATIONS, V13, P16 DOI 10.1038/s41467-022-32063-z
11	2	0	Marchetto, E (2024-JAN) Addressing multiple facets of bias and uncertainty in continental-scale biodiversity databases . BIODIVERSITY INFORMATICS, V18, P22 DOI 10.5281/zenodo.12179384
11	0	0	Barreiro, K (2025-JAN) Species richness variation in marine and terrestrial fauna across widespread, fragmented territories: assessing inherent challenges of data scarcity at local and regional scales . SCIENTIFIC REPORTS, V15, P19 DOI 10.1038/s41598-025-06631-4
10	7	0	Essl, F (2021-JAN) New and old invaders in forests in eastern austria: the role of species attributes and invasion history . FLORA DOI 10.1016/j.flora.2021.151922
10	60	0	Albani, rocchetti G (2021-JAN) Reversing extinction trends: new uses of (old) herbarium specimens to accelerate conservation action on threatened species . NEW PHYTOLOGIST, V230, P18 DOI 10.1111/nph.17133
10	26	0	Lenzner, B (2021-JAN) Role of diversification rates and evolutionary history as a driver of plant naturalization success . NEW PHYTOLOGIST, V229, P11 DOI 10.1111/nph.17014
10	2	0	Fernandes, MF (2024-JAN) Knowledge gaps in legume diversity and distribution and prospects for future research . BRAZILIAN JOURNAL OF BOTANY, V48, P14 DOI 10.1007/s40415-024-01051-6
10	3	0	De, santis S (2023-JAN) Geographic range vs. occurrence records in plant distribution mapping: the case of arbutus in the old world . FORESTS, V14, P17 DOI 10.3390/f14051010
10	109	0	Cai, L (2023-JAN) Global models and predictions of plant diversity based on advanced machine learning techniques . NEW PHYTOLOGIST, V237, P14 DOI 10.1111/nph.18533
10	35	0	Axmanova, I (2021-JAN) Neophyte invasions in european grasslands . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V32, P17 DOI 10.1111/jvs.12994
10	29	0	Farooq, H (2021-JAN) Mapping africa's biodiversity: more of the same is just not good enough . SYSTEMATIC BIOLOGY, V70, P11 DOI 10.1093/sysbio/syaa090
10	1	0	Szymura, TH (2023-JAN) Vegetation databases augment but do not replace species distribution atlases in species richness assessment . ECOLOGICAL INDICATORS DOI 10.1016/j.ecolind.2023.110876
9	25	0	Sporbert, M (2021-JAN) Different sets of traits explain abundance and distribution patterns of european plants at different spatial scales .

			integrative approach to act urgently . BIOLOGICAL CONSERVATION DOI 10.1016/j.biocon.2023.110118
9	48	0	Feng, X (2022-JAN) A review of the heterogeneous landscape of biodiversity databases: opportunities and challenges for a synthesized biodiversity knowledge base . GLOBAL ECOLOGY AND BIOGEOGRAPHY, V31, P19 DOI 10.1111/geb.13497
9	27	0	Geurts, EM (2023-JAN) Turning observations into biodiversity data: broadscale spatial biases in community science . ECOSPHERE, V14, P13 DOI 10.1002/ecs2.4582
9	1	0	Camila, pacheco-riano L (2024-JAN) Reliability of presence-only data for assessing plant community responses to climate warming . ECOGRAPHY, V2024, P11 DOI 10.1111/ecog.07213
9	15	0	Omer, A (2021-JAN) Characteristics of the naturalized flora of southern africa largely reflect the non-random introduction of alien species for cultivation . ECOGRAPHY, V44, P14 DOI 10.1111/ecog.05669
8	0	0	Clement, RA (2025-JAN) Addressing biological invasions in agriculture with big data in an informatics age . AGRICULTURE-BASEL, V15, P34 DOI 10.3390/agriculture15111157
8	36	0	Andrew, SC (2021-JAN) Functional diversity of the australian flora: strong links to species richness and climate . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V32, P14 DOI 10.1111/jvs.13018
8	14	0	Lannuzel, G (2022-JAN) Mining rare earth elements: identifying the plant species most threatened by ore extraction in an insular hotspot . FRONTIERS IN ECOLOGY AND EVOLUTION, V10, P13 DOI 10.3389/fevo.2022.952439
8	52	0	Bachman, SP (2024-JAN) Extinction risk predictions for the world's flowering plants to support their conservation . NEW PHYTOLOGIST, V242, P12 DOI 10.1111/nph.19592
8	1	0	Domazetoski, V (2025-JAN) Using large language models to extract plant functional traits from unstructured text . APPLICATIONS IN PLANT SCIENCES, V13, P14 DOI 10.1002/aps3.70011
8	0	0	Szymura, TH (2024-JAN) Spatial patterns of vascular plant species richness in poland: relations among species group richness and hot spot distribution . ACTA SOCIETATIS BOTANICORUM POLONIAE, V93, P13 DOI 10.5586/asbp/192897
8	9	0	Kusumoto, B (2023-JAN) Occurrence-based diversity estimation reveals macroecological and conservation knowledge gaps for global woody plants . SCIENCE ADVANCES DOI 10.1126/sciadv.adh9719
8	1	0	Trindade, WCF (2024-JAN) The invisible species: big data unveil coverage gaps in the atlantic forest hotspot . DIVERSITY AND DISTRIBUTIONS, V30, P13 DOI 10.1111/ddi.13931
8	12	0	Pouteau, R (2021-JAN) Potential alien ranges of european plants will shrink in the future, but less so for already naturalized than for not yet naturalized species . DIVERSITY AND DISTRIBUTIONS, V27, P14 DOI 10.1111/ddi.13378

8	52	0	Meineke, EK (2021-JAN) Bias assessments to expand research harnessing biological collections . TRENDS IN ECOLOGY & EVOLUTION, V36, P12 DOI 10.1016/j.tree.2021.08.003
8	4	0	de, melo PHA (2024-JAN) A new r package to parse plant species occurrence records into unique collection events efficiently reduces data redundancy . SCIENTIFIC REPORTS DOI 10.1038/s41598-024-56158-3
8	19	0	Corlett, RT (2023-JAN) Achieving zero extinction for land plants . TRENDS IN PLANT SCIENCE, V28, P11 DOI 10.1016/j.tplants.2023.03.019
8	7	0	de, bello F (2025-JAN) Raunkiæran shortfalls: challenges and perspectives in trait-based ecology . ECOLOGICAL MONOGRAPHS, V95, P26 DOI 10.1002/ecm.70018
8	4	0	Minev-benzecry, S (2024-JAN) Climate change alters the future of natural floristic regions of deep evolutionary origins . NATURE COMMUNICATIONS, V15, P10 DOI 10.1038/s41467-024-53860-8
8	30	0	Auffret, AG (2022-JAN) Climate warming has compounded plant responses to habitat conversion in northern europe . NATURE COMMUNICATIONS, V13, P11 DOI 10.1038/s41467-022-35516-7
7	0	0	Wilcox, RC (2025-JAN) Documenting biodiversity with digital data: comparing and contrasting the efficacy of specimen-based and observation-based approaches . NEW PHYTOLOGIST DOI 10.1111/nph.70406
7	12	0	Fratte, MD (2022-JAN) Identifying typical and early warning species by the combination of functional-based diagnostic species and dark diversity . BIODIVERSITY AND CONSERVATION, V31, P19 DOI 10.1007/s10531-022-02427-4
7	27	0	Rapacciuolo, G (2021-JAN) Deriving indicators of biodiversity change from unstructured community-contributed data . OIKOS, V130, P15 DOI 10.1111/oik.08215
7	79	0	Maeder, P (2021-JAN) The flora incognita app - interactive plant species identification . METHODS IN ECOLOGY AND EVOLUTION DOI 10.1111/2041-210X.13611
7	110	0	Schneider, FD (2020-JAN) Towards mapping the diversity of canopy structure from space with gedi . ENVIRONMENTAL RESEARCH LETTERS, V15, P15 DOI 10.1088/1748-9326/ab9e99
7	1	0	Patterson, CR (2025-JAN) A multidimensional assessment of antarctic terrestrial biological data . DIVERSITY AND DISTRIBUTIONS, V31, P16 DOI 10.1111/ddi.13909
7	0	0	Svahnstrom, VJ (2025-JAN) Geographic range size and rarity of epiphytic flowering plants . NATURE PLANTS, V11, P17 DOI 10.1038/s41477-025-02022-9
7	0	0	Goury, R (2025-JAN) Recent vegetation shifts in the french alps with winners outnumbering losers . JOURNAL OF ECOLOGY DOI 10.1111/1365-2745.70159
7	194	0	Santini, L (2021-JAN) Assessing the reliability of species distribution projections in climate change research . DIVERSITY AND DISTRIBUTIONS, V27, P16 DOI 10.1111/ddi.13252

7	0	0	Schmidt, RJ (2025-JAN) The collector practices that shape spatial, temporal, and taxonomic bias in herbaria . NEW PHYTOLOGIST DOI 10.1111/nph.70297
7	187	0	Shi, W (2024-JAN) Near-unity nir phosphorescent quantum yield from a room-temperature solvated metal nanocluster . SCIENCE DOI 10.1126/science.adk6628
7	36	0	Marceno, C (2021-JAN) Facebook groups as citizen science tools for plant species monitoring . JOURNAL OF APPLIED ECOLOGY, V58, P11 DOI 10.1111/1365-2664.13896
7	2	0	Swain, H (2024-JAN) Science behind herbarium and its importance in recent years . NORDIC JOURNAL OF BOTANY, V2024, P10 DOI 10.1111/njb.04499
7	1	0	Rivera, R (2024-JAN) Latitudinal diversity of planktonic copepods in the eastern pacific: overcoming sampling biases and predicting patterns . FRONTIERS IN ECOLOGY AND EVOLUTION, V12, P13 DOI 10.3389/fevo.2024.1305916
7	7	0	Happonen, K (2021-JAN) Trait-based responses to land use and canopy dynamics modify long-term diversity changes in forest understories . GLOBAL ECOLOGY AND BIOGEOGRAPHY, V30, P13 DOI 10.1111/geb.13351
7	23	0	Tordoni, E (2021-JAN) Disentangling native and alien plant diversity in coastal sand dune ecosystems worldwide . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V32, P13 DOI 10.1111/jvs.12961
7	21	0	Chowdhury, S (2023-JAN) Increasing biodiversity knowledge through social media: a case study from tropical bangladesh . BIOSCIENCE DOI 10.1093/biosci/biad042
7	15	0	Bobrowski, M (2021-JAN) Searching for ecology in species distribution models in the himalayas . ECOLOGICAL MODELLING, V458, P14 DOI 10.1016/j.ecolmodel.2021.109693
7	13	0	Lyu, L (2022-JAN) An integrated high-resolution mapping shows congruent biodiversity patterns of fagales and pinales . NEW PHYTOLOGIST, V235, P14 DOI 10.1111/nph.18158
6	58	0	Thomas, HJD (2019-JAN) Traditional plant functional groups explain variation in economic but not size-related traits across the tundra biome . GLOBAL ECOLOGY AND BIOGEOGRAPHY, V28, P18 DOI 10.1111/geb.12783
6	0	0	Lombardi, EM (2024-JAN) Synthesizing historical plant collections to identify priorities for future collection efforts and research applications . ECOSPHERE, V15, P21 DOI 10.1002/ecs2.70102
6	10	0	Chanachai, J (2024-JAN) What remains to be discovered: a global assessment of tree species inventory completeness . DIVERSITY AND DISTRIBUTIONS, V30, P16 DOI 10.1111/ddi.13862
6	21	0	Cutts, V (2021-JAN) Scientific floras can be reliable sources for some trait data in a system with poor coverage in global trait databases . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V32, P11 DOI 10.1111/jvs.12996
6	5	0	Dubose, TP (2023-JAN) Mismatch between conservation status and climate change sensitivity leaves some anurans in the united states

			unprotected . BIOLOGICAL CONSERVATION, V277, P10 DOI 10.1016/j.biocon.2022.109866
6	22	0	Chowdhury, S (2024-JAN) Using social media records to inform conservation planning . CONSERVATION BIOLOGY, V38, P11 DOI 10.1111/cobi.14161
6	31	0	Guo, W (2022-JAN) High exposure of global tree diversity to human pressure . PROCEEDINGS OF THE NATIONAL ACADEMY OF SCIENCES OF THE UNITED STATES OF AMERICA, V119, P11 DOI 10.1073/pnas.2026733119
6	7	0	Chowdhury, S (2024-JAN) A protocol for harvesting biodiversity data from facebook . CONSERVATION BIOLOGY, V38, P10 DOI 10.1111/cobi.14257
6	22	0	Boyd, RJ (2021-JAN) Occassess: an r package for assessing potential biases in species occurrence data . ECOLOGY AND EVOLUTION, V11, P11 DOI 10.1002/ece3.8299
6	1	0	Lessa, T (2024-JAN) Quantifying spatial ignorance in the effort to collect terrestrial fauna in namibia, africa . ECOLOGICAL INDICATORS, V158, P10 DOI 10.1016/j.ecolind.2023.111490
6	17	0	Pang, SEH (2022-JAN) Occurrence-habitat mismatching and niche truncation when modelling distributions affected by anthropogenic range contractions . DIVERSITY AND DISTRIBUTIONS, V28, P17 DOI 10.1111/ddi.13544
6	44	0	Boyd, RJ (2022-JAN) Robitt: a tool for assessing the risk-of-bias in studies of temporal trends in ecology . METHODS IN ECOLOGY AND EVOLUTION, V13, P11 DOI 10.1111/2041-210X.13857
6	0	0	Humphreys, AM (2025-JAN) Harnessing the benefits of herbarium specimen digitisation for inferring recent and ongoing plant extinctions . NEW PHYTOLOGIST DOI 10.1111/nph.70552
6	26	0	Eckert, I (2024-JAN) Herbarium collections remain essential in the age of community science . NATURE COMMUNICATIONS, V15, P12 DOI 10.1038/s41467-024-51899-1
6	5	0	Ronquillo, C (2024-JAN) Occur shiny application: a user-friendly guide for curating species occurrence records . METHODS IN ECOLOGY AND EVOLUTION DOI 10.1111/2041-210X.14271
6	24	0	Paertel, J (2021-JAN) Plant image identification application demonstrates high accuracy in northern europe . AOB PLANTS, V13, P10 DOI 10.1093/aobpla/plab050
6	0	0	Baasanmunkh, S (2025-JAN) Inaturalist projects represent a valuable resource for aggregating plant observations and engaging society: a case study of the flora of mongolia project . PLANTS PEOPLE PLANET DOI 10.1002/ppp3.70054
6	10	0	Backstrom, LJ (2025-JAN) Estimating sampling biases in citizen science datasets . IBIS, V167, P15 DOI 10.1111/ibi.13343
6	12	0	Grattarola, F (2023-JAN) Integrating presence-only and presence-absence data to model changes in species geographic ranges: an example in the neotropics . JOURNAL OF BIOGEOGRAPHY, V50, P15 DOI 10.1111/jbi.14622

6	73	0	Grenie, M (2023-JAN) Harmonizing taxon names in biodiversity data: a review of tools, databases and best practices . METHODS IN ECOLOGY AND EVOLUTION, V14, P14 DOI 10.1111/2041-210X.13802
6	15	0	Mendes, SB (2024-JAN) Evidence of a european seed dispersal crisis . SCIENCE DOI 10.1126/science.ado1464
6	7	0	Rodrigues, AV (2022-JAN) Species misidentification affects biodiversity metrics: dealing with this issue using the new r package naturalist . ECOLOGICAL INFORMATICS DOI 10.1016/j.ecoinf.2022.101625
6	3	0	Hughes, AC (2024-JAN) Big data, big problems? how to circumvent problems in biodiversity mapping and ensure meaningful results . ECOGRAPHY, V2024, P15 DOI 10.1111/ecog.07115
6	1	0	Schrodt, F (2025-JAN) Advancing causal inference in ecology: pathways for biodiversity change detection and attribution . METHODS IN ECOLOGY AND EVOLUTION, V16, P29 DOI 10.1111/2041-210X.70131
6	26	0	Dimson, M (2023-JAN) Citizen science can complement professional invasive plant surveys and improve estimates of suitable habitat . DIVERSITY AND DISTRIBUTIONS, V29, P16 DOI 10.1111/ddi.13749
5	22	0	Seebens, H (2022-JAN) Dasco: a workflow to downscale alien species checklists using occurrence records and to re-allocate species distributions across realms . NEOBIOTA, V74, P17 DOI 10.3897/neobiota.74.81082
5	21	0	Thonicke, K (2020-JAN) Simulating functional diversity of european natural forests along climatic gradients . JOURNAL OF BIOGEOGRAPHY, V47, P17 DOI 10.1111/jbi.13809
5	8	0	Walker, BE (2023-JAN) Evidence-based guidelines for automated conservation assessments of plant species . CONSERVATION BIOLOGY, V37, P12 DOI 10.1111/cobi.13992
5	14	0	Bryn, A (2021-JAN) Reliability in distribution modeling - a synthesis and step-by-step guidelines for improved practice . FRONTIERS IN ECOLOGY AND EVOLUTION DOI 10.3389/fevo.2021.658713
5	1	0	Werner, M (2024-JAN) Instagram data for validating nothofagus pumilio distribution mapping in the southern andes: a novel ground truthing approach . FRONTIERS OF BIOGEOGRAPHY, V17, P17 DOI 10.21425/fob.17.140606
5	6	0	Daru, BH (2024-JAN) Predicting undetected native vascular plant diversity at a global scale . PROCEEDINGS OF THE NATIONAL ACADEMY OF SCIENCES OF THE UNITED STATES OF AMERICA DOI 10.1073/pnas.2319989121
5	5	0	Pfeiffer, J (2024-JAN) Synthesis of natural history collections data reveals patterns of us freshwater mussel diversity and decline . BIOLOGICAL CONSERVATION, V291, P11 DOI 10.1016/j.biocon.2024.110462
5	5	0	Richard-bollans, A (2023-JAN) Machine learning enhances prediction of plants as potential sources of antimalarials . FRONTIERS IN PLANT SCIENCE, V14, P14 DOI 10.3389/fpls.2023.1173328
5	29	0	Schellenberger, costa D (2023-JAN) The big four of plant taxonomy - a comparison of global checklists of vascular plant names . NEW PHYTOLOGIST, V240, P16 DOI 10.1111/nph.18961

5	3	0	Tack, W (2022-JAN) The ecat dataset: expert-validated distribution data of endemic and sub-endemic trees of central africa (dem. rep. congo, rwanda, burundi) . PHYTOKEYS DOI 10.3897/phytokeys.206.77379
5	6	0	Borgelt, J (2024-JAN) What is the impact of accidentally transporting terrestrial alien species? a new life cycle impact assessment model . ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCE & TECHNOLOGY, V58, P14 DOI 10.1021/acs.est.3c08500
5	234	0	Jung, M (2021-JAN) Areas of global importance for conserving terrestrial biodiversity, carbon and water . NATURE ECOLOGY & EVOLUTION DOI 10.1038/s41559-021-01528-7
5	0	0	Jackowiak, B (2025-JAN) How does sharing data from research institutions on global biodiversity information facility enhance its scientific value? . DIVERSITY-BASEL, V17, P25 DOI 10.3390/d17040221
5	1	0	Lobo, JM (2023-JAN) Taking advantage of opportunistically collected historical occurrence data to detect responses to climate change: the case of temperature and iberian dung beetles . ECOLOGY AND EVOLUTION, V13, P18 DOI 10.1002/ece3.10674
5	8	0	Borgelt, J (2022-JAN) Native range estimates for red-listed vascular plants . SCIENTIFIC DATA DOI 10.1038/s41597-022-01233-5
5	0	0	Shi, D (2025-JAN) How new plant species have been discovered in china: collection gaps and preferences over the past century . FRONTIERS IN PLANT SCIENCE, V16, P10 DOI 10.3389/fpls.2025.1605431
5	12	0	Ribeiro, BR (2022-JAN) Issues with species occurrence data and their impact on extinction risk assessments . BIOLOGICAL CONSERVATION DOI 10.1016/j.biocon.2022.109674
5	0	0	Beierkuhnlein, C (2025-JAN) Towards a comprehensive geodiversity-biodiversity nexus in terrestrial ecosystems . EARTH-SCIENCE REVIEWS, V264, P20 DOI 10.1016/j.earscirev.2025.105075
5	22	0	Mesaglio, T (2023-JAN) Photographs as an essential biodiversity resource: drivers of gaps in the vascular plant photographic record . NEW PHYTOLOGIST, V238, P10 DOI 10.1111/nph.18813
5	0	0	Prylutskyi, O (2024-JAN) State-of-the-art of inaturalist as a source of data on ukrainian fungi . CITIZEN SCIENCE-THEORY AND PRACTICE DOI 10.5334/cstp.717
5	0	0	Deomurari, A (2023-JAN) Potential range map dataset of indian birds . DATA DOI 10.3390/data8090144
5	36	0	Smith, AB (2023-JAN) Including imprecisely georeferenced specimens improves accuracy of species distribution models and estimates of niche breadth . GLOBAL ECOLOGY AND BIOGEOGRAPHY, V32, P14 DOI 10.1111/geb.13628
5	10	0	Fuehrding-potschkat, P (2022-JAN) Influence of different data cleaning solutions of point-occurrence records on downstream macroecological diversity models . ECOLOGY AND EVOLUTION, V12, P14 DOI 10.1002/ece3.9168
5	7	0	Nicolson, N (2023-JAN) Global access to nomenclatural botanical resources: evaluating open access availability . PLANTS PEOPLE PLANET DOI 10.1002/ppp3.10438

5	9	0	Cubino, JP (2022-JAN) The effect of niche filtering on plant species abundance in temperate grassland communities . FUNCTIONAL ECOLOGY, V36, P12 DOI 10.1111/1365-2435.13994
5	8	0	Deomurari, A (2023-JAN) Projected shifts in bird distribution in india under climate change . DIVERSITY-BASEL, V15, P19 DOI 10.3390/d15030404
5	1	0	Shweta, S (2024-JAN) Herbaria: a valuable resource of the time treasured historic plant specimens with boundless research potential for environmental sustainability . ENVIRONMENT DEVELOPMENT AND SUSTAINABILITY DOI 10.1007/s10668-024-05301-1
4	3	0	Kermavnar, J (2023-JAN) More losses than gains? distribution models predict species-specific shifts in climatic suitability for european beech forest herbs under climate change . FRONTIERS IN FORESTS AND GLOBAL CHANGE DOI 10.3389/ffgc.2023.1236842
4	14	0	Dimson, M (2023-JAN) Who, where, when: observer behavior influences spatial and temporal patterns of inaturalist participation . APPLIED GEOGRAPHY, V153, P11 DOI 10.1016/j.apgeog.2023.102916
4	0	0	Lu, X (2025-JAN) Growing completeness of multitaxon biodiversity data from citizen science is associated with long-term socioeconomic advance in china . JOURNAL OF BIOGEOGRAPHY, V52, P14 DOI 10.1111/jbi.70020
4	6	0	Mcneillie, MJ (2021-JAN) Extending vegetation site data and ensemble models to predict patterns of foliage cover and species richness for plant functional groups . LANDSCAPE ECOLOGY, V36, P17 DOI 10.1007/s10980-021-01221-x
4	6	0	Schertler, A (2024-JAN) Biogeography and global flows of 100 major alien fungal and fungus-like oomycete pathogens . JOURNAL OF BIOGEOGRAPHY, V51, P19 DOI 10.1111/jbi.14755
4	8	0	Lanuza, JB (2025-JAN) Eupollnet: a european database of plant-pollinator networks . GLOBAL ECOLOGY AND BIOGEOGRAPHY, V34, P16 DOI 10.1111/geb.70000
4	24	0	Montti, L (2021-JAN) Predicting current and future global distribution of invasive ligustrum lucidum wt aiton: assessing emerging risks to biodiversity hotspots . DIVERSITY AND DISTRIBUTIONS, V27, P16 DOI 10.1111/ddi.13303
4	5	0	Ostermann-miyashita, E (2023-JAN) Opportunities and challenges for monitoring a recolonizing large herbivore using citizen science . ECOLOGY AND EVOLUTION, V13, P17 DOI 10.1002/ece3.10484
4	2	0	Swati, U (2023-JAN) A comprehensive database of squirrel distribution and occurrence in south asia . BIODIVERSITY DATA JOURNAL, V11, P16 DOI 10.3897/BDJ.11.e109946
4	2	0	Enriquez-de-salamanca, A (2025-JAN) Botanical databases in eia: opportunities and challenges . IMPACT ASSESSMENT AND PROJECT APPRAISAL, V43, P11 DOI 10.1080/14615517.2025.2482137
4	0	0	He, J (2025-JAN) Impacts of road networks on the geography of floristic collections in china . PLANT DIVERSITY, V47, P12 DOI 10.1016/j.pld.2025.02.001

4	34	0	Brandt, AJ (2021-JAN) Naturalised plants transform the composition and function of the new zealand flora . BIOLOGICAL INVASIONS, V23, P16 DOI 10.1007/s10530-020-02393-4
4	10	0	Terzi, M (2021-JAN) Effects of ailanthus altissima invasion and removal on high-biodiversity mediterranean grasslands . ENVIRONMENTAL MANAGEMENT, V68, P14 DOI 10.1007/s00267-021-01522-6
4	6	0	Mondain-monval, T (2024-JAN) Adaptive sampling by citizen scientists improves species distribution model performance: a simulation study . METHODS IN ECOLOGY AND EVOLUTION, V15, P15 DOI 10.1111/2041-210X.14355
4	47	0	Pironon, S (2024-JAN) The global distribution of plants used by humans . SCIENCE DOI 10.1126/science.adg8028
4	0	0	Penhacek, M (2025-JAN) Biases in amphibian sampling in the amazon: using infrastructure and accessibility data to identify sampling gaps . BIOTROPICA, V57, P13 DOI 10.1111/btp.70079
4	61	0	Di, febraro M (2023-JAN) Different facets of the same niche: integrating citizen science and scientific survey data to predict biological invasion risk under multiple global change drivers . GLOBAL CHANGE BIOLOGY, V29, P15 DOI 10.1111/gcb.16901
4	1	0	Boxriker, M (2025-JAN) Almost nothing left to lose: suitable habitat for glacial relicts strongly declines under future climate and land use scenarios . GLOBAL ECOLOGY AND CONSERVATION, V59, P13 DOI 10.1016/j.gecco.2025.e03541
4	0	0	de, aguiar messias CSM (2024-JAN) New perspectives for the annelida collection (national museum/ufjr) database: using data visualization to analyze and manage biological collections . OCEAN AND COASTAL RESEARCH, V72, P15 DOI 10.1590/2675-2824072.23102
4	39	0	Tietje, M (2023-JAN) Global hotspots of plant phylogenetic diversity . NEW PHYTOLOGIST, V240, P11 DOI 10.1111/nph.19151
4	2	0	Andrella, GC (2023-JAN) Considering spatial constraints to identify areas for new species sampling: a species-specific prioritization approach . BIOLOGICAL CONSERVATION, V288, P10 DOI 10.1016/j.biocon.2023.110379
4	1	0	Oliveira, U (2024-JAN) Controlling the effects of sampling bias in biodiversity models . JOURNAL OF BIOGEOGRAPHY, V51, P12 DOI 10.1111/jbi.14851
4	2	0	Bracho-estevanez, CA (2024-JAN) Spatially explicit metrics improve the evaluation of species distribution models facing sampling biases . ECOLOGICAL INFORMATICS, V84, P11 DOI 10.1016/j.ecoinf.2024.102916
4	0	0	Forbes, O (2025-JAN) Natural history collections at the crossroads: shifting priorities and data-driven opportunities . ECOLOGY LETTERS DOI 10.1111/ele.70188
4	1	0	Szymura, TH (2023-JAN) Spatial patterns of vascular plant species richness in poland-a data set . SCIENTIFIC DATA DOI 10.1038/s41597-023-02446-y

4	0	0	Castro-souza, RA (2025-JAN) Mapping the status of global taxonomic knowledge of orthoptera (arthropoda, insecta) . FRONTIERS OF BIOGEOGRAPHY, V18, P17 DOI 10.21425/fob.18.145455
4	48	0	Ribeiro, BR (2022-JAN) Bdc: a toolkit for standardizing, integrating and cleaning biodiversity data . METHODS IN ECOLOGY AND EVOLUTION DOI 10.1111/2041-210X.13868
3	0	0	Li, M (2025-JAN) Citizen scientists as butterfly predators: using foraging theory to understand individual recorder behaviour . ECOLOGICAL MODELLING DOI 10.1016/j.ecolmodel.2025.111344
3	2	0	Quarmby, J (2024-JAN) Evaluating extinction risk in tasmania's vascular flora using rapid iucn red list assessments . PACIFIC CONSERVATION BIOLOGY, V30, P13 DOI 10.1071/PC23005
3	35	0	Rossi, C (2021-JAN) Remote sensing of spectral diversity: a new methodological approach to account for spatio-temporal dissimilarities between plant communities . ECOLOGICAL INDICATORS, V130, P12 DOI 10.1016/j.ecolind.2021.108106
3	1	0	Dugerdil, L (2025-JAN) Functional signatures of surface pollen and vegetation are broadly similar: good news for past reconstructions of vegetation . JOURNAL OF BIOGEOGRAPHY, V52, P17 DOI 10.1111/jbi.15100
3	20	0	Tan, X (2022-JAN) Comparison of the predictive ability of spectral indices for commonly used species diversity indices and hill numbers in wetlands . ECOLOGICAL INDICATORS, V142, P11 DOI 10.1016/j.ecolind.2022.109233
3	0	0	Melis, R (2025-JAN) Unravelling bias: a sardinian perspective on taxonomic, spatial, and temporal biases in vascular plant biodiversity data from gbif . ECOLOGICAL INFORMATICS, V90, P11 DOI 10.1016/j.ecoinf.2025.103289
3	6	0	Glaser, M (2022-JAN) Agriweedclim database: a repository of vegetation plot data from central european arable habitats over 100 years . APPLIED VEGETATION SCIENCE, V25, P13 DOI 10.1111/avsc.12675
3	29	0	Hagen, O (2023-JAN) Coupling eco-evolutionary mechanisms with deep-time environmental dynamics to understand biodiversity patterns . ECOGEOGRAPHY, V2023, P16 DOI 10.1111/ecog.06132
3	18	0	Bergeson, CB (2022-JAN) Soil infiltration rates are underestimated by models in an urban watershed in central north carolina, usa . JOURNAL OF ENVIRONMENTAL MANAGEMENT DOI 10.1016/j.jenvman.2022.115004
3	0	0	Hernandez, C (2025-JAN) Shifts in trait diversity across the range of an endemic treeline species in central chile . ANNALS OF BOTANY, V135, P16 DOI 10.1093/aob/mcaf052
3	0	0	Ulrich, W (2025-JAN) The proper middle class: assessing the importance of subordinate species on plant community assembly and functional diversity . OIKOS DOI 10.1002/oik.11572
3	33	0	Chauvier, Y (2021-JAN) Novel methods to correct for observer and sampling bias in presence-only species distribution models . GLOBAL ECOLOGY AND BIOGEOGRAPHY, V30, P14 DOI 10.1111/geb.13383

3	2	0	Petisco-souza, AC (2023-JAN) Minding the gap: range size and economic use drive functional trait data gaps in the atlantic forest. BIOLOGICAL CONSERVATION DOI 10.1016/j.biocon.2023.110087
3	8	0	Mandrioli, M (2023-JAN) From dormant collections to repositories for the study of habitat changes: the importance of herbaria in modern life sciences. LIFE-BASEL, V13, P11 DOI 10.3390/life13122310
3	0	0	Crum, AH (2024-JAN) Traditional medicinal use is linked with apparency, not specialized metabolite profiles in the order caryophyllales. AMERICAN JOURNAL OF BOTANY, V111, P11 DOI 10.1002/ajb2.16308
3	34	0	Wolf, S (2022-JAN) Citizen science plant observations encode global trait patterns. NATURE ECOLOGY & EVOLUTION DOI 10.1038/s41559-022-01904-x
3	11	0	Mahaut, L (2022-JAN) Matches and mismatches between the global distribution of major food crops and climate suitability. PROCEEDINGS OF THE ROYAL SOCIETY B-BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES, V289, P10 DOI 10.1098/rspb.2022.1542
3	2	0	Harvey, GL (2025-JAN) Global diversity and energy of animals shaping the earth's surface. PROCEEDINGS OF THE NATIONAL ACADEMY OF SCIENCES OF THE UNITED STATES OF AMERICA DOI 10.1073/pnas.2415104122
3	5	0	Karger, DN (2023-JAN) Interannual climate variability improves niche estimates for ectothermic but not endothermic species. SCIENTIFIC REPORTS, V13, P11 DOI 10.1038/s41598-023-39637-x
3	8	0	Guerin, GR (2020-JAN) Stocktaking the environmental coverage of a continental ecosystem observation network. ECOSPHERE, V11, P17 DOI 10.1002/ecs2.3307
3	3	0	Kartzinel, TR (2025-JAN) Global availability of plant dna barcodes as genomic resources to support basic and policy-relevant biodiversity research. MOLECULAR ECOLOGY DOI 10.1111/mec.17712
3	0	0	Rather, SA (2025-JAN) Rosewoods at crossroads: a modern paradigm to secure the survival of the world's most trafficked wild species. BIOLOGICAL CONSERVATION, V311, P18 DOI 10.1016/j.biocon.2025.111399
3	15	0	Rossi, C (2023-JAN) Uncovering the hidden: leveraging sub-pixel spectral diversity to estimate plant diversity from space. REMOTE SENSING OF ENVIRONMENT, V296, P17 DOI 10.1016/j.rse.2023.113734
3	9	0	Westoby, M (2025-JAN) Trait-based ecology, trait-free ecology, and in between. NEW PHYTOLOGIST DOI 10.1111/nph.20197
3	8	0	Monteiro, M (2022-JAN) Patterns and drivers of the global diversity of non-native macrofungi. DIVERSITY AND DISTRIBUTIONS, V28, P14 DOI 10.1111/ddi.13607
3	4	0	Yahr, R (2024-JAN) Red listing lichenized fungi: best practices and future prospects. LICHENOLOGIST, V56, P18 DOI 10.1017/S0024282924000355

3	8	0	Alba, C (2021-JAN) Combining botanical collections and ecological data to better describe plant community diversity . PLOS ONE, V16, P17 DOI 10.1371/journal.pone.0244982
3	1	0	Everest, JJ (2025-JAN) Evaluating the utility of hyperspectral data to monitor local-scale β-diversity across space and time . REMOTE SENSING OF ENVIRONMENT, V316, P14 DOI 10.1016/j.rse.2024.114507
3	14	0	Moura, MR (2024-JAN) A phylogeny-informed characterisation of global tetrapod traits addresses data gaps and biases . PLOS BIOLOGY, V22, P31 DOI 10.1371/journal.pbio.3002658
3	0	0	Bisang, I (2025-JAN) Priority ranking for the conservation of all european bryophyte species ☆. BIOLOGICAL CONSERVATION, V309, P10 DOI 10.1016/j.biocon.2025.111297
3	2	0	Prenda, J (2024-JAN) Assessing citizen science data quality for bird monitoring in the iberian peninsula . SCIENTIFIC REPORTS, V14, P17 DOI 10.1038/s41598-024-70827-3
3	0	0	Garcia-rodriguez, A (2025-JAN) The global distribution patterns of alien vertebrate richness in mountains . NATURE COMMUNICATIONS, V16, P13 DOI 10.1038/s41467-025-57214-w

Appendix 2 Table 3 Cluster 1

Coverage	GCS	LCS	Bibliography
27	234	0	Hajek, M (2006-JAN) Habitat diversity of central european fens in relation to environmental gradients and an effort to standardise fen terminology in ecological studies . PERSPECTIVES IN PLANT ECOLOGY EVOLUTION AND SYSTEMATICS DOI 10.1016/j.ppees.2006.08.002
24	275	0	Dengler, J (2011-JAN) The global index of vegetation-plot databases (givd): a new resource for vegetation science . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V22, P16 DOI 10.1111/j.1654-1103.2011.01265.x
22	87	0	Hajkova, P (2006-JAN) Diversity of wetland vegetation in the bulgarian high mountains, main gradients and context-dependence of the ph role . PLANT ECOLOGY, V184, P20 DOI 10.1007/s11258-005-9056-5
18	247	0	Chytry, M (2005-JAN) Invasions by alien plants in the czech republic: a quantitative assessment across habitats. PRESLIA, V77, P16
17	136	0	Pysek, P (2005-JAN) Alien plants in temperate weed communities: prehistoric and recent invaders occupy different habitats . ECOLOGY, V86, P14 DOI 10.1890/04-0012
16	119	0	Sadlo, J (2007-JAN) Regional species pools of vascular plants in habitats of the czech republic. PRESLIA, V79, P19
15	150	0	Chytry, M (2003-JAN) Local and regional patterns of species richness in central european vegetation types along the ph/calcium gradient . FOLIA GEOBOTANICA, V38, P14 DOI 10.1007/BF02803250
15	23	0	Hajek, M (2008-JAN) The balkan wet grassland vegetation: a prerequisite to better understanding of european habitat diversity . PLANT ECOLOGY, V195, P17 DOI 10.1007/s11258-007-9315-8
15	8	0	Jansen, F (2011-JAN) Central european databases in the global index of vegetation plot databases (givd). TUEXENIA
14	44	0	Rolecek, J (2007-JAN) Formalized classification of thermophilous oak forests in the czech republic: what brings the cocktail method?. PRESLIA, V79, P21
14	33	0	Lososova, Z (2006-JAN) Classification of weed vegetation of arable land in the czech republic and slovakia . FOLIA GEOBOTANICA, V41, P15 DOI 10.1007/BF02904941
14	75	0	Rolecek, J (2007-JAN) Sampling design in large-scale vegetation studies: do not sacrifice ecological thinking to statistical purism! . FOLIA GEOBOTANICA, V42, P10 DOI 10.1007/BF02893886
13	52	0	Chytry, M (2009-JAN) Maps of the level of invasion of the czech republic by alien plants. PRESLIA, V81, P21
13	131	0	Knollová, I (2005-JAN) Stratified resampling of phytosociological databases: some strategies for obtaining more representative data sets for classification studies . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE DOI 10.1658/1100-9233(2005)016[0479:SR0PDS]2.0.CO;2
13	25	0	Dite, D (2007-JAN) Formal definitions of slovakian mire plant associations and their application in regional research . BIOLOGIA DOI 10.2478/s11756-007-0082-8

13	105	0	Ewald, J (2003-JAN) A critique for phytosociology . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE DOI 10.1658/1100-9233(2003)014[0291:ACFP]2.0.CO;2
12	85	0	Jansen, F (2010-JAN) Plant names in vegetation databases - a neglected source of bias . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE DOI 10.1111/j.1654-1103.2010.01209.x
12	13	0	Petrik, P (2006-JAN) Species groups can be transferred across different scales . JOURNAL OF BIOGEOGRAPHY, V33, P15 DOI 10.1111/j.1365-2699.2006.01514.x
12	31	0	Havlová, M (2006-JAN) Syntaxonomical revision of the molinion meadows in the czech republic. PRESLIA, V78, P15
12	11	0	Lososova, Z (2009-JAN) Chorological spectra of arable weed vegetation types in the czech republic . PHYTOCOENOLOGIA, V39, P18 DOI 10.1127/0340-269X/2009/0039-0235
12	12	0	Knollová, I (2006-JAN) Local ranges of phytosociological associations: are they reflected in numerical classification? . BIOLOGIA DOI 10.2478/s11756-006-0010-3
12	12	0	Dite, D (2006-JAN) Habitat variability and classification of utricularia communities:: comparison of peat depressions in slovakia and the trebon basin. PRESLIA, V78, P13
12	71	0	Dengler, J (2009-JAN) Species constancy depends on plot size - a problem for vegetation classification and how it can be solved . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V20, P13 DOI 10.1111/j.1654-1103.2009.01073.x
11	43	0	Havlová, M (2004-JAN) Diversity of hay meadows in the czech republic: major types and environmental gradients . PHYTOCOENOLOGIA, V34, P17 DOI 10.1127/0340-269X/2004/0034-0551
11	62	0	Illyes, E (2007-JAN) Semi-dry grasslands along a climatic gradient across central europe:: vegetation classification with validation . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V18, P12 DOI 10.1658/1100-9233(2007)18[835:SGAACG]2.0.CO;2
11	34	0	Lososová, Z (2004-JAN) Weed vegetation in southern moravia (czech republic):: a formalized phytosociological classification. PRESLIA, V76, P21
10	76	0	Pysek, P (2005-JAN) Effects of abiotic factors on species richness and cover in central european weed communities . AGRICULTURE ECOSYSTEMS & ENVIRONMENT DOI 10.1016/j.agee.2005.02.018
10	347	0	Chytry, M (2008-JAN) Separating habitat invasibility by alien plants from the actual level of invasion . ECOLOGY, V89, P13 DOI 10.1890/07-0682.1
10	400	0	Chytry, M (2008-JAN) Habitat invasions by alien plants:: a quantitative comparison among mediterranean, subcontinental and oceanic regions of europe . JOURNAL OF APPLIED ECOLOGY, V45, P11 DOI 10.1111/j.1365-2664.2007.01398.x
10	32	0	Rozbrojova, Z (2010-JAN) Vegetation diversity of mesic meadows and pastures in the west carpathians. PRESLIA, V82, P26

10	17	0	Boublik, K (2007-JAN) Calcicolous beech forests and related vegetation in the czech republic:: a comparison of formalized classifications. PRESLIA, V79, P21
10	194	0	Lososová, Z (2004-JAN) Weed vegetation of arable land in central europe: gradients of diversity and species composition . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE DOI 10.1111/j.1654-1103.2004.tb02279.x
10	166	0	Lososova, Z (2006-JAN) Patterns of plant traits in annual vegetation of man-made habitats in central europe . PERSPECTIVES IN PLANT ECOLOGY EVOLUTION AND SYSTEMATICS DOI 10.1016/j.ppees.2006.07.001
10	52	0	Dubravkova, D (2010-JAN) Dry grasslands in the western carpathians and the northern pannonian basin: a numerical classification. PRESLIA, V82, P57
9	20	0	Kuzelová, I (2004-JAN) Interspecific associations in phytosociological data sets: how do they change between local and regional scale? . PLANT ECOLOGY, V173, P11 DOI 10.1023/B:VEGE.0000029330.38055.8e
9	75	0	Michalcova, D (2011-JAN) Bias in vegetation databases? a comparison of stratified-random and preferential sampling . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V22, P11 DOI 10.1111/j.1654-1103.2010.01249.x
9	56	0	Lososova, Z (2008-JAN) Changes during the 20th century in species composition of synanthropic vegetation in moravia (czech republic). PRESLIA, V80, P15
9	143	0	Botta-dukát, Z (2005-JAN) Vegetation of lowland wet meadows along a climatic continentality gradient in central europe. PRESLIA, V77, P23
9	56	0	Simonova, D (2008-JAN) Which factors determine plant invasions in man-made habitats in the czech republic? . PERSPECTIVES IN PLANT ECOLOGY EVOLUTION AND SYSTEMATICS, V10, P12 DOI 10.1016/j.ppees.2007.11.003
9	113	0	Pysek, P (2004-JAN) Trends in species diversity and composition of urban vegetation over three decades . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE DOI 10.1658/1100-9233(2004)015[0781:TISDAC]2.0.CO;2
9	45	0	Juergens, N (2012-JAN) The biota biodiversity observatories in africa-a standardized framework for large-scale environmental monitoring . ENVIRONMENTAL MONITORING AND ASSESSMENT, V184, P24 DOI 10.1007/s10661-011-1993-y
9	40	0	Zeleny, D (2010-JAN) Pattern of local plant species richness along a gradient of landscape topographical heterogeneity: result of spatial mass effect or environmental shift? . ECOGEOGRAPHY, V33, P12 DOI 10.1111/j.1600-0587.2009.05762.x
9	63	0	Lososova, Z (2008-JAN) Plant attributes determining the regional abundance of weeds on central european arable land . JOURNAL OF BIOGEOGRAPHY, V35, P11 DOI 10.1111/j.1365-2699.2007.01778.x
9	41	0	Kropac, Z (2006-JAN) Segetal vegetation in the czech republic:: synthesis and syntaxonomical revision. PRESLIA, V78, P88
8	104	0	Kocí, M (2003-JAN) Formalized reproduction of an expert-based phytosociological classification:: a case study of subalpine tall-forb

			vegetation . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V14, P10 DOI 10.1111/j.1654-1103.2003.tb02187.x
8	476	0	Tichy, L (2006-JAN) Statistical determination of diagnostic species for site groups of unequal size . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V17, P10 DOI 10.1658/1100-9233(2006)17[809:SDODSF]2.0.CO;2
8	50	0	Jandt, U (2011-JAN) Exploring large vegetation databases to detect temporal trends in species occurrences . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V22, P16 DOI 10.1111/j.1654-1103.2011.01318.x
8	2	0	Petrik, P (2009-JAN) Combining numerical and traditional approaches to classify echinops sphaerocephalus invaded communities in the czech republic . PHYTOCOENOLOGIA, V39, P12 DOI 10.1127/0340-269X/2009/0039-0253
8	113	0	Tichy, L (2010-JAN) Optimclass: using species-to-cluster fidelity to determine the optimal partition in classification of ecological communities . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V21, P13 DOI 10.1111/j.1654-1103.2009.01143.x
8	6	0	Simonova, D (2008-JAN) Vegetation of trampled habitats in the czech republic: a formalized phytosociological classification . PHYTOCOENOLOGIA, V38, P15 DOI 10.1127/0340-269X/2008/0038-0177
8	57	0	Dengler, J (2009-JAN) A flexible multi-scale approach for standardised recording of plant species richness patterns . ECOLOGICAL INDICATORS DOI 10.1016/j.ecolind.2009.02.002
8	29	0	Sumberova, K (2006-JAN) Variability of vegetation of exposed pond bottoms in relation to management and environmental factors. PRESLIA, V78, P18
7	23	0	Pinke, G (2008-JAN) Phytosociological and conservational study of the arable weed communities in western hungary . PLANT BIOSYSTEMS, V142, P18 DOI 10.1080/11263500802410843
7	68	0	Loidi, J (2012-JAN) Potential natural vegetation: reburying or reborning? . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE DOI 10.1111/j.1654-1103.2012.01387.x
7	142	0	Vila, M (2007-JAN) Regional assessment of plant invasions across different habitat types . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE DOI 10.1111/j.1654-1103.2007.tb02513.x
7	274	0	Chytry, M (2003-JAN) Czech national phytosociological database:: basic statistics of the available vegetation-plot data. PRESLIA, V75, P15
7	19	0	Hölzel, N (2003-JAN) Re-assessing the ecology of rare flood-meadow violets (viola elatior, v-pumila and v-persicifolia) with large phytosociological data sets . FOLIA GEOBOTANICA, V38, P18 DOI 10.1007/BF02803200
7	300	0	Chytry, M (2003-JAN) Plot sizes used for phytosociological sampling of european vegetation . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE DOI 10.1111/j.1654-1103.2003.tb02183.x
7	21	0	Hedl, R (2007-JAN) Is sampling subjectivity a distorting factor in surveys for vegetation diversity? . FOLIA GEOBOTANICA DOI 10.1007/BF02893885

7	109	0	De, caceres M (2010-JAN) The management of vegetation classifications with fuzzy clustering . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V21, P14 DOI 10.1111/j.1654-1103.2010.01211.x
7	49	0	Michl, T (2010-JAN) Montane-subalpine tall-herb vegetation (mulgedio-aconitetea) in central europe: large-scale synthesis and comparison with northern europe . PHYTOCOENOLOGIA, V40, P38 DOI 10.1127/0340-269X/2010/0040-0377
7	16	0	Stancic, Z (2008-JAN) Classification of mesic and wet grasslands in northwest croatia . BIOLOGIA, V63, P15 DOI 10.2478/s11756-008-0153-5
7	57	0	Knollová, I (2004-JAN) Oak-hornbeam forests of the czech republic: geographical and ecological approaches to vegetation classification. PRESLIA, V76, P21
7	239	0	Chytry, M (2009-JAN) European map of alien plant invasions based on the quantitative assessment across habitats . DIVERSITY AND DISTRIBUTIONS, V15, P10 DOI 10.1111/j.1472-4642.2008.00515.x
6	11	0	Dengler, J (2006-JAN) Working group on dry grasslands in the nordic and baltic region - outline of the project and first results for the class festuco-brometea. ANNALI DI BOTANICA
6	6	0	Voss, N (2011-JAN) Vegetation databases as a tool to analyse factors affecting the range expansion of the forest understory herb ceratocapnos claviculata . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V22, P15 DOI 10.1111/j.1654-1103.2011.01284.x
6	43	0	Cerná, L (2005-JAN) Supervised classification of plant communities with artificial neural networks . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE DOI 10.1111/j.1654-1103.2005.tb02380.x
6	31	0	Jansen, F (2011-JAN) Ecological preferences of alien plant species in north-eastern germany . BIOLOGICAL INVASIONS, V13, P11 DOI 10.1007/s10530-011-9939-4
6	5	0	Rutherford, MC (2012-JAN) The south african national vegetation database: history, development, applications, problems and future . SOUTH AFRICAN JOURNAL OF SCIENCE DOI 10.4102/sajs.v108i1/2.629
6	5	0	Lengyel, A (2012-JAN) How do locally infrequent species influence numerical classification? a simulation study . COMMUNITY ECOLOGY DOI 10.1556/ComEc.13.2012.1.8
6	26	0	Lososova, Z (2009-JAN) Effects of different cultivation types on native and alien weed species richness and diversity in moravia (czech republic) . BASIC AND APPLIED ECOLOGY, V10, P10 DOI 10.1016/j.baae.2008.11.001
6	33	0	De, caceres M (2009-JAN) Numerical reproduction of traditional classifications and automatic vegetation identification . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE DOI 10.1111/j.1654-1103.2009.01081.x
6	31	0	Wiser, SK (2011-JAN) Veg-x - an exchange standard for plot-based vegetation data . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V22, P12 DOI 10.1111/j.1654-1103.2010.01245.x
6	27	0	Lanikova, D (2009-JAN) Rocks and walls: natural versus secondary habitats . FOLIA GEOBOTANICA, V44, P18 DOI 10.1007/s12224-009-9045-x

6	48	0	Douda, J (2008-JAN) Formalized classification of the vegetation of alder carr and floodplain forests in the czech republic. PRESLIA, V80, P26
5	19	0	Sumberová, K (2005-JAN) Vegetation dynamics on exposed pond bottoms in the ceskobudejovicka basin (czech republic) . PHYTOCOENOLOGIA, V35, P28 DOI 10.1127/0340-269X/2005/0035-0421
5	46	0	Diekmann, M (2007-JAN) Random its non-random sampling:: effects on patterns of species abundance, species richness and vegetation-environment relationships . FOLIA GEOBOTANICA, V42, P12 DOI 10.1007/BF02893884
5	33	0	Ugurlu, E (2012-JAN) Oak woodland vegetation of turkey - a first overview based on multivariate statistics . APPLIED VEGETATION SCIENCE, V15, P19 DOI 10.1111/j.1654-109X.2012.01192.x
5	48	0	Pysek, P (2010-JAN) Habitats and land use as determinants of plant invasions in the temperate zone of europe. BIOINVASIONS AND GLOBALIZATION: ECOLOGY, ECONOMICS, MANAGEMENT, AND POLICY
5	89	0	Novák, J (2006-JAN) Proximity of valuable habitats affects succession patterns in abandoned quarries . ECOLOGICAL ENGINEERING, V26, P10 DOI 10.1016/j.ecoleng.2005.06.008
5	54	0	Willner, W (2009-JAN) Effects of different fidelity measures and contexts on the determination of diagnostic species . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE DOI 10.1111/j.1654-1103.2009.05390.x
5	115	0	Podani, J (2006-JAN) Braun-blanquet's legacy and data analysis in vegetation science . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE DOI 10.1111/j.1654-1103.2006.tb02429.x
5	70	0	Lengyel, A (2011-JAN) Heterogeneity-constrained random resampling of phytosociological databases . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE DOI 10.1111/j.1654-1103.2010.01225.x
5	9	0	Torok, K (2010-JAN) Long-term changes of rock grassland communities in hungary . COMMUNITY ECOLOGY DOI 10.1556/ComEc.11.2010.1.10
5	57	0	Hédli, R (2004-JAN) Vegetation of beech forests in the rychlebske mountains, czech republic, re-inspected after 60 years with assessment of environmental changes . PLANT ECOLOGY, V170, P23 DOI 10.1023/B:VEGE.0000021681.83068.53
5	22	0	Bhatta, KP (2012-JAN) A comparison of systematic versus stratified-random sampling design for gradient analyses: a case study in subalpine himalaya, nepal . PHYTOCOENOLOGIA, V42, P12 DOI 10.1127/0340-269X/2012/0042-0519
5	53	0	Chytry, M (2011-JAN) Vegetation survey: a new focus for applied vegetation science . APPLIED VEGETATION SCIENCE DOI 10.1111/j.1654-109X.2011.01154.x
5	80	0	Münzbergová, Z (2004-JAN) Identification of suitable unoccupied habitats in metapopulation studies using co-occurrence of species . OIKOS DOI 10.1111/j.0030-1299.2004.13017.x
5	39	0	De, caceres M (2008-JAN) Assessing species diagnostic value in large data sets: a comparison between phi-coefficient and ochiai index . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V19, P12 DOI 10.3170/2008-8-18446

5	7	0	Dengler, J (2011-JAN) Ecoinformatics and global change - an overdue liaison . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE DOI 10.1111/j.1654-1103.2011.01313.x
5	14	0	Boublik, K (2010-JAN) Formalized classification of the vegetation of abies alba-dominated forests in the czech republic . BIOLOGIA, V65, P10 DOI 10.2478/s11756-010-0085-8
4	56	0	Hanula, JL (2011-JAN) Removing an invasive shrub (chinese privet) increases native bee diversity and abundance in riparian forests of the southeastern united states . INSECT CONSERVATION AND DIVERSITY DOI 10.1111/j.1752-4598.2011.00131.x
4	89	0	Wiser, SK (2011-JAN) New zealand's forest and shrubland communities: a quantitative classification based on a nationally representative plot network . APPLIED VEGETATION SCIENCE, V14, P18 DOI 10.1111/j.1654-109X.2011.01146.x
4	23	0	Gaudnik, C (2011-JAN) Detecting the footprint of changing atmospheric nitrogen deposition loads on acid grasslands in the context of climate change . GLOBAL CHANGE BIOLOGY, V17, P15 DOI 10.1111/j.1365-2486.2011.02463.x
4	40	0	Landucci, F (2012-JAN) Vegitaly: the italian collaborative project for a national vegetation database . PLANT BIOSYSTEMS DOI 10.1080/11263504.2012.740093
4	31	0	Jimenez-alfaro, B (2012-JAN) Diversity of rich fen vegetation and related plant specialists in mountain refugia of the iberian peninsula . FOLIA GEOBOTANICA, V47, P17 DOI 10.1007/s12224-012-9125-1
4	5	0	Lajer, K (2007-JAN) Hungarian phytosociological database (coenodatref): sampling methodology, nomenclature and its actual stage. ANNALI DI BOTANICA
4	24	0	Lososová, Z (2003-JAN) Estimating past distribution of vanishing weed vegetation in south moravia. PRESLIA
4	51	0	van, tongeren O (2008-JAN) Assignment of relevés to pre-defined classes by supervised clustering of plant communities using a new composite index . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V19, P12 DOI 10.3170/2008-8-18402

Appendix 2 Table 4 Cluster 2

Coverage	GCS	LCS	Bibliography
13	43	0	Meineke, EK (2019-JAN) Museum specimens provide novel insights into changing plant-herbivore interactions . PHILOSOPHICAL TRANSACTIONS OF THE ROYAL SOCIETY B-BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES, V374, P14 DOI 10.1098/rstb.2017.0393
12	303	0	Daru, BH (2018-JAN) Widespread sampling biases in herbaria revealed from large-scale digitization . NEW PHYTOLOGIST, V217, P17 DOI 10.1111/nph.14855
11	41	0	Rapacciuolo, G (2019-JAN) Understanding ecological change across large spatial, temporal and taxonomic scales: integrating data and methods in light of theory . ECOGEOGRAPHY, V42, P20 DOI 10.1111/ecog.04616
10	156	0	Lang, PLM (2019-JAN) Using herbaria to study global environmental change . NEW PHYTOLOGIST, V221, P13 DOI 10.1111/nph.15401
10	45	0	Park, DS (2017-JAN) Implications and alternatives of assigning climate data to geographical centroids . JOURNAL OF BIOGEOGRAPHY, V44, P11 DOI 10.1111/jbi.13029
9	24	0	Klonner, G (2017-JAN) Will climate change increase hybridization risk between potential plant invaders and their congeners in europe? . DIVERSITY AND DISTRIBUTIONS, V23, P10 DOI 10.1111/ddi.12578
9	200	0	Kissling, WD (2018-JAN) Building essential biodiversity variables (ebvs) of species distribution and abundance at a global scale . BIOLOGICAL REVIEWS, V93, P26 DOI 10.1111/brv.12359
9	165	0	Nelson, G (2019-JAN) The history and impact of digitization and digital data mobilization on biodiversity research . PHILOSOPHICAL TRANSACTIONS OF THE ROYAL SOCIETY B-BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES DOI 10.1098/rstb.2017.0391
9	23	0	Ronquillo, C (2020-JAN) Assessing spatial and temporal biases and gaps in the publicly available distributional information of iberian mosses . BIODIVERSITY DATA JOURNAL DOI 10.3897/BDJ.8.e53474
9	14	0	Glon, HE (2017-JAN) The contribution of small collections to species distribution modelling: a case study from fuireneae (cyperaceae) . ECOLOGICAL INFORMATICS, V42, P12 DOI 10.1016/j.ecoinf.2017.09.009
9	21	0	Ronk, A (2017-JAN) Observed and dark diversity of alien plant species in europe: estimating future invasion risk . BIODIVERSITY AND CONSERVATION, V26, P18 DOI 10.1007/s10531-016-1278-4
8	29	0	Jin, J (2020-JAN) Bdcleaner: a workflow for cleaning taxonomic and geographic errors in occurrence data archived in biodiversity databases . GLOBAL ECOLOGY AND CONSERVATION, V21, P12 DOI 10.1016/j.gecco.2019.e00852
8	20	0	Sporbert, M (2019-JAN) Assessing sampling coverage of species distribution in biodiversity databases . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V30, P13 DOI 10.1111/jvs.12763
8	7	0	Haque, MM (2018-JAN) A journey through time: exploring temporal patterns amongst digitized plant specimens from australia . SYSTEMATICS AND BIODIVERSITY, V16, P10 DOI 10.1080/14772000.2018.1472674

8	50	0	Panchen, ZA (2019-JAN) Patterns and biases in an arctic herbarium specimen collection: implications for phenological research. APPLICATIONS IN PLANT SCIENCES DOI 10.1002/aps3.1229
8	149	0	Meineke, EK (2018-JAN) The unrealized potential of herbaria for global change biology. ECOLOGICAL MONOGRAPHS, V88, P21 DOI 10.1002/ecm.1307
8	1	0	Osazuwa-peters, OL (2018-JAN) Using museum specimens to estimate broad- scale species richness: exploring the performance of individual-based and spatially explicit rarefaction. PLOS ONE, V13, P22 DOI 10.1371/journal.pone.0204484
8	190	0	Meineke, EK (2019-JAN) Biological collections for understanding biodiversity in the anthropocene. PHILOSOPHICAL TRANSACTIONS OF THE ROYAL SOCIETY B-BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES DOI 10.1098/rstb.2017.0386
8	209	0	Feng, X (2019-JAN) A checklist for maximizing reproducibility of ecological niche models. NATURE ECOLOGY & EVOLUTION DOI 10.1038/s41559-019-0972-5
8	48	0	Tessarolo, G (2017-JAN) Temporal degradation of data limits biodiversity research. ECOLOGY AND EVOLUTION DOI 10.1002/ece3.3259
8	98	0	Staude, IR (2020-JAN) Replacements of small- by large-ranged species scale up to diversity loss in europe's temperate forest biome. NATURE ECOLOGY & EVOLUTION DOI 10.1038/s41559-020-1176-8
7	227	0	Farley, SS (2018-JAN) Situating ecology as a big-data science: current advances, challenges, and solutions. BIOSCIENCE, V68, P14 DOI 10.1093/biosci/biy068
7	36	0	Hoveka, LN (2020-JAN) Identifying biodiversity knowledge gaps for conserving south africa's endemic flora. BIODIVERSITY AND CONSERVATION, V29, P17 DOI 10.1007/s10531-020-01998-4
7	13	0	Araujo, MLd (2021-JAN) Targeting the survey efforts: gaps and biases in epiphyte sampling at a biodiversity hotspot. FOREST ECOLOGY AND MANAGEMENT, V498, P11 DOI 10.1016/j.foreco.2021.119544
7	47	0	Paton, A (2020-JAN) Plant and fungal collections: current status, future perspectives. PLANTS PEOPLE PLANET DOI 10.1002/ppp3.10141
7	111	0	Ball-damerow, JE (2019-JAN) Research applications of primary biodiversity databases in the digital age. PLOS ONE, V14, P26 DOI 10.1371/journal.pone.0215794
7	193	0	Hedrick, BP (2020-JAN) Digitization and the future of natural history collections. BIOSCIENCE DOI 10.1093/biosci/biz163
7	11	0	Sofaer, HR (2017-JAN) Accounting for sampling patterns reverses the relative importance of trade and climate for the global sharing of exotic plants. GLOBAL ECOLOGY AND BIOGEOGRAPHY, V26, P10 DOI 10.1111/geb.12577
7	16	0	Pender, JE (2019-JAN) How sensitive are climatic niche inferences to distribution data sampling? a comparison of biota of north america program (bonap) and global biodiversity information facility (gbif) datasets. ECOLOGICAL INFORMATICS DOI 10.1016/j.ecoinf.2019.100991

7	41	0	Troudet, J (2018-JAN) The increasing disconnection of primary biodiversity data from specimens: how does it happen and how to handle it? . SYSTEMATIC BIOLOGY, V67, P10 DOI 10.1093/sysbio/syy044
7	24	0	Lagomarsino, LP (2020-JAN) The central role of taxonomy in the study of neotropical biodiversity . ANNALS OF THE MISSOURI BOTANICAL GARDEN, V105, P17 DOI 10.3417/2020601
7	3	0	Primack, RB (2022-JAN) Was henry david thoreau a good naturalist? an approach for assessing data from historical natural history records . BIOSCIENCE, V72, P10 DOI 10.1093/biosci/biac063
7	29	0	Vangansbeke, P (2021-JAN) Climplant: realized climatic niches of vascular plants in european forest understoreys . GLOBAL ECOLOGY AND BIOGEOGRAPHY DOI 10.1111/geb.13303
7	623	0	Zurell, D (2020-JAN) A standard protocol for reporting species distribution models . ECOGRAPHY, V43, P17 DOI 10.1111/ecog.04960
7	44	0	Yost, JM (2018-JAN) Digitization protocol for scoring reproductive phenology from herbarium specimens of seed plants . APPLICATIONS IN PLANT SCIENCES DOI 10.1002/aps3.1022
7	13	0	Bachman, SP (2020-JAN) Extinction risk and conservation gaps for aloe (asphodelaceae) in the horn of africa . BIODIVERSITY AND CONSERVATION, V29, P22 DOI 10.1007/s10531-019-01870-0
6	21	0	Walker, BE (2020-JAN) Caution needed when predicting species threat status for conservation prioritization on a global scale . FRONTIERS IN PLANT SCIENCE DOI 10.3389/fpls.2020.00520
6	65	0	Meineke, EK (2019-JAN) Herbarium specimens reveal increasing herbivory over the past century . JOURNAL OF ECOLOGY, V107, P13 DOI 10.1111/1365-2745.13057
6	97	0	Cornwell, WK (2019-JAN) What we (don't) know about global plant diversity . ECOGRAPHY, V42, P13 DOI 10.1111/ecog.04481
6	9	0	Escribano, N (2019-JAN) Completeness of digital accessible knowledge (dak) about terrestrial mammals in the iberian peninsula . PLOS ONE, V14, P16 DOI 10.1371/journal.pone.0213542
6	91	0	Koenig, C (2019-JAN) Biodiversity data integration--the significance of data resolution and domain . PLOS BIOLOGY, V17, P16 DOI 10.1371/journal.pbio.3000183
6	31	0	Daru, BH (2019-JAN) A novel proof of concept for capturing the diversity of endophytic fungi preserved in herbarium specimens . PHILOSOPHICAL TRANSACTIONS OF THE ROYAL SOCIETY B-BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES, V374, P10 DOI 10.1098/rstb.2017.0395
6	16	0	Depauw, L (2022-JAN) The use of photos to investigate ecological change . JOURNAL OF ECOLOGY, V110, P17 DOI 10.1111/1365-2745.13876
6	17	0	Hufft, RA (2018-JAN) Using herbarium specimens to select indicator species for climate change monitoring . BIODIVERSITY AND CONSERVATION, V27, P15 DOI 10.1007/s10531-018-1505-2
6	8	0	Huang, X (2020-JAN) The persistent multi-dimensional biases of biodiversity digital accessible knowledge of birds in china . BIODIVERSITY AND CONSERVATION, V29, P25 DOI 10.1007/s10531-020-02024-3

6	53	0	Besnard, G (2018-JAN) Herbarium-based science in the twenty-first century . BOTANY LETTERS DOI 10.1080/23818107.2018.1482783
6	238	0	Willis, CG (2017-JAN) Old plants, new tricks: phenological research using herbarium specimens . TRENDS IN ECOLOGY & EVOLUTION, V32, P16 DOI 10.1016/j.tree.2017.03.015
6	21	0	Jimenez-valverde, A (2019-JAN) Photo-sharing platforms key for characterising niche and distribution in poorly studied taxa . INSECT CONSERVATION AND DIVERSITY, V12, P15 DOI 10.1111/icad.12351
6	0	0	UNKNOWN, - (2017-JAN) Detecting and responding to alien plant incursions preface. DETECTING AND RESPONDING TO ALIEN PLANT INCURSIONS
6	104	0	Dullinger, I (2017-JAN) Climate change will increase the naturalization risk from garden plants in europe . GLOBAL ECOLOGY AND BIOGEOGRAPHY, V26, P11 DOI 10.1111/geb.12512
6	346	0	Jetz, W (2019-JAN) Essential biodiversity variables for mapping and monitoring species populations . NATURE ECOLOGY & EVOLUTION DOI 10.1038/s41559-019-0826-1
6	167	0	Pocock, MJO (2018-JAN) A vision for global biodiversity monitoring with citizen science . NEXT GENERATION BIOMONITORING, PT 2, V59, P55 DOI 10.1016/bs.aacr.2018.06.003
6	78	0	Pearse, WD (2017-JAN) A statistical estimator for determining the limits of contemporary and historic phenology . NATURE ECOLOGY & EVOLUTION DOI 10.1038/s41559-017-0350-0
6	59	0	Mayer, K (2017-JAN) Naturalization of ornamental plant species in public green spaces and private gardens . BIOLOGICAL INVASIONS, V19, P15 DOI 10.1007/s10530-017-1594-y
6	16	0	Girardello, M (2018-JAN) Gaps in biodiversity occurrence information may hamper the achievement of international biodiversity targets: insights from a cross-taxon analysis . ENVIRONMENTAL CONSERVATION DOI 10.1017/S0376892918000115
5	23	0	Zizka, A (2018-JAN) Finding needles in the haystack: where to look for rare species in the american tropics . ECOGRAPHY, V41, P10 DOI 10.1111/ecog.02192
5	92	0	Lobo, JM (2018-JAN) Knower: an application to map the geographical variation of survey effort and identify well-surveyed areas from biodiversity databases . ECOLOGICAL INDICATORS DOI 10.1016/j.ecolind.2018.03.077
5	29	0	Berend, K (2019-JAN) Common garden experiments as a dynamic tool for ecological studies of alpine plants and communities in northeastern north america . RHODORA, V121, P39 DOI 10.3119/18-16
5	10	0	Correia, RA (2019-JAN) Using ignorance scores to explore biodiversity recording effort for multiple taxa in the caatinga . ECOLOGICAL INDICATORS, V106, P10 DOI 10.1016/j.ecolind.2019.105539
5	26	0	Lughadha, EMN (2019-JAN) Harnessing the potential of integrated systematics for conservation of taxonomically complex, megadiverse plant groups . CONSERVATION BIOLOGY, V33, P12 DOI 10.1111/cobi.13289

5	10	0	Yang, W (2021-JAN) Taxonomic bias in occurrence information of angiosperm species in china . SCIENCE CHINA-LIFE SCIENCES DOI 10.1007/s11427-020-1821-x
5	192	0	Newbold, T (2018-JAN) Widespread winners and narrow-ranged losers: land use homogenizes biodiversity in local assemblages worldwide . PLOS BIOLOGY, V16, P24 DOI 10.1371/journal.pbio.2006841
5	48	0	Girardello, M (2019-JAN) Gaps in butterfly inventory data: a global analysis . BIOLOGICAL CONSERVATION DOI 10.1016/j.biocon.2019.05.053
5	0	0	Chiu, C (2021-JAN) Exploring the potential distribution of relic trochodendron aralioides: an approach using open-access resources and free software . FORESTS, V12, P15 DOI 10.3390/f12121749
5	5	0	Stenhouse, A (2020-JAN) Koala counter: recording citizen scientists' search paths to improve data quality . GLOBAL ECOLOGY AND CONSERVATION, V24, P12 DOI 10.1016/j.gecco.2020.e01376
5	6	0	Suarez-castro, AF (2021-JAN) Spatial information gaps in continental terrestrial mammal richness from colombia . CALDASIA, V43, P14 DOI 10.15446/caldasia.v43n2.85443
5	92	0	Franklin, J (2017-JAN) Big data for forecasting the impacts of global change on plant communities . GLOBAL ECOLOGY AND BIOGEOGRAPHY, V26, P12 DOI 10.1111/geb.12501
5	220	0	Heberling, JM (2021-JAN) Data integration enables global biodiversity synthesis . PROCEEDINGS OF THE NATIONAL ACADEMY OF SCIENCES OF THE UNITED STATES OF AMERICA DOI 10.1073/pnas.2018093118
5	71	0	Serra-diaz, JM (2018-JAN) Big data of tree species distributions: how big and how good? . FOREST ECOSYSTEMS DOI 10.1186/s40663-017-0120-0
5	70	0	Guedes, TB (2018-JAN) Patterns, biases and prospects in the distribution and diversity of neotropical snakes . GLOBAL ECOLOGY AND BIOGEOGRAPHY DOI 10.1111/geb.12679
5	29	0	Wiser, SK (2016-JAN) Achievements and challenges in the integration, reuse and synthesis of vegetation plot data . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V27, P12 DOI 10.1111/jvs.12419
5	294	0	Lughadha, EN (2020-JAN) Extinction risk and threats to plants and fungi . PLANTS PEOPLE PLANET DOI 10.1002/ppp3.10146
5	386	0	Antonelli, A (2018-JAN) Amazonia is the primary source of neotropical biodiversity . PROCEEDINGS OF THE NATIONAL ACADEMY OF SCIENCES OF THE UNITED STATES OF AMERICA DOI 10.1073/pnas.1713819115
5	8	0	Haque, MM (2020-JAN) Taxonomic shortfalls in digitised collections of australia's flora . BIODIVERSITY AND CONSERVATION, V29, P11 DOI 10.1007/s10531-019-01885-7
5	8	0	Larrain, J (2019-JAN) Hidden in plain sight: how overlooking ephemeral bryophytes can bias biodiversity assessments and conservation actions . BRYOLOGIST, V122, P11 DOI 10.1639/0007-2745-122.2.260

5	69	0	Kharouba, HM (2019-JAN) Using insect natural history collections to study global change impacts: challenges and opportunities. PHILOSOPHICAL TRANSACTIONS OF THE ROYAL SOCIETY B-BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES, V374, P10 DOI 10.1098/rstb.2017.0405
4	8	0	Banaszak, C (2020-JAN) Chilling consequences: herbarium records reveal earlier reproductive phenology of winter annual gladdress in a wetter, cooler climate. PLANTS PEOPLE PLANET DOI 10.1002/ppp3.10095
4	39	0	Zhong, Y (2021-JAN) The application of species distribution modeling in wetland restoration: a case study in the songnen plain, northeast china. ECOLOGICAL INDICATORS, V121, P13 DOI 10.1016/j.ecolind.2020.107137
4	27	0	Rapacciuolo, G (2021-JAN) Deriving indicators of biodiversity change from unstructured community-contributed data. OIKOS, V130, P15 DOI 10.1111/oik.08215
4	6	0	Oliveira, EVS (2021-JAN) Sampling effort and the drivers of plant species richness in the brazilian coastal regions. OECOLOGIA DOI 10.1007/s00442-020-04805-7
4	9	0	Guerin, GR (2018-JAN) When macroecological transitions are a fiction of sampling: comparing herbarium records to plot-based species inventory data. ECOGRAPHY, V41, P12 DOI 10.1111/ecog.03607
4	1	0	Kuehn, I (2017-JAN) Seven years of neobiota the times, were they a changin'? NEOBIOTA DOI 10.3897/neobiota.36.21926
4	68	0	Elith, J (2017-JAN) Predicting distributions of invasive species. INVASIVE SPECIES: RISK ASSESSMENT AND MANAGEMENT
4	342	0	Dawson, W (2017-JAN) Global hotspots and correlates of alien species richness across taxonomic groups. NATURE ECOLOGY & EVOLUTION DOI 10.1038/s41559-017-0186
4	3	0	Rodriguez-rey, M (2022-JAN) Disentangling the drivers of the sampling bias of freshwater fish across europe. FISHES DOI 10.3390/fishes7060383
4	29	0	Farooq, H (2021-JAN) Mapping africa's biodiversity: more of the same is just not good enough. SYSTEMATIC BIOLOGY, V70, P11 DOI 10.1093/sysbio/syaa090
4	29	0	Scherrer, D (2018-JAN) How to best threshold and validate stacked species assemblages? community optimisation might hold the answer. METHODS IN ECOLOGY AND EVOLUTION DOI 10.1111/2041-210X.13041
4	11	0	Narvaez-gomez, JP (2021-JAN) Recovering the drivers of sampling bias in bignoniaceae (bignoniaceae) and identifying priority areas for new survey efforts. BIODIVERSITY AND CONSERVATION, V30, P21 DOI 10.1007/s10531-021-02195-7
4	13	0	Zarrate-charry, DA (2018-JAN) Multi-criteria spatial identification of carnivore conservation areas under data scarcity and conflict: a jaguar case study in sierra nevada de santa marta, colombia. BIODIVERSITY AND CONSERVATION, V27, P20 DOI 10.1007/s10531-018-1605-z
4	52	0	Meineke, EK (2021-JAN) Bias assessments to expand research harnessing biological collections. TRENDS IN ECOLOGY & EVOLUTION, V36, P12 DOI 10.1016/j.tree.2021.08.003

4	80	0	Chardon, NI (2020-JAN) Incorporating intraspecific variation into species distribution models improves distribution predictions, but cannot predict species traits for a wide-spread plant species . ECOGRAPHY, V43, P15 DOI 10.1111/ecog.04630
4	86	0	Coxen, CL (2017-JAN) Species distribution models for a migratory bird based on citizen science and satellite tracking data . GLOBAL ECOLOGY AND CONSERVATION, V11, P14 DOI 10.1016/j.gecco.2017.08.001
4	64	0	Daru, BH (2019-JAN) Spatial overlaps between the global protected areas network and terrestrial hotspots of evolutionary diversity . GLOBAL ECOLOGY AND BIOGEOGRAPHY, V28, P10 DOI 10.1111/geb.12888
4	50	0	Willis, CG (2017-JAN) Crowdcurio: an online crowdsourcing platform to facilitate climate change studies using herbarium specimens . NEW PHYTOLOGIST, V215, P10 DOI 10.1111/nph.14535
4	20	0	Vorontsova, MS (2021-JAN) Inequality in plant diversity knowledge and unrecorded plant extinctions: an example from the grasses of madagascar . PLANTS PEOPLE PLANET DOI 10.1002/ppp3.10123
4	18	0	Haque, MM (2017-JAN) How well documented is australia's flora? understanding spatial bias in vouchered plant specimens . AUSTRAL ECOLOGY, V42, P10 DOI 10.1111/aec.12487
4	18	0	Piccolo, RL (2020-JAN) Location biases in ecological research on australian terrestrial reptiles . SCIENTIFIC REPORTS, V10, P10 DOI 10.1038/s41598-020-66719-x
4	7	0	Bottin, M (2020-JAN) Phytosociological data and herbarium collections show congruent large-scale patterns but differ in their local descriptions of community composition . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V31, P12 DOI 10.1111/jvs.12825
4	241	0	Guerra, CA (2020-JAN) Blind spots in global soil biodiversity and ecosystem function research . NATURE COMMUNICATIONS, V11, P13 DOI 10.1038/s41467-020-17688-2
4	157	0	Weigelt, P (2020-JAN) Gift - a global inventory of floras and traits for macroecology and biogeography . JOURNAL OF BIOGEOGRAPHY, V47, P28 DOI 10.1111/jbi.13623
4	347	0	Hughes, AC (2021-JAN) Sampling biases shape our view of the natural world . ECOGRAPHY, V44, P11 DOI 10.1111/ecog.05926
4	29	0	Park, DS (2019-JAN) Anthropogenic threats can have cascading homogenizing effects on the phylogenetic and functional diversity of tropical ecosystems . ECOGRAPHY, V42, P14 DOI 10.1111/ecog.03825
4	23	0	Bystriakova, N (2019-JAN) A preliminary evaluation of the karst flora of brazil using collections data . SCIENTIFIC REPORTS DOI 10.1038/s41598-019-53104-6
3	9	0	Rock, BM (2021-JAN) Impediments to understanding seagrasses? response to global change . FRONTIERS IN MARINE SCIENCE DOI 10.3389/fmars.2021.608867
3	6	0	Buldrini, F (2023-JAN) Botanical memory: five centuries of floristic changes revealed by a renaissance herbarium (ulisse aldrovandi, 1551-1586) . ROYAL SOCIETY OPEN SCIENCE, V10, P16 DOI 10.1098/rsos.230866

3	9	0	Vargas, CA (2022-JAN) Environmental and geographical biases in plant specimen data from the colombian andes . BOTANICAL JOURNAL OF THE LINNEAN SOCIETY, V200, P14 DOI 10.1093/botlinnean/boac035
3	42	0	Bradsworth, N (2017-JAN) Species distribution models derived from citizen science data predict the fine scale movements of owls in an urbanizing landscape . BIOLOGICAL CONSERVATION DOI 10.1016/j.biocon.2017.06.039
3	8	0	Cunha, crescente alves DM (2020-JAN) Unveiling geographical gradients of species richness from scant occurrence data . GLOBAL ECOLOGY AND BIOGEOGRAPHY, V29, P12 DOI 10.1111/geb.13055
3	33	0	Engemann, K (2016-JAN) Patterns and drivers of plant functional group dominance across the western hemisphere: a macroecological re-assessment based on a massive botanical dataset . BOTANICAL JOURNAL OF THE LINNEAN SOCIETY, V180, P20 DOI 10.1111/boj.12362
3	4	0	Seymour, V (2022-JAN) Incorporating citizen science to advance the natural capital approach . ECOSYSTEM SERVICES, V54, P14 DOI 10.1016/j.ecoser.2022.101419
3	19	0	Arle, E (2021-JAN) Bracatus: a method to estimate the accuracy and biogeographical status of georeferenced biological data . METHODS IN ECOLOGY AND EVOLUTION, V12, P11 DOI 10.1111/2041-210X.13629
3	29	0	Hugo, S (2017-JAN) The second southern african bird atlas project: causes and consequences of geographical sampling bias . ECOLOGY AND EVOLUTION DOI 10.1002/ece3.3228
3	46	0	Culina, A (2018-JAN) Navigating the unfolding open data landscape in ecology and evolution . NATURE ECOLOGY & EVOLUTION DOI 10.1038/s41559-017-0458-2
3	69	0	Qian, L (2020-JAN) Plant diversity in yunnan: current status and future directions . PLANT DIVERSITY, V42, P11 DOI 10.1016/j.pld.2020.07.006
3	21	0	Onyia, NN (2018-JAN) Normalized difference vegetation vigour index: a new remote sensing approach to biodiversity monitoring in oil polluted regions . REMOTE SENSING, V10, P34 DOI 10.3390/rs10060897
3	11	0	Tarli, VD (2018-JAN) The informative value of museum collections for ecology and conservation: a comparison with target sampling in the brazilian atlantic forest . PLOS ONE, V13, P17 DOI 10.1371/journal.pone.0205710
3	10	0	Bystriakova, N (2021-JAN) Colombia's bioregions as a source of useful plants . PLOS ONE, V16, P19 DOI 10.1371/journal.pone.0256457
3	194	0	Santini, L (2021-JAN) Assessing the reliability of species distribution projections in climate change research . DIVERSITY AND DISTRIBUTIONS, V27, P16 DOI 10.1111/ddi.13252
3	58	0	Thomas, HJD (2019-JAN) Traditional plant functional groups explain variation in economic but not size-related traits across the tundra biome . GLOBAL ECOLOGY AND BIOGEOGRAPHY, V28, P18 DOI 10.1111/geb.12783

3	100	0	Altwegg, R (2019-JAN) Occupancy models for citizen-science data . METHODS IN ECOLOGY AND EVOLUTION, V10, P14 DOI 10.1111/2041-210X.13090
3	25	0	Hernandez-rojas, AC (2020-JAN) Latitudinal patterns of species richness and range size of ferns along elevational gradients at the transition from tropics to subtropics . JOURNAL OF BIOGEOGRAPHY, V47, P15 DOI 10.1111/jbi.13841
3	44	0	Veron, S (2019-JAN) Distribution and relative age of endemism across islands worldwide . SCIENTIFIC REPORTS DOI 10.1038/s41598-019-47951-6
3	14	0	Lannuzel, G (2022-JAN) Mining rare earth elements: identifying the plant species most threatened by ore extraction in an insular hotspot . FRONTIERS IN ECOLOGY AND EVOLUTION, V10, P13 DOI 10.3389/fevo.2022.952439
3	24	0	Rindel, DD (2021-JAN) The distribution of the guanaco (lama guanicoe) in patagonia during late pleistocene-holocene and its importance for prehistoric human diet . HOLOCENE, V31, P14 DOI 10.1177/0959683620981689
3	3	0	Rivera-quiros, FA (2020-JAN) Mining data from legacy taxonomic literature and application for sampling spiders of the teutamus group (araneae; liocranidae) in southeast asia . SCIENTIFIC REPORTS, V10, P13 DOI 10.1038/s41598-020-72549-8
3	23	0	Porro, F (2019-JAN) Could plant diversity metrics explain climate-driven vegetation changes on mountain summits of the gloria network? . BIODIVERSITY AND CONSERVATION, V28, P22 DOI 10.1007/s10531-019-01837-1
3	45	0	Daru, BH (2023-JAN) Mass production of unvouchered records fails to represent global biodiversity patterns . NATURE ECOLOGY & EVOLUTION DOI 10.1038/s41559-023-02047-3
3	23	0	Mackenzie, CM (2019-JAN) Floristic change in new england and new york: regional patterns of plant species loss and decline . RHODORA, V121, P36 DOI 10.3119/18-04
3	115	0	Staude, IR (2020-JAN) Range size predicts the risk of local extinction from habitat loss . GLOBAL ECOLOGY AND BIOGEOGRAPHY, V29, P10 DOI 10.1111/geb.13003
3	104	0	Wueest, RO (2020-JAN) Macroecology in the age of big data - where to go from here? . JOURNAL OF BIOGEOGRAPHY, V47, P12 DOI 10.1111/jbi.13633
3	19	0	Beaulieu, C (2019-JAN) Bookkeeping of insect herbivory trends in herbarium specimens of purple loosestrife (lythrum salicaria) . PHILOSOPHICAL TRANSACTIONS OF THE ROYAL SOCIETY B-BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES DOI 10.1098/rstb.2017.0398
3	118	0	Soltis, PS (2017-JAN) Digitization of herbaria enables novel research . AMERICAN JOURNAL OF BOTANY DOI 10.3732/ajb.1700281
3	27	0	Ansong, M (2019-JAN) Naturalized and invasive alien flora of ghana . BIOLOGICAL INVASIONS, V21, P15 DOI 10.1007/s10530-018-1860-7

3	96	0	Lughadha, EN (2019-JAN) The use and misuse of herbarium specimens in evaluating plant extinction risks . PHILOSOPHICAL TRANSACTIONS OF THE ROYAL SOCIETY B-BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES, V374, P13 DOI 10.1098/rstb.2017.0402
3	28	0	Meineke, EK (2021-JAN) Phenological sensitivity to temperature mediates herbivory . GLOBAL CHANGE BIOLOGY, V27, P13 DOI 10.1111/gcb.15600
3	38	0	Marsico, TD (2020-JAN) Small herbaria contribute unique biogeographic records to county, locality, and temporal scales . AMERICAN JOURNAL OF BOTANY, V107, P11 DOI 10.1002/ajb2.1563
3	36	0	Andrew, SC (2021-JAN) Functional diversity of the australian flora: strong links to species richness and climate . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V32, P14 DOI 10.1111/jvs.13018
3	83	0	Mancinelli, G (2021-JAN) A global occurrence database of the atlantic blue crab callinectes sapidus . SCIENTIFIC DATA DOI 10.1038/s41597-021-00888-w
3	9	0	Tang, L (2019-JAN) Throwing light on dark diversity of vascular plants in china: predicting the distribution of dark and threatened species under global climate change . PEERJ DOI 10.7717/peerj.6731
3	15	0	Bobrowski, M (2021-JAN) Searching for ecology in species distribution models in the himalayas . ECOLOGICAL MODELLING, V458, P14 DOI 10.1016/j.ecolmodel.2021.109693
3	60	0	Albani, rocchetti G (2021-JAN) Reversing extinction trends: new uses of (old) herbarium specimens to accelerate conservation action on threatened species . NEW PHYTOLOGIST, V230, P18 DOI 10.1111/nph.17133
3	38	0	Ringelberg, JJ (2020-JAN) Biomes as evolutionary arenas: convergence and conservatism in the trans-continental succulent biome . GLOBAL ECOLOGY AND BIOGEOGRAPHY, V29, P14 DOI 10.1111/geb.13089
3	3	0	Zhang, J (2021-JAN) Reconsideration of the native range of the chinese swamp cypress (glyptostrobus pensilis) based on new insights from historic, remnant and planted populations . GLOBAL ECOLOGY AND CONSERVATION, V32, P15 DOI 10.1016/j.gecco.2021.e01927

Appendix 2 Table 5 Cluster 3

Coverage	GCS	LCS	Bibliography
11	22	0	Sadoti, G (2013-JAN) Applying occupancy estimation and modelling to the analysis of atlas data . DIVERSITY AND DISTRIBUTIONS, V19, P11 DOI 10.1111/ddi.12041
10	21	0	van, strien AJ (2013-JAN) Occupancy modelling as a new approach to assess supranational trends using opportunistic data: a pilot study for the damselfly calopteryx splendens . BIODIVERSITY AND CONSERVATION, V22, P14 DOI 10.1007/s10531-013-0436-1
9	309	0	van, strien AJ (2013-JAN) Opportunistic citizen science data of animal species produce reliable estimates of distribution trends if analysed with occupancy models . JOURNAL OF APPLIED ECOLOGY DOI 10.1111/1365-2664.12158
9	76	0	Ratnieks, FLW (2016-JAN) Data reliability in citizen science: learning curve and the effects of training method, volunteer background and experience on identification accuracy of insects visiting ivy flowers . METHODS IN ECOLOGY AND EVOLUTION DOI 10.1111/2041-210X.12581
9	86	0	Tulloch, AIT (2013-JAN) To boldly go where no volunteer has gone before: predicting volunteer activity to prioritize surveys at the landscape scale . DIVERSITY AND DISTRIBUTIONS, V19, P16 DOI 10.1111/j.1472-4642.2012.00947.x
8	437	0	Tulloch, AIT (2013-JAN) Realising the full potential of citizen science monitoring programs . BIOLOGICAL CONSERVATION, V165, P11 DOI 10.1016/j.biocon.2013.05.025
8	33	0	Smart, SM (2010-JAN) Empirical realised niche models for british higher and lower plants - development and preliminary testing . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V21, P14 DOI 10.1111/j.1654-1103.2010.01173.x
8	32	0	Niamir, A (2011-JAN) Finessing atlas data for species distribution models . DIVERSITY AND DISTRIBUTIONS, V17, P13 DOI 10.1111/j.1472-4642.2011.00793.x
7	32	0	Wei, JW (2016-JAN) Citizen science and the urban ecology of birds and butterflies-a systematic review . PLOS ONE, V11, P23 DOI 10.1371/journal.pone.0156425
7	54	0	Pescott, OL (2015-JAN) Ecological monitoring with citizen science: the design and implementation of schemes for recording plants in britain and ireland . BIOLOGICAL JOURNAL OF THE LINNEAN SOCIETY, V115, P17 DOI 10.1111/bij.12581
7	576	0	Kosmala, M (2016-JAN) Assessing data quality in citizen science . FRONTIERS IN ECOLOGY AND THE ENVIRONMENT, V14, P10 DOI 10.1002/fee.1436
7	9	0	Mellert, KH (2014-JAN) Regionalizing nutrient values of vegetation to assess site fertility of mountain forests in the bavarian alps . FOLIA GEOBOTANICA, V49, P17 DOI 10.1007/s12224-013-9167-z
7	24	0	Bacaro, G (2011-JAN) Geostatistical modelling of regional bird species richness: exploring environmental proxies for conservation purpose .

			BIODIVERSITY AND CONSERVATION, V20, P18 DOI 10.1007/s10531-011-0054-8
6	23	0	Queenborough, SA (2011-JAN) From meso- to macroscale population dynamics: a new density-structured approach . METHODS IN ECOLOGY AND EVOLUTION DOI 10.1111/j.2041-210X.2010.00075.x
6	16	0	Kou, X (2011-JAN) Quantifying species' range shifts in relation to climate change: a case study of abies spp. in china . PLOS ONE DOI 10.1371/journal.pone.0023115
6	41	0	Jackson, MM (2015-JAN) Citizen science and field survey observations provide comparable results for mapping vancouver island white-tailed ptarmigan (lagopus leucura saxatilis) distributions . BIOLOGICAL CONSERVATION, V181, P11 DOI 10.1016/j.biocon.2014.11.010
6	2	0	Michel, V (2010-JAN) Climate change impact on vegetation: lessons from an exceptionally hot and dry decade in south-eastern france. CLIMATE CHANGE AND VARIABILITY
6	161	0	Feeley, KJ (2011-JAN) Keep collecting: accurate species distribution modelling requires more collections than previously thought . DIVERSITY AND DISTRIBUTIONS DOI 10.1111/j.1472-4642.2011.00813.x
6	157	0	Lewandowski, E (2015-JAN) Influence of volunteer and project characteristics on data quality of biological surveys . CONSERVATION BIOLOGY, V29, P11 DOI 10.1111/cobi.12481
6	57	0	Mellert, KH (2011-JAN) Hypothesis-driven species distribution models for tree species in the bavarian alps . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V22, P12 DOI 10.1111/j.1654-1103.2011.01274.x
6	62	0	Lenoir, J (2010-JAN) Forest plant community changes during 1989-2007 in response to climate warming in the jura mountains (france and switzerland) . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V21, P16 DOI 10.1111/j.1654-1103.2010.01201.x
6	16	0	Reger, B (2014-JAN) The trm model of potential natural vegetation in mountain forests . FOLIA GEOBOTANICA, V49, P23 DOI 10.1007/s12224-013-9158-0
5	24	0	Vennetier, M (2009-JAN) Forest flora turnover with climate change in the mediterranean region: a case study in southeastern france . FOREST ECOLOGY AND MANAGEMENT DOI 10.1016/j.foreco.2009.09.015
5	43	0	Huddart, JEA (2016-JAN) Citizen science: from detecting pollution to evaluating ecological restoration . WILEY INTERDISCIPLINARY REVIEWS-WATER DOI 10.1002/wat2.1138
5	28	0	Mellert, KH (2014-JAN) Nutrient limitation and site-related growth potential of norway spruce (picea abies [l.] karst) in the bavarian alps . EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF FOREST RESEARCH, V133, P19 DOI 10.1007/s10342-013-0775-1
5	17	0	Pardo, I (2013-JAN) A novel method to handle the effect of uneven sampling effort in biodiversity databases . PLOS ONE DOI 10.1371/journal.pone.0052786
5	26	0	Marcser, A (2012-JAN) Modelling invasive alien species distributions from digital biodiversity atlases. model upscaling as a means of reconciling data

			at different scales . DIVERSITY AND DISTRIBUTIONS, V18, P13 DOI 10.1111/j.1472-4642.2012.00911.x
5	10	0	Friedmann, B (2011-JAN) Suitability of methods for recording species numbers and cover in alpine long-term vegetation monitoring . PHYTOCOENOLOGIA DOI 10.1127/0340-269X/2011/0041-0480
5	7	0	Haering, T (2014-JAN) Regionalizing indicator values for soil reaction in the bavarian alps - from averages to multivariate spectra . FOLIA GEOBOTANICA, V49, P21 DOI 10.1007/s12224-013-9157-1
5	159	0	Beck, J (2012-JAN) What's on the horizon for macroecology? . ECOGRAPHY, V35, P11 DOI 10.1111/j.1600-0587.2012.07364.x
5	58	0	Butt, N (2013-JAN) Quantifying the sampling error in tree census measurements by volunteers and its effect on carbon stock estimates . ECOLOGICAL APPLICATIONS DOI 10.1890/11-2059.1
5	76	0	Vittoz, P (2010-JAN) Reproducibility of species lists, visual cover estimates and frequency methods for recording high-mountain vegetation . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V21, P13 DOI 10.1111/j.1654-1103.2010.01216.x
5	30	0	Kreyling, J (2010-JAN) Potential consequences of climate warming for tropical plant species in high mountains of southern ethiopia . DIVERSITY AND DISTRIBUTIONS, V16, P13 DOI 10.1111/j.1472-4642.2010.00675.x
4	180	0	Richardson, DM (2010-JAN) Conservation biogeography - foundations, concepts and challenges . DIVERSITY AND DISTRIBUTIONS DOI 10.1111/j.1472-4642.2010.00660.x
4	48	0	Hearn, SM (2011-JAN) The repeatability of vegetation classification and mapping . JOURNAL OF ENVIRONMENTAL MANAGEMENT, V92, P11 DOI 10.1016/j.jenvman.2010.11.021
4	6	0	Baasch, A (2010-JAN) How much effort is required for proper monitoring? assessing the effects of different survey scenarios in a dry acidic grassland . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V21, P12 DOI 10.1111/j.1654-1103.2010.01193.x
4	52	0	Archaux, F (2009-JAN) Can we reliably estimate species richness with large plots? an assessment through calibration training . PLANT ECOLOGY, V203, P13 DOI 10.1007/s11258-008-9551-6
4	42	0	Eyre, TJ (2011-JAN) Measure it to better manage it: a biodiversity monitoring framework for the australian rangelands . RANGELAND JOURNAL, V33, P15 DOI 10.1071/RJ10071
4	387	0	Meyer, C (2016-JAN) Multidimensional biases, gaps and uncertainties in global plant occurrence information . ECOLOGY LETTERS, V19, P15 DOI 10.1111/ele.12624
4	66	0	Feilhauer, H (2011-JAN) On variable relations between vegetation patterns and canopy reflectance . ECOLOGICAL INFORMATICS DOI 10.1016/j.ecoinf.2010.12.004
4	63	0	Pellissier, L (2010-JAN) Spatial pattern of floral morphology: possible insight into the effects of pollinators on plant distributions . OIKOS DOI 10.1111/j.1600-0706.2010.18560.x

4	1165	0	Hortal, J (2015-JAN) Seven shortfalls that beset large-scale knowledge of biodiversity . ANNUAL REVIEW OF ECOLOGY, EVOLUTION, AND SYSTEMATICS, VOL 46, V46, P30 DOI 10.1146/annurev-ecolsys-112414-054400
4	40	0	Bergstedt, J (2009-JAN) In the eye of the beholder: bias and stochastic variation in cover estimates . PLANT ECOLOGY, V204, P13 DOI 10.1007/s11258-009-9590-7
4	13	0	Geri, F (2013-JAN) Mapping patterns of ferns species richness through the use of herbarium data . BIODIVERSITY AND CONSERVATION, V22, P12 DOI 10.1007/s10531-013-0503-7
4	37	0	Kujala, H (2013-JAN) Range margin shifts of birds revisited - the role of spatiotemporally varying survey effort . GLOBAL CHANGE BIOLOGY, V19, P11 DOI 10.1111/gcb.12042
4	346	0	Aertsen, W (2010-JAN) Comparison and ranking of different modelling techniques for prediction of site index in mediterranean mountain forests . ECOLOGICAL MODELLING, V221, P12 DOI 10.1016/j.ecolmodel.2010.01.007
4	84	0	Beauregard, F (2014-JAN) Beyond a climate-centric view of plant distribution: edaphic variables add value to distribution models . PLOS ONE DOI 10.1371/journal.pone.0092642
4	2	0	Converse, R (2016-JAN) Bringing citizen monitoring into land management: a case study of the bosque ecosystem monitoring program. JCOM-JOURNAL OF SCIENCE COMMUNICATION, V15, P14
4	24	0	Reger, B (2011-JAN) Modelling effective thermal climate for mountain forests in the bavarian alps: which is the best model? . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V22, P11 DOI 10.1111/j.1654-1103.2011.01270.x
4	80	0	Crall, AW (2015-JAN) Citizen science contributes to our knowledge of invasive plant species distributions . BIOLOGICAL INVASIONS, V17, P13 DOI 10.1007/s10530-015-0885-4
4	96	0	Milberg, P (2008-JAN) Observer bias and random variation in vegetation monitoring data . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V19, P12 DOI 10.3170/2008-8-18423
4	7	0	Seidling, W (2014-JAN) Vascular plant species richness in forest vegetation records differs depending on surveyor. TUEXENIA
3	1	0	Martellos, S (2016-JAN) Botanical gardens and citizen science: an (as yet) under-exploited potential . PLANT BIOSYSTEMS DOI 10.1080/11263504.2016.1179234
3	299	0	Carvalho, LG (2013-JAN) Species richness declines and biotic homogenisation have slowed down for nw-european pollinators and plants . ECOLOGY LETTERS DOI 10.1111/ele.12121
3	50	0	Greenville, AC (2016-JAN) Population dynamics of desert mammals: similarities and contrasts within a multispecies assemblage . ECOSPHERE DOI 10.1002/ecs2.1343
3	16	0	Greenville, AC (2016-JAN) Spatial and temporal synchrony in reptile population dynamics in variable environments . OECOLOGIA, V182, P11 DOI 10.1007/s00442-016-3672-8

3	200	0	Lavoie, C (2013-JAN) Biological collections in an ever changing world: herbaria as tools for biogeographical and environmental studies. PERSPECTIVES IN PLANT ECOLOGY EVOLUTION AND SYSTEMATICS DOI 10.1016/j.ppees.2012.10.002
3	69	0	Kelling, S (2015-JAN) Can observation skills of citizen scientists be estimated using species accumulation curves? . PLOS ONE, V10, P20 DOI 10.1371/journal.pone.0139600
3	59	0	Cox, TE (2012-JAN) Expert variability provides perspective on the strengths and weaknesses of citizen-driven intertidal monitoring program. ECOLOGICAL APPLICATIONS, V22, P12 DOI 10.1890/11-1614.1
3	10	0	Karl, JW (2014-JAN) A double-sampling approach to deriving training and validation data for remotely-sensed vegetation products. INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF REMOTE SENSING, V35, P20 DOI 10.1080/01431161.2014.880820
3	71	0	Worthington, JP (2012-JAN) Evolution megalab: a case study in citizen science methods. METHODS IN ECOLOGY AND EVOLUTION DOI 10.1111/j.2041-210X.2011.00164.x
3	6	0	Buesching, CD (2015-JAN) Many hands make light work-but do they? a critical evaluation of citizen science. WILDLIFE CONSERVATION ON FARMLAND, VOL 2: CONFLICT IN THE COUNTRYSIDE
3	5	0	Aranda, SC (2015-JAN) The iterative process of plant species inventorying for obtaining reliable biodiversity patterns. BOTANICAL JOURNAL OF THE LINNEAN SOCIETY, V177, P13 DOI 10.1111/boj.12259
3	55	0	Forrester, G (2015-JAN) Comparing monitoring data collected by volunteers and professionals shows that citizen scientists can detect long-term change on coral reefs. JOURNAL FOR NATURE CONSERVATION DOI 10.1016/j.jnc.2015.01.002
3	115	0	Vittoz, P (2009-JAN) Low impact of climate change on subalpine grasslands in the swiss northern alps. GLOBAL CHANGE BIOLOGY, V15, P12 DOI 10.1111/j.1365-2486.2008.01707.x
3	65	0	Feilhauer, H (2009-JAN) Mapping continuous fields of forest alpha and beta diversity. APPLIED VEGETATION SCIENCE, V12, P11 DOI 10.1111/j.1654-109X.2009.01037.x
3	63	0	Freitag, A (2013-JAN) Process, not product: investigating recommendations for improving citizen science "success". PLOS ONE DOI 10.1371/journal.pone.0064079
3	21	0	Birnbaum, P (2015-JAN) Environmental correlates for tree occurrences, species distribution and richness on a high-elevation tropical island. AOB PLANTS DOI 10.1093/aobpla/plv075
3	21	0	Rutherford, MC (2011-JAN) Early post-fire plant succession in peninsula sandstone fynbos: the first three years after disturbance. SOUTH AFRICAN JOURNAL OF BOTANY, V77, P10 DOI 10.1016/j.sajb.2011.02.002
3	24	0	Archaux, F (2009-JAN) Could we obtain better estimates of plot species richness from multiple-observer plant censuses? . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE DOI 10.1111/j.1654-1103.2009.01079.x

3	6	0	Macdonald, AJ (2010-JAN) Testing the reliability of assessment of land management impacts on scottish upland vegetation. PLANT ECOLOGY & DIVERSITY DOI 10.1080/17550874.2010.542781
3	109	0	Robertson, MP (2010-JAN) Getting the most out of atlas data. DIVERSITY AND DISTRIBUTIONS, V16, P13 DOI 10.1111/j.1472-4642.2010.00639.x
3	9	0	Hespanhol, H (2015-JAN) How to describe species richness patterns for bryophyte conservation?. ECOLOGY AND EVOLUTION DOI 10.1002/ece3.1796
3	38	0	Bornand, CN (2014-JAN) Hide-and-peek in vegetation: time-to-detection is an efficient design for estimating detectability and occurrence. METHODS IN ECOLOGY AND EVOLUTION DOI 10.1111/2041-210X.12171
3	85	0	Jansen, F (2010-JAN) Plant names in vegetation databases - a neglected source of bias. JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE DOI 10.1111/j.1654-1103.2010.01209.x
3	17	0	Thimonier, A (2011-JAN) Ground vegetation monitoring in swiss forests: comparison of survey methods and implications for trend assessments. ENVIRONMENTAL MONITORING AND ASSESSMENT, V174, P17 DOI 10.1007/s10661-010-1759-y

Appendix 2 Table 6 Cluster 4

Coverage	GCS	LCS	Bibliography
15	4	0	Vynokurov, D (2024-JAN) Dry grasslands and thorn-cushion communities of armenia: a first syntaxonomic classification . VEGETATION CLASSIFICATION AND SURVEY DOI 10.3897/VCS.119253
15	66	0	Dengler, J (2023-JAN) Ecological indicator values for europe (eive) 1.0 . VEGETATION CLASSIFICATION AND SURVEY DOI 10.3897/VCS.98324
14	13	0	Peterka, T (2020-JAN) Is variable plot size a serious constraint in broad-scale vegetation studies? a case study on fens . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V31, P12 DOI 10.1111/jvs.12885
13	271	0	Chytry, M (2020-JAN) Eunis habitat classification: expert system, characteristic species combinations and distribution maps of european habitats . APPLIED VEGETATION SCIENCE, V23, P28 DOI 10.1111/avsc.12519
13	11	0	Yannelli, FA (2022-JAN) Fifteen emerging challenges and opportunities for vegetation science: a horizon scan by early career researchers . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V33, P18 DOI 10.1111/jvs.13119
12	6	0	Rodriguez-rojo, MP (2020-JAN) An expert system as an applied tool for the conservation of semi-natural grasslands on the iberian peninsula . BIODIVERSITY AND CONSERVATION, V29, P16 DOI 10.1007/s10531-020-01963-1
12	6	0	Noriyuki, M (2021-JAN) A new formal classification for japanese forest vegetation based on traditional phytosociological concepts . APPLIED VEGETATION SCIENCE, V24, P24 DOI 10.1111/avsc.12611
12	62	0	Biurrun, I (2021-JAN) Benchmarking plant diversity of palaeartic grasslands and other open habitats . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V32, P21 DOI 10.1111/jvs.13050
12	2	0	Liu, C (2024-JAN) Predicting the responses of european grassland communities to climate and land cover change . PHILOSOPHICAL TRANSACTIONS OF THE ROYAL SOCIETY B-BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES, V379, P15 DOI 10.1098/rstb.2023.0335
12	10	0	Harasek, M (2023-JAN) Vegetation change in acidic dry grasslands in moravia (czech republic) over three decades: slow decrease in habitat quality after grazing cessation . APPLIED VEGETATION SCIENCE, V26, P16 DOI 10.1111/avsc.12726
12	10	0	Kacki, Z (2020-JAN) Formalized hierarchically nested expert system for classification of mesic and wet grasslands in poland . ACTA SOCIETATIS BOTANICORUM POLONIAE, V89, P14 DOI 10.5586/asbp.8941
12	36	0	Landucci, F (2020-JAN) Classification of the european marsh vegetation (phragmito-magnocaricetea) to the association level . APPLIED VEGETATION SCIENCE, V23, P20 DOI 10.1111/avsc.12484
12	9	0	Garcia-mijangos, I (2021-JAN) Grasslands of navarre (spain), focusing on the festuco- brometea : classification, hierarchical and characterisation . VEGETATION CLASSIFICATION AND SURVEY DOI 10.3897/VCS/2021/69614

11	48	0	Bonari, G (2021-JAN) Classification of the mediterranean lowland to submontane pine forest vegetation . APPLIED VEGETATION SCIENCE, V24, P37 DOI 10.1111/avsc.12544
10	5	0	Axmanova, I (2024-JAN) Catalogue of expansive plants of the czech republic . PRESLIA, V96, P29 DOI 10.23855/preslia.2024.299
10	7	0	Dembicz, I (2021-JAN) Fine-grain beta diversity in palaeartic open vegetation: variability within and between biomes and vegetation types . VEGETATION CLASSIFICATION AND SURVEY DOI 10.3897/VCS/2021/77193
10	4	0	Sabatini, FM (2023-JAN) Vegetation of southern patagonia in the 1970s-digitization of a gray-literature data set as a monitoring baseline in a changing world . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V34, P10 DOI 10.1111/jvs.13209
10	2	0	Skobel, N (2024-JAN) Nordic-baltic grassland vegetation database (nbgvd) - current state and future prospects . VEGETATION CLASSIFICATION AND SURVEY DOI 10.3897/VCS.119968
9	140	0	Chytry, M (2021-JAN) Pladias database of the czech flora and vegetation . PRESLIA, V93, P87 DOI 10.23855/preslia.2021.001
9	25	0	Biurrun, I (2016-JAN) Floodplain forests of the iberian peninsula: vegetation classification and climatic features . APPLIED VEGETATION SCIENCE, V19, P19 DOI 10.1111/avsc.12219
9	17	0	Midolo, G (2024-JAN) Diversity and distribution of raunkiaer's life forms in european vegetation . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V35, P15 DOI 10.1111/jvs.13229
9	15	0	Bruehlheide, H (2020-JAN) Deriving site-specific species pools from large databases . ECOGRAPHY, V43, P14 DOI 10.1111/ecog.05172
9	15	0	Magnes, M (2021-JAN) Xeric grasslands of the inner-alpine dry valleys of austria - new insights into syntaxonomy, diversity and ecology . VEGETATION CLASSIFICATION AND SURVEY DOI 10.3897/VCS/2021/68594
9	4	0	Kermavnar, J (2024-JAN) Three decades of understorey vegetation change in quercus-dominated forests as a result of increasing canopy mortality and global change symptoms . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V35, P20 DOI 10.1111/jvs.13317
9	1	0	Hartmann, LJ (2025-JAN) Productivity, moisture and competition-habitat conditions affecting population viability of the wet grassland orchid dactylorhiza majalis under conservation-oriented management . JOURNAL OF APPLIED ECOLOGY, V62, P16 DOI 10.1111/1365-2664.70024
9	959	0	Mucina, L (2016-JAN) Vegetation of europe: hierarchical floristic classification system of vascular plant, bryophyte, lichen, and algal communities . APPLIED VEGETATION SCIENCE, V19, P262 DOI 10.1111/avsc.12257
9	8	0	Alessi, N (2023-JAN) Probabilistic and preferential sampling approaches offer integrated perspectives of italian forest diversity . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V34, P13 DOI 10.1111/jvs.13175

9	2	0	Ramzi, S (2024-JAN) Iranveg - the vegetation database of iran: current status and the way forward . VEGETATION CLASSIFICATION AND SURVEY DOI 10.3897/VCS.114081
9	1	0	Le, dez M (2021-JAN) An expert system for the conservation of atlantic estuarine wet meadows: application to a natura 2000 site in france . BIODIVERSITY AND CONSERVATION, V30, P21 DOI 10.1007/s10531-021-02310-8
8	2	0	Guuroh, RT (2024-JAN) African vegetation studies: introduction to a special collection . VEGETATION CLASSIFICATION AND SURVEY DOI 10.3897/VCS.143360
8	2	0	Partel, M (2022-JAN) Macroecology of vegetation - lessons learnt from the virtual special issue . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE DOI 10.1111/jvs.13121
8	4	0	Kumpli, J (2021-JAN) Vegetation changes in urban grasslands over 25 years in the city of zurich, switzerland . TUEXENIA DOI 10.14471/2021.41.018
8	4	0	Boch, S (2021-JAN) Grasslands of temperate europe in a changing world - editorial to the 16th edgg special feature in tuexenia . TUEXENIA DOI 10.14471/2021.41.020
8	26	0	Wagner, V (2021-JAN) Alien plant invasion hotspots and invasion debt in european woodlands . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V32, P15 DOI 10.1111/jvs.13014
8	22	0	Hajek, M (2020-JAN) Towards the pan-european bioindication system: assessing and testing updated hydrological indicator values for vascular plants and bryophytes in mires . ECOLOGICAL INDICATORS, V116, P10 DOI 10.1016/j.ecolind.2020.106527
8	0	0	Buzhdygan, O (2025-JAN) Scale-dependent effects of plant diversity drivers across different grassland habitats in ukraine . ECOLOGY AND EVOLUTION, V15, P16 DOI 10.1002/ece3.70941
8	6	0	Maciejewski, L (2020-JAN) Vegetation unit assignments: phytosociology experts and classification programs show similar performance but low convergence . APPLIED VEGETATION SCIENCE, V23, P12 DOI 10.1111/avsc.12516
7	84	0	Sabatini, FM (2021-JAN) Splotopen - an environmentally balanced, open-access, global dataset of vegetation plots . GLOBAL ECOLOGY AND BIOGEOGRAPHY, V30, P25 DOI 10.1111/geb.13346
7	16	0	Agrillo, E (2018-JAN) The use of large databases to characterize habitat types: the case of quercus suber woodlands in europe . RENDICONTI LINCEI-SCIENZE FISICHE E NATURALI, V29, P11 DOI 10.1007/s12210-018-0703-x
7	26	0	Boch, S (2019-JAN) Mean indicator values suggest decreasing habitat quality in swiss dry grasslands and are robust to relocation error . TUEXENIA DOI 10.14471/2019.39.010
7	28	0	Luis, villasenor J (2022-JAN) Floristics in mexico today: insights into a better understanding of biodiversity in a megadiverse country . BOTANICAL SCIENCES, V100, P20 DOI 10.17129/botsci.3050

7	28	0	Villasenor, JL (2022-JAN) Floristics in mexico today: insights into a better understanding of biodiversity in a megadiverse country . BOTANICAL SCIENCES DOI 10.17129/botsoci.3050
7	8	0	Attorre, F (2020-JAN) Finite mixture model-based classification of a complex vegetation system . VEGETATION CLASSIFICATION AND SURVEY DOI 10.3897/VCS/2020/48518
7	24	0	Cheng, C (2023-JAN) Plant species richness on the tibetan plateau: patterns and determinants . ECOGEOGRAPHY, V2023, P14 DOI 10.1111/ecog.06265
7	36	0	Tichy, L (2020-JAN) Optimal transformation of species cover for vegetation classification . APPLIED VEGETATION SCIENCE DOI 10.1111/avsc.12510
7	29	0	Dembicz, I (2021-JAN) Fine-grain beta diversity of palaeartic grassland vegetation . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V32, P15 DOI 10.1111/jvs.13045
7	39	0	Guarino, R (2021-JAN) Alien plant invasions in mediterranean habitats: an assessment for sicily . BIOLOGICAL INVASIONS, V23, P17 DOI 10.1007/s10530-021-02561-0
7	65	0	Willner, W (2019-JAN) Formalized classification of semi-dry grasslands in central and eastern europe . PRESLIA, V91, P25 DOI 10.23855/preslia.2019.025
6	19	0	Kalnikova, V (2021-JAN) Vegetation of the european mountain river gravel bars: a formalized classification . APPLIED VEGETATION SCIENCE, V24, P27 DOI 10.1111/avsc.12542
6	15	0	Fanfarillo, E (2020-JAN) Patterns of co-occurrence of rare and threatened species in winter arable plant communities of italy . DIVERSITY-BASEL, V12, P11 DOI 10.3390/d12050195
6	0	0	Fahs, N (2025-JAN) Parasitic plants in europe: ecological niches and spatial patterns . PLANT BIOLOGY DOI 10.1111/plb.70099
6	41	0	Guarino, R (2018-JAN) Spatio-temporal variations in the application of the braun-blanquet approach in europe . PHYTOCOENOLOGIA, V48, P12 DOI 10.1127/phyto/2017/0181
6	38	0	Boch, S (2021-JAN) Effects of fertilization and irrigation on vascular plant species richness, functional composition and yield in mountain grasslands . JOURNAL OF ENVIRONMENTAL MANAGEMENT DOI 10.1016/j.jenvman.2020.111629
6	5	0	Kalusova, V (2023-JAN) Neophyte invasions in european heathlands and scrub . BIOLOGICAL INVASIONS, V25, P27 DOI 10.1007/s10530-023-03005-7
6	8	0	Naqinezhad, A (2021-JAN) Syntaxonomy and biogeography of the irano-turanian mires and springs . APPLIED VEGETATION SCIENCE, V24, P30 DOI 10.1111/avsc.12571
6	8	0	Berg, C (2020-JAN) The whole and its parts: why and how to disentangle plant communities and synusiae in vegetation classification . APPLIED VEGETATION SCIENCE DOI 10.1111/avsc.12461
6	13	0	Jirousek, M (2022-JAN) Classification of european bog vegetation of the oxycocco-sphagnetea class . APPLIED VEGETATION SCIENCE, V25, P19 DOI 10.1111/avsc.12646

6	37	0	Cao, pinna L (2021-JAN) The biogeography of alien plant invasions in the mediterranean basin . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V32, P13 DOI 10.1111/jvs.12980
6	29	0	Del, vecchio S (2018-JAN) Biogeographic variability of coastal perennial grasslands at the european scale . APPLIED VEGETATION SCIENCE, V21, P10 DOI 10.1111/avsc.12356
6	3	0	Kacki, Z (2021-JAN) Formalized classification of ephemeral wetland vegetation (isoeto-nanojuncetea class) in poland (central europe) . PEERJ DOI 10.7717/peerj.11703
6	22	0	Vecera, M (2021-JAN) Mapping species richness of plant families in european vegetation . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V32, P17 DOI 10.1111/jvs.13035
6	10	0	Hajek, M (2021-JAN) Variability and classification of carpathian calcium-rich fens: breaking the state borders . PRESLIA, V93, P33 DOI 10.23855/preslia.2021.203
6	3	0	Pielech, R (2018-JAN) Changes in species composition in alder swamp forest following forest dieback . FORESTS DOI 10.3390/f9060316
6	12	0	Bergauer, M (2022-JAN) Scale-dependent patterns and drivers of vascular plant, bryophyte and lichen diversity in dry grasslands of the swiss inneralpine valleys . ALPINE BOTANY, V132, P15 DOI 10.1007/s00035-022-00285-y
6	8	0	Biurrun, I (2019-JAN) Vegetation classification and its application are relevant globally . PHYTOCOENOLOGIA DOI 10.1127/phyto/2019/0323
6	14	0	Kavgaci, A (2021-JAN) Classification of forest and shrubland vegetation in mediterranean turkey . APPLIED VEGETATION SCIENCE, V24, P29 DOI 10.1111/avsc.12589
6	10	0	Carli, E (2018-JAN) Using vegetation dynamics to face the challenge of the conservation status assessment in semi-natural habitats . RENDICONTI LINCEI-SCIENZE FISICHE E NATURALI, V29, P12 DOI 10.1007/s12210-018-0707-6
5	16	0	Lisner, A (2020-JAN) Everyone makes mistakes: sampling errors in vegetation analysis - the effect of different sampling methods, abundance estimates, experimental manipulations, and data transformation . ACTA OECOLOGICA-INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ECOLOGY, V109, P10 DOI 10.1016/j.actao.2020.103667
5	35	0	Axmanova, I (2021-JAN) Neophyte invasions in european grasslands . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V32, P17 DOI 10.1111/jvs.12994
5	0	0	Miholcsa, Z (2025-JAN) In the footsteps of sheep herds: the neonative xeranthemum cylindraceum has no impact but indicates ruderalisation of overgrazed pastures in the new range . APPLIED VEGETATION SCIENCE, V28, P10 DOI 10.1111/avsc.70041
5	57	0	Vecera, M (2019-JAN) Alpha diversity of vascular plants in european forests . JOURNAL OF BIOGEOGRAPHY, V46, P17 DOI 10.1111/jbi.13624
5	6	0	Vassilev, K (2024-JAN) Classification of the high-rank syntaxa of the central and eastern balkan dry grasslands with a new hierarchical expert

			system approach . APPLIED VEGETATION SCIENCE, V27, P29 DOI 10.1111/avsc.12779
5	2	0	Walther, G (2022-JAN) Functional rarity of plants in german hay meadows - patterns on the species level and mismatches with community species richness . ECOLOGY AND EVOLUTION, V12, P16 DOI 10.1002/ece3.9375
5	1	0	Szymura, TH (2023-JAN) Vegetation databases augment but do not replace species distribution atlases in species richness assessment . ECOLOGICAL INDICATORS DOI 10.1016/j.ecolind.2023.110876
5	5	0	Alessi, N (2022-JAN) Ams-vegbank: a new database of vegetation plots for the italian territory . VEGETATION CLASSIFICATION AND SURVEY DOI 10.3897/VCS.85083
5	27	0	Boch, S (2019-JAN) Threatened and specialist species suffer from increased wood cover and productivity in swiss steppes . FLORA DOI 10.1016/j.flora.2019.151444
5	21	0	Bonari, G (2018-JAN) Eu priority habitats: rethinking mediterranean coastal pine forests . RENDICONTI LINCEI-SCIENZE FISICHE E NATURALI, V29, P13 DOI 10.1007/s12210-018-0684-9
5	29	0	Tichy, L (2019-JAN) Grimp: a machine-learning method for improving groups of discriminating species in expert systems for vegetation classification . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V30, P13 DOI 10.1111/jvs.12696
5	4	0	Bergmeier, E (2016-JAN) Classifying halophytes and halophytic vegetation - an editorial . PHYTOCOENOLOGIA DOI 10.1127/phyto/2016/0174
5	9	0	Peterka, T (2022-JAN) The long history of rich fens supports persistence of plant and snail habitat specialists . BIODIVERSITY AND CONSERVATION, V31, P19 DOI 10.1007/s10531-021-02318-0
5	1	0	Hegedusova, K (2020-JAN) Syntaxonomical revision of thetrisetoflavescens-polygonion bistortaealliance in the carpathians . PLANT BIOSYSTEMS, V155, P26 DOI 10.1080/11263504.2020.1801877
5	10	0	Charmillot, K (2021-JAN) Vegetation change in meso-xeric grasslands of the swiss jura mts. over 40 years . TUEXENIA DOI 10.14471/2021.41.019
5	4	0	Dengler, J (2024-JAN) Vegetation classification and survey is performing well . VEGETATION CLASSIFICATION AND SURVEY DOI 10.3897/VCS.118454
5	22	0	Chytry, M (2018-JAN) National vegetation classification of the czech republic: a summary of the approach . PHYTOCOENOLOGIA, V48, P11 DOI 10.1127/phyto/2017/0184
5	4	0	Tomaselli, M (2021-JAN) Scree vegetation in the northern apennines (n-italy) . PHYTOCOENOLOGIA, V51, P56 DOI 10.1127/phyto/2021/0391
5	45	0	Hajek, M (2021-JAN) A european map of groundwater ph and calcium . EARTH SYSTEM SCIENCE DATA, V13, P17 DOI 10.5194/essd-13-1089-2021
5	48	0	Walker, DA (2018-JAN) Circumpolar arctic vegetation classification . PHYTOCOENOLOGIA, V48, P21 DOI 10.1127/phyto/2017/0192

5	118	0	Sabatini, FM (2022-JAN) Global patterns of vascular plant alpha diversity . NATURE COMMUNICATIONS, V13, P16 DOI 10.1038/s41467-022-32063-z
5	16	0	Fanfarillo, E (2020-JAN) Species composition, richness, and diversity of weed communities of winter arable land in relation to geo-environmental factors: a gradient analysis in mainland italy . BOTANY, V98, P12 DOI 10.1139/cjb-2019-0178
5	2	0	Boch, S (2025-JAN) Haymaking complemented by moderate disturbances can sustain and restore species-rich alpine to subalpine grasslands . ALPINE BOTANY, V135, P14 DOI 10.1007/s00035-024-00320-0
5	0	0	Midolo, G (2025-JAN) Nineteenth-century land use shapes the current occurrence of some plant species, but weakly affects the richness and total composition of central european grasslands . LANDSCAPE ECOLOGY, V40, P18 DOI 10.1007/s10980-024-02016-6
5	8	0	de, francesco MC (2023-JAN) Identifying critical thresholds in the impacts of invasive alien plants and dune paths on native coastal dune vegetation . LAND, V12, P16 DOI 10.3390/land12010135
4	0	0	Dembicz, I (2025-JAN) Drivers of plant and lichen diversity in grasslands on mineral islands surrounded by peatlands (biebrza valley, ne poland) . PERSPECTIVES IN PLANT ECOLOGY EVOLUTION AND SYSTEMATICS, V67, P15 DOI 10.1016/j.ppees.2025.125870
4	1	0	Alonso, maya-lastra C (2022-JAN) The mexican flora as a case study in systematics: a meta-analysis of genbank accessions . BOTANICAL SCIENCES, V100, P17 DOI 10.17129/botsci.3061
4	1	0	Deschenes, E (2024-JAN) Mosses and vascular plants show diverging diversity patterns along a latitudinal gradient in boreal bogs and fens . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V35, P16 DOI 10.1111/jvs.13249
4	24	0	Mokany, K (2022-JAN) Patterns and drivers of plant diversity across australia . ECOGRAPHY, V2022, P15 DOI 10.1111/ecog.06426
4	8	0	Hegedusova, K (2021-JAN) Thermophilous oak forests in slovakia: classification of vegetation and an expert system . PRESLIA, V93, P35 DOI 10.23855/preslia.2021.089
4	3	0	Dengler, J (2022-JAN) Vegetation classification and survey: development and diversification . VEGETATION CLASSIFICATION AND SURVEY DOI 10.3897/VCS.80379
4	1	0	Fantinato, E (2023-JAN) Alien plant colonisation and community homogenisation: cause or consequence? a test in coastal dunes . PLANT BIOSYSTEMS, V157, P10 DOI 10.1080/11263504.2023.2176941
4	8	0	Riedel, S (2023-JAN) The historic square foot dataset - outstanding small-scale richness in swiss grasslands around the year 1900 . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V34, P11 DOI 10.1111/jvs.13208
4	2	0	Li, X (2023-JAN) Identifying hotspots of woody plant diversity and their relevance with home ranges of the critically endangered gibbon (nomascus hainanus) across forest landscapes within a tropical nature reserve . FRONTIERS IN PLANT SCIENCE, V14, P13 DOI 10.3389/fpls.2023.1283037

4	3	0	Cancellieri, L (2024-JAN) Drivers of vascular plant, bryophyte and lichen richness in grasslands along a precipitation gradient (central apennines, italy) . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V35, P14 DOI 10.1111/jvs.13305
4	2	0	Dubyna, DV (2023-JAN) Alien plant invasion across coastal dunes of ukraine . BIOLOGIA, V78, P14 DOI 10.1007/s11756-023-01369-8
4	4	0	Janisova, M (2024-JAN) Exploring a grassland biodiversity hotspot in the serbian carpathians: interdisciplinary perspectives and conservation implications . BIOLOGICAL CONSERVATION, V299, P11 DOI 10.1016/j.biocon.2024.110822
4	23	0	Hajek, M (2022-JAN) Rising temperature modulates ph niches of fen species . GLOBAL CHANGE BIOLOGY, V28, P15 DOI 10.1111/gcb.15980
4	10	0	Cambria, S (2023-JAN) New data on native and alien vascular flora of sicily (italy): new findings and updates . PLANTS-BASEL, V12, P20 DOI 10.3390/plants12091743
4	12	0	Fratte, MD (2022-JAN) Identifying typical and early warning species by the combination of functional-based diagnostic species and dark diversity . BIODIVERSITY AND CONSERVATION, V31, P19 DOI 10.1007/s10531-022-02427-4
4	15	0	Karakose, M (2019-JAN) Numerical classification and ordination of esenli (giresun) forest vegetation . BIOLOGIA, V74, P13 DOI 10.2478/s11756-019-00321-z
4	4	0	Guarino, R (2022-JAN) Plant communities, synusiae and the arithmetic of a sustainable classification . VEGETATION CLASSIFICATION AND SURVEY DOI 10.3897/VCS.60951
4	0	0	Boch, S (2024-JAN) Editorial to the 17th edgg special feature in tuexenia . TUEXENIA DOI 10.14471/2024.44.012
4	14	0	Kalnikova, V (2018-JAN) Early vegetation succession on gravel bars of czech carpathian streams . FOLIA GEOBOTANICA, V53, P16 DOI 10.1007/s12224-018-9323-6
4	25	0	Sporbert, M (2021-JAN) Different sets of traits explain abundance and distribution patterns of european plants at different spatial scales . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V32, P15 DOI 10.1111/jvs.13016
4	7	0	Jansen, F (2020-JAN) Vegetation classification goes open access . VEGETATION CLASSIFICATION AND SURVEY DOI 10.3897/VCS/2020/53445
4	3	0	Varricchione, M (2021-JAN) Diagnostic species diversity pattern can provide key information on vegetation change: an insight into high mountain habitats in central apennines . JOURNAL OF ZOOLOGICAL AND BOTANICAL GARDENS DOI 10.3390/jzbg2030033
4	0	0	Tichy, L (2020-JAN) Central-european vegetation types and their optima along successional gradient . PRESLIA, V92, P12 DOI 10.23855/preslia.2020.341
4	11	0	Jansen, F (2016-JAN) Vegetation classification: a task of our time . PHYTOCOENOLOGIA DOI 10.1127/phyto/2016/0134

4	0	0	Rasino, MdV (2025-JAN) Linking taxonomic diversity and ecological traits of geometrid moths and plants in coastal dunes: insights from a mediterranean lter site . ECOLOGICAL INDICATORS, V178, P14 DOI 10.1016/j.ecolind.2025.113975
4	7	0	Kavgaci, A (2023-JAN) Classification of forest and shrubland vegetation in central and eastern euxine turkey and sw georgia . APPLIED VEGETATION SCIENCE, V26, P30 DOI 10.1111/avsc.12753
4	10	0	Paetsch, R (2019-JAN) Making them visible and usable - vegetation-plot observations from fennoscandia based on historical species-quantity scales . APPLIED VEGETATION SCIENCE DOI 10.1111/avsc.12452
4	5	0	Massetti, L (2023-JAN) Detection of yucca gloriosa in mediterranean coastal dunes: a comparative analysis of field-based sampling, human interpretation of uav imagery and deep learning to develop an effective tool for controlling invasive plants . REGIONAL STUDIES IN MARINE SCIENCE, V68, P11 DOI 10.1016/j.rsma.2023.103265
4	9	0	Peterka, T (2023-JAN) Formalized classification of the class montio-cardaminetea in europe: towards a consistent typology of spring vegetation . PRESLIA, V95, P37 DOI 10.23855/preslia.2023.347
3	9	0	Lengyel, A (2020-JAN) Trait-based numerical classification of mesic and wet grasslands in poland . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V31, P12 DOI 10.1111/jvs.12850
3	1	0	Jakob, A (2025-JAN) Determination of forest communities on the basis of small plots (microplots) within the geomorphologically diverse landscape of the kras plateau (italy, slovenia) . FOREST ECOSYSTEMS, V12, P10 DOI 10.1016/j.fecs.2024.100283
3	23	0	Tordoni, E (2021-JAN) Disentangling native and alien plant diversity in coastal sand dune ecosystems worldwide . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V32, P13 DOI 10.1111/jvs.12961
3	3	0	Addicott, E (2019-JAN) Supervised versus un-supervised classification: a quantitative comparison of plant communities in savanna vegetation . APPLIED VEGETATION SCIENCE, V22, P10 DOI 10.1111/avsc.12442
3	4	0	Szokala, D (2023-JAN) Alpine and subalpine acidophilous vegetation on the eastern side of the chiprovska planina mts. . TUEXENIA, V43, P58 DOI 10.14471/2023.43.001
3	4	0	Sfair, JC (2022-JAN) Functional rarity and evolutionary uniqueness of threatened species across different scales and habitats in a central european flora . JOURNAL OF APPLIED ECOLOGY, V59, P11 DOI 10.1111/1365-2664.14255
3	87	0	Peterka, T (2017-JAN) Formalized classification of european fen vegetation at the alliance level . APPLIED VEGETATION SCIENCE, V20, P19 DOI 10.1111/avsc.12271
3	36	0	Kolari, THM (2021-JAN) Accelerated vegetation succession but no hydrological change in a boreal fen during 20 years of recent climate change . ECOLOGY AND EVOLUTION, V11, P20 DOI 10.1002/ece3.7592

3	3	0	Terzi, M (2023-JAN) A new asphodelus ramosus-dominated association from the murge plateau (se italy) . HACQUETIA, V22, P17 DOI 10.2478/hacq-2022-0020
3	4	0	Man, M (2022-JAN) Dalibor: database of lichens and bryophytes of the czech republic . PRESLIA, V94, P27 DOI 10.23855/preslia.2022.579
3	2	0	Jaskova, A (2020-JAN) European boreal forest vegetation database . PHYTOCOENOLOGIA, V50, P14 DOI 10.1127/phyto/2019/0336
3	1	0	Jasprica, N (2023-JAN) Contribution to the syntaxonomy of plant communities with insular endemic species of genus brassica (southern croatia) . HACQUETIA, V22, P18 DOI 10.2478/hacq-2022-0019
3	6	0	Fantinato, E (2023-JAN) Growth-survival trade-offs and the restoration of non-forested open ecosystems . GLOBAL ECOLOGY AND CONSERVATION, V41, P10 DOI 10.1016/j.gecco.2023.e02383
3	15	0	Costanza, JK (2018-JAN) Classifying forest inventory data into species-based forest community types at broad extents: exploring tradeoffs among supervised and unsupervised approaches . FOREST ECOSYSTEMS DOI 10.1186/s40663-017-0123-x
3	32	0	Cai, Q (2021-JAN) The relationship between niche breadth and range size of beech (fagus) species worldwide . JOURNAL OF BIOGEOGRAPHY, V48, P14 DOI 10.1111/jbi.14074
3	0	0	Naqinezhad, A (2025-JAN) Advancing vegetation classification of grassland ecosystems across asia: current status and way forward . VEGETATION CLASSIFICATION AND SURVEY DOI 10.3897/VCS.151773
3	22	0	Hobohm, C (2019-JAN) Global endemics-area relationships of vascular plants . PERSPECTIVES IN ECOLOGY AND CONSERVATION DOI 10.1016/j.pecon.2019.04.002
3	7	0	Essl, F (2021-JAN) New and old invaders in forests in eastern austria: the role of species attributes and invasion history . FLORA DOI 10.1016/j.flora.2021.151922
3	4	0	Viciani, D (2018-JAN) Woods with quercus petraea (matt.) Liebl. in tuscany (italy): a vegetation classification approach . MEDITERRANEAN BOTANY, V39, P14 DOI 10.5209/MBOT.59040
3	1	0	Janisova, M (2024-JAN) Agricultural legacy shapes plant diversity patterns in mountain grasslands of maramures and bukovina: a cross-border perspective (ukraine, romania) . PEOPLE AND NATURE DOI 10.1002/pan3.10698
3	0	0	Novak, P (2025-JAN) Ravine forests in colchis (georgia) - azonal forests in a tertiary relict flora hotspot . VEGETATION CLASSIFICATION AND SURVEY DOI 10.3897/VCS.154417
3	20	0	Ivanova, N (2024-JAN) Global overview of the application of the braun-blanquet approach in research . FORESTS, V15, P34 DOI 10.3390/f15060937
3	5	0	Nowak, A (2022-JAN) Geobotany revisited - a glimpse at the blooming and influential discipline with its strong roots in the beauty of nature and the pragmatic need of its protection . ACTA SOCIETATIS BOTANICORUM POLONIAE, V91, P27 DOI 10.5586/asbp.912

3	8	0	Agrillo, E (2023-JAN) Modeling approach for coastal dune habitat detection on coastal ecosystems combining very high-resolution uav imagery and field survey . REMOTE SENSING IN ECOLOGY AND CONSERVATION DOI 10.1002/rse2.308
3	5	0	Mullerova, A (2020-JAN) What is a reasonable plot size for sampling aquatic vegetation? . AQUATIC SCIENCES, V82, P10 DOI 10.1007/s00027-020-00743-x
3	1	0	Alexandrova, A (2020-JAN) Forest vegetation diversity of the slivenska mountain (eastern stara planina, bulgaria) . HACQUETIA, V19, P26 DOI 10.2478/hacq-2020-0009
3	45	0	Giulio, S (2020-JAN) Alien flora across european coastal dunes . APPLIED VEGETATION SCIENCE, V23, P11 DOI 10.1111/avsc.12490
3	3	0	Bolpagni, R (2022-JAN) A longitudinal snapshot of pioneer plant patterns along lowland temperate rivers . RIVER RESEARCH AND APPLICATIONS, V38, P10 DOI 10.1002/rra.3988
3	10	0	Willner, W (2021-JAN) Braun-blanquet meets ecoveg: a formation and division level classification of european phytosociological units . VEGETATION CLASSIFICATION AND SURVEY DOI 10.3897/VCS/2021/71299
3	4	0	De, sanctis M (2018-JAN) The forest communities of shebenik-jabllanice national park (central albania) . PHYTOCOENOLOGIA, V48, P26 DOI 10.1127/phyto/2017/0205
3	8	0	Karakose, M (2021-JAN) Numerical classification and ordination of finike (antalya) forest vegetation . BIOLOGIA, V76, P15 DOI 10.1007/s11756-021-00910-x
3	1	0	Bennett, JA (2021-JAN) Using functional dissimilarity among species pools and communities to predict establishment of native and alien species . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V32, P12 DOI 10.1111/jvs.13062
3	15	0	Peyre, G (2019-JAN) Fine-scale plant richness mapping of the andean paramo according to macroclimate . FRONTIERS IN ECOLOGY AND EVOLUTION DOI 10.3389/fevo.2019.00377
3	6	0	Reutimann, P (2023-JAN) Effects of grazing versus mowing on the vegetation of wet grasslands in the northern pre-alps, switzerland . APPLIED VEGETATION SCIENCE, V26, P12 DOI 10.1111/avsc.12706
3	13	0	Lami, F (2021-JAN) Habitat type and community age as barriers to alien plant invasions in coastal species-habitat networks . ECOLOGICAL INDICATORS, V133, P10 DOI 10.1016/j.ecolind.2021.108450
3	109	0	Cai, L (2023-JAN) Global models and predictions of plant diversity based on advanced machine learning techniques . NEW PHYTOLOGIST, V237, P14 DOI 10.1111/nph.18533
3	3	0	Skobel, N (2023-JAN) Biodiversity surveys of grassland and coastal habitats in 2021 as a documentation of pre-war status in southern ukraine . BIODIVERSITY DATA JOURNAL, V11, P19 DOI 10.3897/BDJ.11.e99605

3	0	0	Dembicz, I (2025-JAN) Should we estimate plant cover in percent or on ordinal scales? ii - diversity indices . VEGETATION CLASSIFICATION AND SURVEY DOI 10.3897/VCS.144252
3	31	0	Divisek, J (2018-JAN) High-resolution and large-extent mapping of plant species richness using vegetation-plot databases . ECOLOGICAL INDICATORS, V89, P12 DOI 10.1016/j.ecolind.2017.11.005
3	1	0	Swacha, G (2024-JAN) Varying patterns of taxonomic and functional plant composition and diversity across different types of urban and rural grasslands . LAND DEGRADATION & DEVELOPMENT, V35, P14 DOI 10.1002/ldr.5273
3	57	0	Willner, W (2017-JAN) A higher-level classification of the pannonian and western pontic steppe grasslands (central and eastern europe) . APPLIED VEGETATION SCIENCE, V20, P16 DOI 10.1111/avsc.12265
3	7	0	Alessi, N (2018-JAN) Phytocoenological approach to the ecology of laurus nobilis l. in italy . RENDICONTI LINCEI-SCIENZE FISICHE E NATURALI, V29, P12 DOI 10.1007/s12210-018-0677-8
3	6	0	Dahler, NB (2019-JAN) Effectiveness of swiss protected areas in maintaining populations of rare vascular plants . JOURNAL FOR NATURE CONSERVATION DOI 10.1016/j.jnc.2019.125749
3	1	0	Stanbury, DPB (2020-JAN) Hedgerow management experiment relevant to agri-environment schemes: cutting regime impacts species richness of basal flora and ellenberg indicator profiles . BIODIVERSITY AND CONSERVATION, V29, P13 DOI 10.1007/s10531-020-01989-5
3	23	0	Filibeck, G (2019-JAN) Exploring the drivers of vascular plant richness at very fine spatial scale in sub-mediterranean limestone grasslands (central apennines, italy) . BIODIVERSITY AND CONSERVATION, V28, P25 DOI 10.1007/s10531-019-01788-7
3	3	0	Swierkosz, K (2022-JAN) Differentiation of natural scrub communities of the cotoneastro-amelanchieretum group in central europe . PLOS ONE, V17, P20 DOI 10.1371/journal.pone.0266868
3	2	0	Dite, Z (2022-JAN) Isolated occurrence of halophytic vegetation on mineral springs in the eastern and western carpathians . FOLIA GEOBOTANICA, V57, P16 DOI 10.1007/s12224-023-09426-5
3	8	0	Danihelka, J (2022-JAN) Halophytic flora and vegetation in southern moravia . PRESLIA, V94, P98 DOI 10.23855/preslia.2022.013
3	36	0	De, caceres M (2018-JAN) Global overview of plot-based vegetation classification approaches . PHYTOCOENOLOGIA, V48, P12 DOI 10.1127/phyto/2018/0256
3	0	0	Iemelianova, S (2025-JAN) Syntaxonomy of the class alnetea glutinosae in ukraine: a critical revision . VEGETATION CLASSIFICATION AND SURVEY DOI 10.3897/VCS.122617
3	0	0	Ostrowski, G (2025-JAN) Mean ecological indicator values: use eive but no cover-weighting . VEGETATION CLASSIFICATION AND SURVEY DOI 10.3897/VCS.134800
3	20	0	Sporbert, M (2019-JAN) Assessing sampling coverage of species distribution in biodiversity databases . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V30, P13 DOI 10.1111/jvs.12763

3	8	0	Tichy, L (2019-JAN) Probabilistic key for identifying vegetation types in the field: a new method and android application . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE DOI 10.1111/jvs.12799
3	36	0	Marceno, C (2021-JAN) Facebook groups as citizen science tools for plant species monitoring . JOURNAL OF APPLIED ECOLOGY, V58, P11 DOI 10.1111/1365-2664.13896

Appendix 2 Table 7 Cluster 5

Coverage	GCS	LCS	Bibliography
15	96	0	Kopecky, M (2015-JAN) Vegetation resurvey is robust to plot location uncertainty . DIVERSITY AND DISTRIBUTIONS DOI 10.1111/ddi.12299
15	4	0	Bergmeier, E (2015-JAN) Re-launch of phytocoenologia: new profile for the classic vegetation ecology journal . PHYTOCOENOLOGIA, V45, P10 DOI 10.1127/phyto/2015/0069
14	146	0	De, caceres M (2015-JAN) A comparative framework for broad-scale plot-based vegetation classification . APPLIED VEGETATION SCIENCE, V18, P18 DOI 10.1111/avsc.12179
14	477	0	Dengler, J (2014-JAN) Biodiversity of palaeartic grasslands: a synthesis . AGRICULTURE ECOSYSTEMS & ENVIRONMENT, V182, P14 DOI 10.1016/j.agee.2013.12.015
13	124	0	Chytry, M (2012-JAN) Vegetation of the czech republic: diversity, ecology, history and dynamics. PRESLIA, V84, P78
12	75	0	Turtureanu, PD (2014-JAN) Scale- and taxon-dependent biodiversity patterns of dry grassland vegetation in transylvania . AGRICULTURE ECOSYSTEMS & ENVIRONMENT, V182, P10 DOI 10.1016/j.agee.2013.10.028
11	17	0	Acic, S (2014-JAN) Nomenclatural revision of dry grassland syntaxa of the central balkan. TUEXENIA
10	42	0	Berg, C (2014-JAN) Red lists and conservation prioritization of plant communities - a methodological framework . APPLIED VEGETATION SCIENCE, V17, P12 DOI 10.1111/avsc.12093
9	2	0	Pysek, P (2014-JAN) Preslia: hundred years of exploring central-european flora and vegetation. PRESLIA, V86, P11
9	5	0	Attorre, F (2013-JAN) Botanical information in the italian biodiversity network: one year of data aggregation and future perspectives . PLANT BIOSYSTEMS DOI 10.1080/11263504.2013.860054
8	9	0	Izco, J (2015-JAN) Risk of extinction of plant communities: risk and assessment categories . PLANT BIOSYSTEMS, V149, P14 DOI 10.1080/11263504.2014.1000998
8	9	0	Swacha, G (2016-JAN) Classification of molinia meadows in poland using a hierarchical expert system . PHYTOCOENOLOGIA, V46, P15 DOI 10.1127/phyto/2016/0094
8	108	0	Faber-langendoen, D (2014-JAN) Ecoveg: a new approach to vegetation description and classification . ECOLOGICAL MONOGRAPHS, V84, P29 DOI 10.1890/13-2334.1
8	25	0	Viciani, D (2014-JAN) Natura 2000 habitats in tuscany (central italy): synthesis of main conservation features based on a comprehensive database . BIODIVERSITY AND CONSERVATION, V23, P26 DOI 10.1007/s10531-014-0686-6
8	28	0	Pilar, rodriguez-rojo M (2014-JAN) Vegetation diversity of mesic grasslands (arrhenatheretalia) in the iberian peninsula . APPLIED VEGETATION SCIENCE, V17, P17 DOI 10.1111/avsc.12118

8	12	0	Farris, E (2013-JAN) Human trampling effects on mediterranean coastal dune plants . PLANT BIOSYSTEMS DOI 10.1080/11263504.2013.861540
8	27	0	Kuzemko, AA (2014-JAN) Dry grassland vegetation of central podolia (ukraine) - a preliminary overview of its syntaxonomy, ecology and biodiversity. TUEXENIA
7	11	0	Kasari, L (2016-JAN) Hybrid ecosystems can contribute to local biodiversity conservation . BIODIVERSITY AND CONSERVATION, V25, P19 DOI 10.1007/s10531-016-1218-3
7	114	0	Douda, J (2016-JAN) Vegetation classification and biogeography of european floodplain forests and alder carrs . APPLIED VEGETATION SCIENCE, V19, P17 DOI 10.1111/avsc.12201
7	87	0	Dengler, J (2012-JAN) Festuco-brometea communities of the transylvanian plateau (romania) - a preliminary overview on syntaxonomy, ecology, and biodiversity. TUEXENIA
7	22	0	Jimenez-alfaro, B (2014-JAN) The number of vegetation types in european countries: major determinants and extrapolation to other regions . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V25, P10 DOI 10.1111/jvs.12145
7	0	0	Bloch-orlowska, J (2016-JAN) Diversity of vegetation with carex chordorrhiza l.f. and factors affecting the species abundance across its geographical range in europe . FLORA, V224, P12 DOI 10.1016/j.flora.2016.07.003
6	36	0	Dengler, J (2013-JAN) Towards a consistent classification of european grasslands . APPLIED VEGETATION SCIENCE DOI 10.1111/avsc.12041
6	959	0	Mucina, L (2016-JAN) Vegetation of europe: hierarchical floristic classification system of vascular plant, bryophyte, lichen, and algal communities . APPLIED VEGETATION SCIENCE, V19, P262 DOI 10.1111/avsc.12257
6	74	0	Rolecek, J (2014-JAN) Understanding the extreme species richness of semi-dry grasslands in east-central europe: a comparative approach. PRESLIA, V86, P22
6	10	0	Viciani, D (2017-JAN) Natura 2000 protected habitats, massaciuccoli lake (northern tuscan, italy) . JOURNAL OF MAPS DOI 10.1080/17445647.2017.1290557
6	26	0	Angiolini, C (2017-JAN) Habitat conservation prioritization: a floristic approach applied to a mediterranean wetland network . PLANT BIOSYSTEMS, V151, P15 DOI 10.1080/11263504.2016.1187678
6	8	0	Zajac, M (2016-JAN) Classification of semi-natural mesic grasslands in the ukrainian carpathians . PHYTOCOENOLOGIA, V46, P37 DOI 10.1127/phyto/2016/0104
6	11	0	Janisova, M (2016-JAN) Classification of palaeartic grasslands . PHYTOCOENOLOGIA DOI 10.1127/phyto/2016/0169
6	19	0	Bagella, S (2013-JAN) Gap analysis revealed a low efficiency of natura 2000 network for the conservation of endemic species in mediterranean temporary freshwater habitats . PLANT BIOSYSTEMS DOI 10.1080/11263504.2013.860055

6	0	0	Koczur, A (2016-JAN) Coenology of the stands of the endangered liliu bulbiferum subsp bulbiferum on the north-eastern border of its range in europe . TUEXENIA DOI 10.14471/2016.36.004
6	69	0	Landucci, F (2015-JAN) Formalized classification of species-poor vegetation: a proposal of a consistent protocol for aquatic vegetation . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V26, P13 DOI 10.1111/jvs.12277
5	25	0	Biurrun, I (2016-JAN) Floodplain forests of the iberian peninsula: vegetation classification and climatic features . APPLIED VEGETATION SCIENCE, V19, P19 DOI 10.1111/avsc.12219
5	5	0	Wang, GM (2013-JAN) Challenge of weed risk assessment (wra) for ecological restoration in china: the case of rhus typhina l. and the new officially released weed risk assessment system . PLANT BIOSYSTEMS DOI 10.1080/11263504.2013.852632
5	31	0	Michalcova, D (2014-JAN) High plant diversity of grasslands in a landscape context: a comparison of contrasting regions in central europe . FOLIA GEOBOTANICA, V49, P19 DOI 10.1007/s12224-013-9173-1
5	73	0	Janisova, M (2014-JAN) Landscape effects on diversity of semi-natural grasslands . AGRICULTURE ECOSYSTEMS & ENVIRONMENT, V182, P12 DOI 10.1016/j.agee.2013.05.022
5	18	0	Korzeniak, J (2016-JAN) Mountain nardus stricta grasslands as a relic of past farming - the effects of grazing abandonment in relation to elevation and spatial scale . FOLIA GEOBOTANICA, V51, P21 DOI 10.1007/s12224-016-9246-z
5	9	0	Vymazalova, M (2014-JAN) How does vegetation sampling in different parts of the growing season influence classification results and analyses of beta diversity? . APPLIED VEGETATION SCIENCE, V17, P11 DOI 10.1111/avsc.12087
5	19	0	Lengyel, A (2015-JAN) Assessing the relative importance of methodological decisions in classifications of vegetation data . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V26, P12 DOI 10.1111/jvs.12268
5	13	0	Reczynska, K (2015-JAN) Diversity and ecology of oak forests in sw poland (sudetes mts.) . PHYTOCOENOLOGIA, V45, P21 DOI 10.1127/phyto/2015/0021
5	20	0	Landucci, F (2014-JAN) A prioritized inventory of crop wild relatives and wild harvested plants of italy . CROP SCIENCE, V54, P17 DOI 10.2135/cropsci2013.05.0355
5	22	0	Gennai, M (2014-JAN) The nardus-rich communities in the northern apennines (n-italy): a phytosociological, ecological and phytogeographical study . PHYTOCOENOLOGIA, V44, P26 DOI 10.1127/0340-269X/2014/0044-0574
5	34	0	Pedashenko, H (2013-JAN) Dry grasslands of nw bulgarian mountains: first insights into diversity, ecology and syntaxonomy. TUEXENIA
5	68	0	Elias, P (2013-JAN) Vegetation diversity of salt-rich grasslands in southeast europe . APPLIED VEGETATION SCIENCE, V16, P17 DOI 10.1111/avsc.12017

5	28	0	Perronne, R (2014-JAN) Contrasted taxonomic, phylogenetic and functional diversity patterns in semi-natural permanent grasslands along an altitudinal gradient . PLANT ECOLOGY AND EVOLUTION, V147, P11 DOI 10.5091/plecevo.2014.885
5	25	0	Diaz, A (2013-JAN) Conservation implications of long-term changes detected in a lowland heath plant metacommunity . BIOLOGICAL CONSERVATION DOI 10.1016/j.biocon.2013.08.018
5	41	0	Blasi, C (2017-JAN) Ecosystem mapping for the implementation of the european biodiversity strategy at the national level: the case of italy . ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCE & POLICY, V78, P12 DOI 10.1016/j.envsci.2017.09.002
4	12	0	Vymazalova, M (2016-JAN) The role of vernal species in vegetation classification: a case study on deciduous forests and dry grasslands of central europe . PHYTOCOENOLOGIA, V46, P12 DOI 10.1127/phyto/2016/0034
4	13	0	Oliver, I (2013-JAN) Semi-automated assignment of vegetation survey plots within an a priori classification of vegetation types . METHODS IN ECOLOGY AND EVOLUTION DOI 10.1111/j.2041-210x.2012.00258.x
4	43	0	Jimenez-alfaro, B (2014-JAN) Biogeographic patterns of base-rich fen vegetation across europe . APPLIED VEGETATION SCIENCE, V17, P14 DOI 10.1111/avsc.12065
4	17	0	Walker, DA (2013-JAN) Rescuing valuable arctic vegetation data for biodiversity models, ecosystem models and a panarctic vegetation classification. ARCTIC
4	12	0	Swierkosz, K (2014-JAN) Variability of abies alba-dominated forests in central europe . CENTRAL EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF BIOLOGY DOI 10.2478/s11535-013-0281-y
4	12	0	Huellbusch, E (2016-JAN) Little vegetation change during two decades in a dry grassland complex in the biosphere reserve schorfheide-chorin (ne germany) . TUEXENIA DOI 10.14471/2016.36.019
4	92	0	Chytry, M (2014-JAN) Assessing vegetation change using vegetation-plot databases: a risky business . APPLIED VEGETATION SCIENCE, V17, P10 DOI 10.1111/avsc.12050
4	112	0	Lavorel, S (2017-JAN) Pathways to bridge the biophysical realism gap in ecosystem services mapping approaches . ECOLOGICAL INDICATORS, V74, P20 DOI 10.1016/j.ecolind.2016.11.015
4	15	0	Reczynska, K (2015-JAN) The spread of impatiens parviflora dc. in central european oak forests - another stage of invasion? . ACTA SOCIETATIS BOTANICORUM POLONIAE, V84, P11 DOI 10.5586/asbp.2015.039
4	28	0	Tesitel, J (2015-JAN) Habitats and ecological niches of root-hemiparasitic plants: an assessment based on a large database of vegetation plots. PRESLIA, V87, P22
4	18	0	Hajek, M (2017-JAN) Long-lasting imprint of former glassworks on vegetation pattern in an extremely species-rich grassland: a battle of species pools on mesic soils . ECOSYSTEMS, V20, P17 DOI 10.1007/s10021-017-0107-2

4	84	0	Diekmann, M (2014-JAN) Long-term changes in calcareous grassland vegetation in north-western germany - no decline in species richness, but a shift in species composition . BIOLOGICAL CONSERVATION, V172, P10 DOI 10.1016/j.biocon.2014.02.038
4	19	0	Bedini, G (2016-JAN) Wikiplantbase #toscana, breaking the dormancy of floristic data . PLANT BIOSYSTEMS, V150, P10 DOI 10.1080/11263504.2015.1057266
4	316	0	Chytry, M (2016-JAN) European vegetation archive (eva): an integrated database of european vegetation plots . APPLIED VEGETATION SCIENCE DOI 10.1111/avsc.12191
4	26	0	Slezak, M (2014-JAN) Numerical classification of alder carr and riparian alder forests in slovakia . PHYTOCOENOLOGIA, V44, P26 DOI 10.1127/0340-269X/2014/0044-0588
4	57	0	Merunkova, K (2012-JAN) White carpathian grasslands: can local ecological factors explain their extraordinary species richness?. PRESLIA, V84, P15
4	19	0	Willner, W (2013-JAN) Syntaxonomic revision of the pannonian grasslands of austria - part i: introduction and general overview. TUEXENIA
4	38	0	Staley, JT (2013-JAN) Changes in hedgerow floral diversity over 70 years in an english rural landscape, and the impacts of management . BIOLOGICAL CONSERVATION DOI 10.1016/j.biocon.2013.07.033
4	32	0	Ujhazyova, M (2016-JAN) Diversity of beech forest vegetation in the eastern alps, bohemian massif and the western carpathians. PRESLIA, V88, P23
4	64	0	Schroeter, M (2017-JAN) Citizen science for assessing ecosystem services: status, challenges and opportunities . ECOSYSTEM SERVICES, V28, P15 DOI 10.1016/j.ecoser.2017.09.017
4	27	0	Roberts, DW (2015-JAN) Vegetation classification by two new iterative reallocation optimization algorithms . PLANT ECOLOGY, V216, P18 DOI 10.1007/s11258-014-0403-2
4	136	0	Chytry, M (2015-JAN) The most species-rich plant communities in the czech republic and slovakia (with new world records). PRESLIA, V87, P62
3	2583	0	Baskin, CC (2014-JAN) Seeds ecology, biogeography, and evolution of dormancy and germination second edition introduction . SEEDS: ECOLOGY, BIOGEOGRAPHY, AND EVOLUTION OF DORMANCY AND GERMINATION, 2ND EDITION DOI 10.1016/B978-0-12-416677-6.00001-9
3	17	0	Kobrllova, L (2016-JAN) Symphytum tuberosum complex in central europe: cytogeography, morphology, ecology and taxonomy. PRESLIA, V88, P36
3	2	0	Chytry, M (2015-JAN) Plant communities: their conservation assessment and surveys across continents and in the tropics . APPLIED VEGETATION SCIENCE DOI 10.1111/avsc.12146
3	4	0	Szymura, TH (2015-JAN) The effect of ecological niche and spatial pattern on the diversity of oak forest vegetation . PLANT ECOLOGY & DIVERSITY DOI 10.1080/17550874.2015.1010186

3	19	0	Prach, K (2017-JAN) Participation of the czech flora in succession at disturbed sites: quantifying species' colonization ability . PRESLIA, V89, P14 DOI 10.23855/preslia.2017.087
3	11	0	Kosuthova, AD (2013-JAN) Ecological indicator values and life history traits of terricolous lichens of the western carpathians . ECOLOGICAL INDICATORS, V34, P14 DOI 10.1016/j.ecolind.2013.05.013
3	61	0	Jiang, M (2013-JAN) Mapping ecosystem service and biodiversity changes over 70 years in a rural english county . JOURNAL OF APPLIED ECOLOGY, V50, P10 DOI 10.1111/1365-2664.12093
3	2	0	Korzeniak, J (2016-JAN) Grasslands in the polish carpathians - a regional thematic phytosociological database . PHYTOCOENOLOGIA DOI 10.1127/phyto/2016/0102
3	15	0	Sengl, P (2016-JAN) Only large and highly-connected semi-dry grasslands achieve plant conservation targets in an agricultural matrix . TUEXENIA DOI 10.14471/2016.36.008
3	42	0	Polyakova, MA (2016-JAN) Scale- and taxon-dependent patterns of plant diversity in steppes of khakassia, south siberia (russia) . BIODIVERSITY AND CONSERVATION, V25, P23 DOI 10.1007/s10531-016-1093-y
3	16	0	Lomba, A (2013-JAN) Simulating long-term effects of abandonment on plant diversity in mediterranean mountain farmland . PLANT BIOSYSTEMS, V147, P15 DOI 10.1080/11263504.2012.716794
3	45	0	Juergens, N (2012-JAN) The biota biodiversity observatories in africa-a standardized framework for large-scale environmental monitoring . ENVIRONMENTAL MONITORING AND ASSESSMENT, V184, P24 DOI 10.1007/s10661-011-1993-y
3	13	0	Sengl, P (2017-JAN) A test of naturalness indicator values to evaluate success in grassland restoration . COMMUNITY ECOLOGY DOI 10.1556/168.2017.18.2.8
3	16	0	Marignani, M (2014-JAN) Is time on our side? strengthening the link between field efforts and conservation needs . BIODIVERSITY AND CONSERVATION, V23, P11 DOI 10.1007/s10531-013-0610-5
3	5	0	Korzeniak, J (2013-JAN) Scope and data set of the phytosociological database 'grasslands in the polish carpathians' . ACTA SOCIETATIS BOTANICORUM POLONIAE DOI 10.5586/asbp.2013.019
3	665	0	Wilson, JB (2012-JAN) Plant species richness: the world records . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE DOI 10.1111/j.1654-1103.2012.01400.x
3	4	0	Svitkova, I (2013-JAN) An expert-based classification of high-altitude arctic-alpine vegetation of the class carici rupestris-kobresietea ohba 1974: achievements and obstacles . PLANT BIOSYSTEMS, V147, P13 DOI 10.1080/11263504.2012.736422
3	2	0	Dite, D (2014-JAN) The heleochloetum alopecuroidis association in the pannonian basin - fiction or reality? . BIOLOGIA DOI 10.2478/s11756-014-0433-1

Appendix 2 Table 8 Cluster 6

Coverage	GCS	LCS	Bibliography
17	13	0	Klinkovska, K (2024-JAN) Dynamics of the czech flora over the last 60 years: winners, losers and causes of changes . BIOLOGICAL CONSERVATION, V292, P14 DOI 10.1016/j.biocon.2024.110502
15	72	0	Jandt, U (2022-JAN) More losses than gains during one century of plant biodiversity change in germany . NATURE, V611, P26 DOI 10.1038/s41586-022-05320-w
13	2	0	Klinkovska, K (2025-JAN) Half a century of temperate non-forest vegetation changes: no net loss in species richness, but considerable shifts in taxonomic and functional composition . GLOBAL CHANGE BIOLOGY, V31, P17 DOI 10.1111/gcb.70030
13	22	0	Trindade, DPF (2020-JAN) Temporal lags in observed and dark diversity in the anthropocene . GLOBAL CHANGE BIOLOGY DOI 10.1111/gcb.15093
12	4	0	Cipa, J (2024-JAN) Accelerating change of vegetation in carpathian beech and mixed montane forests over 55 years . FOREST ECOLOGY AND MANAGEMENT, V568, P20 DOI 10.1016/j.foreco.2024.122006
11	16	0	Jandt, U (2022-JAN) Resurveygermany: vegetation-plot time-series over the past hundred years in germany . SCIENTIFIC DATA DOI 10.1038/s41597-022-01688-6
10	2	0	Reczynska, K (2024-JAN) Solid as a rock: the main drivers of changes in natural, rocky plant communities . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V35, P17 DOI 10.1111/jvs.13263
10	4	0	Luettgert, L (2022-JAN) Repeated habitat mapping data reveal gains and losses of plant species . ECOSPHERE, V13, P18 DOI 10.1002/ecs2.4244
9	10	0	Essl, F (2024-JAN) Potential sources of time lags in calibrating species distribution models . JOURNAL OF BIOGEOGRAPHY, V51, P14 DOI 10.1111/jbi.14726
9	2	0	Bonari, G (2025-JAN) Grassland changes in the eastern alps over four decades: unveiling patterns along an elevation gradient . APPLIED VEGETATION SCIENCE, V28, P14 DOI 10.1111/avsc.70012
9	0	0	Coldea, G (2025-JAN) No decline in plant species diversity despite noticeable land use changes over 58 years (carpathian foothills, romania) . EARTH SYSTEMS AND ENVIRONMENT DOI 10.1007/s41748-025-00853-2
9	10	0	Harasek, M (2023-JAN) Vegetation change in acidic dry grasslands in moravia (czech republic) over three decades: slow decrease in habitat quality after grazing cessation . APPLIED VEGETATION SCIENCE, V26, P16 DOI 10.1111/avsc.12726
9	0	0	Widmer, S (2025-JAN) One century of change: stronger diversity decline in lowland than in mountain grasslands in central europe . GLOBAL CHANGE BIOLOGY, V31, P13 DOI 10.1111/gcb.70529
8	59	0	Staude, IR (2022-JAN) Directional turnover towards larger-ranged plants over time and across habitats . ECOLOGY LETTERS, V25, P17 DOI 10.1111/ele.13937

8	44	0	Valdez, JWW (2023-JAN) The undetectability of global biodiversity trends using local species richness . ECOGRAPHY, V2023, P14 DOI 10.1111/ecog.06604
8	10	0	Caron, MM (2021-JAN) Thermal differences between juveniles and adults increased over time in european forest trees . JOURNAL OF ECOLOGY, V109, P14 DOI 10.1111/1365-2745.13773
8	3	0	Zeidler, M (2023-JAN) Homogenization and species compositional shifts in subalpine vegetation during the 60-year period . ACTA SOCIETATIS BOTANICORUM POLONIAE, V92, P10 DOI 10.5586/asbp/171689
8	4	0	Kindlund, YK (2023-JAN) Magnitude and drivers of plant diversity loss differ between spatial scales in scania, sweden 1957-2021 . APPLIED VEGETATION SCIENCE, V26, P16 DOI 10.1111/avsc.12730
8	66	0	Dengler, J (2023-JAN) Ecological indicator values for europe (eive) 1.0 . VEGETATION CLASSIFICATION AND SURVEY DOI 10.3897/VCS.98324
8	48	0	Dornelas, M (2023-JAN) Looking back on biodiversity change: lessons for the road ahead . PHILOSOPHICAL TRANSACTIONS OF THE ROYAL SOCIETY B-BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES, V378, P15 DOI 10.1098/rstb.2022.0199
7	22	0	Staude, IR (2023-JAN) Prioritize grassland restoration to bend the curve of biodiversity loss . RESTORATION ECOLOGY DOI 10.1111/rec.13931
7	2	0	Liu, C (2024-JAN) Predicting the responses of european grassland communities to climate and land cover change . PHILOSOPHICAL TRANSACTIONS OF THE ROYAL SOCIETY B-BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES, V379, P15 DOI 10.1098/rstb.2023.0335
7	2	0	Buron, M (2024-JAN) Rapid declines in species diversity and occurrence of common plant species are related to nutrient availability and soil moisture in open habitats . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V35, P12 DOI 10.1111/jvs.13316
7	440	0	Blowes, SA (2019-JAN) The geography of biodiversity change in marine and terrestrial assemblages . SCIENCE, V366, P86 DOI 10.1126/science.aaw1620
7	5	0	Axmanova, I (2024-JAN) Catalogue of expansive plants of the czech republic . PRESLIA, V96, P29 DOI 10.23855/preslia.2024.299
7	0	0	Luttgert, L (2025-JAN) Loss of characteristic species of open habitats across germany detected by repeated mapping of protected habitats . BIOLOGICAL CONSERVATION, V311, P11 DOI 10.1016/j.biocon.2025.111410
7	4	0	Padulles, cubino J (2024-JAN) Evaluating plant lineage losses and gains in temperate forest understories: a phylogenetic perspective on climate change and nitrogen deposition . NEW PHYTOLOGIST, V241, P13 DOI 10.1111/nph.19477
7	3	0	Kermavnar, J (2024-JAN) Mixed signals of environmental change and a trend towards ecological homogenization in ground vegetation across different forest types . FOLIA GEOBOTANICA, V58, P20 DOI 10.1007/s12224-024-09445-w

7	7	0	Schwaiger, H (2022-JAN) No species loss, but pronounced species turnover in grasslands in the northern alps over 25 years . APPLIED VEGETATION SCIENCE, V25, P12 DOI 10.1111/avsc.12700
6	2	0	Luettgert, L (2024-JAN) Linking trends of habitat types and plant species using repeated habitat mapping data . APPLIED VEGETATION SCIENCE, V27, P17 DOI 10.1111/avsc.12799
6	1	0	Hartmann, LJ (2025-JAN) Productivity, moisture and competition-habitat conditions affecting population viability of the wet grassland orchid dactylorhiza majalis under conservation-oriented management . JOURNAL OF APPLIED ECOLOGY, V62, P16 DOI 10.1111/1365-2664.70024
6	5	0	Kindermann, E (2024-JAN) Resurveying inner-alpine dry grasslands after 70 years calls for integrative conservation efforts . BIOLOGICAL CONSERVATION, V289, P13 DOI 10.1016/j.biocon.2023.110393
6	5	0	Borderieux, J (2024-JAN) Extinction drives recent thermophilization but does not trigger homogenization in forest understorey . NATURE ECOLOGY & EVOLUTION DOI 10.1038/s41559-024-02362-3
6	15	0	Zolotova, E (2023-JAN) Global overview of modern research based on ellenberg indicator values . DIVERSITY-BASEL, V15, P18 DOI 10.3390/d15010014
6	11	0	Yannelli, FA (2022-JAN) Fifteen emerging challenges and opportunities for vegetation science: a horizon scan by early career researchers . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V33, P18 DOI 10.1111/jvs.13119
6	0	0	Heinrichs, S (2023-JAN) Constancy and dynamics in a species-rich beech forest on limestone - continuation of a time series from 1981 to 2021 . TUEXENIA, V43, P33 DOI 10.14471/2023.43.009
6	0	0	Fanfarillo, E (2025-JAN) Different control strategies of the invasive plant arundo donax l. have taxon-specific effects on above-and belowground biodiversity . JOURNAL OF ENVIRONMENTAL MANAGEMENT, V392, P11 DOI 10.1016/j.jenvman.2025.126833
6	4	0	Kermavnar, J (2024-JAN) Three decades of understorey vegetation change in quercus-dominated forests as a result of increasing canopy mortality and global change symptoms . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V35, P20 DOI 10.1111/jvs.13317
6	1	0	Erdos, L (2024-JAN) Between-year weather differences and long-term environmental trends both contribute to observed vegetation changes in a plot resurvey study . ECOLOGY AND EVOLUTION, V14, P14 DOI 10.1002/ece3.70244
6	12	0	Saatkamp, A (2023-JAN) Climate change impacts on mediterranean vegetation are amplified at low altitudes . GLOBAL ECOLOGY AND BIOGEOGRAPHY, V32, P14 DOI 10.1111/geb.13682
6	25	0	De, palma A (2021-JAN) Annual changes in the biodiversity intactness index in tropical and subtropical forest biomes, 2001-2012 . SCIENTIFIC REPORTS, V11, P13 DOI 10.1038/s41598-021-98811-1
6	4	0	Sabatini, FM (2023-JAN) Vegetation of southern patagonia in the 1970s-digitization of a gray-literature data set as a monitoring baseline in a

			changing world . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V34, P10 DOI 10.1111/jvs.13209
6	2	0	Golivets, M (2024-JAN) Future changes in key plant traits across central europe vary with biogeographical status, woodiness, and habitat type . SCIENCE OF THE TOTAL ENVIRONMENT, V907, P13 DOI 10.1016/j.scitotenv.2023.167954
6	6	0	Auffret, AG (2024-JAN) Underprediction of extirpation and colonisation following climate and land-use change using species distribution models . DIVERSITY AND DISTRIBUTIONS, V30, P13 DOI 10.1111/ddi.13834
5	14	0	Schuele, M (2023-JAN) Long-term effects of environmental alterations in protected grasslands-land-use history determines changes in plant species composition . ECOLOGICAL ENGINEERING, V188, P13 DOI 10.1016/j.ecoleng.2022.106878
5	7	0	Ivanova, N (2023-JAN) Landolt indicator values in modern research: a review . SUSTAINABILITY, V15, P22 DOI 10.3390/su15129618
5	6	0	Kiebacher, T (2023-JAN) Thermophilisation of communities differs between land plant lineages, land use types and elevation . SCIENTIFIC REPORTS, V13, P13 DOI 10.1038/s41598-023-38195-6
5	8	0	Hu, T (2024-JAN) High-resolution mapping of grassland canopy cover in china through the integration of extensive drone imagery and satellite data . ISPRS JOURNAL OF PHOTOGRAMMETRY AND REMOTE SENSING, V218, P15 DOI 10.1016/j.isprsjprs.2024.09.004
5	7	0	Holestova, A (2024-JAN) Contrasting responses of forest phenological guilds to complex floodplain change . JOURNAL OF ECOLOGY, V112, P16 DOI 10.1111/1365-2745.14310
5	16	0	Staude, IR (2023-JAN) Biodiversity change in light of succession theory . OIKOS, V2023, P11 DOI 10.1111/oik.09883
5	8	0	Meier, T (2021-JAN) Floristic changes of xerothermic grasslands in central germany: a resurvey study based on quasi-permanent plots . TUEXENIA DOI 10.14471/2021.41.009
5	55	0	Rolls, RJ (2023-JAN) Biotic homogenisation and differentiation as directional change in beta diversity: synthesising driver-response relationships to develop conceptual models across ecosystems . BIOLOGICAL REVIEWS, V98, P36 DOI 10.1111/brv.12958
5	4	0	Scherrer, D (2024-JAN) Impacts of climate warming, pollution, and management on the vegetation composition of central european beech forests . ECOLOGICAL INDICATORS, V160, P10 DOI 10.1016/j.ecolind.2024.111888
5	14	0	Seliger, A (2023-JAN) Changes of vegetation in coniferous monocultures in the context of conversion to mixed forests in 30 years-implications for biodiversity restoration . JOURNAL OF ENVIRONMENTAL MANAGEMENT, V343, P12 DOI 10.1016/j.jenvman.2023.118199
5	1	0	Haberlin, KER (2025-JAN) Recent biodiversity changes in grasslands across elevational bands in switzerland . BASIC AND APPLIED ECOLOGY DOI 10.1016/j.baae.2025.05.003

5	9	0	Saatkamp, A (2023-JAN) Calibrating ecological indicator values and niche width for a mediterranean flora . PLANT BIOSYSTEMS, V157, P11 DOI 10.1080/11263504.2022.2104399
5	1	0	Dietzel, S (2025-JAN) When to mow and how: short-term effects of river dike grassland management on arthropod abundance, species richness, and community composition . JOURNAL OF INSECT CONSERVATION, V29, P13 DOI 10.1007/s10841-025-00656-w
5	5	0	Reczynska, K (2021-JAN) Phytosociological analysis of natural and artificial pine forests of the class vaccinio-piceetea br.-bl. in br.-bl. et al. 1939 in the sudetes and their foreland (bohemian massif, central europe) . FORESTS, V12, P23 DOI 10.3390/f12010098
5	30	0	Auffret, AG (2022-JAN) Climate warming has compounded plant responses to habitat conversion in northern europe . NATURE COMMUNICATIONS, V13, P11 DOI 10.1038/s41467-022-35516-7
5	6	0	Douda, J (2023-JAN) Historical sampling error: a neglected factor in long-term biodiversity change research . BIOLOGICAL CONSERVATION DOI 10.1016/j.biocon.2023.110317
5	1	0	Ballesteros, M (2024-JAN) Participation of grassland species in various successional series in a temperate european region and implications for habitat management . GLOBAL ECOLOGY AND CONSERVATION, V49, P10 DOI 10.1016/j.gecco.2023.e02761
4	38	0	Mentges, A (2021-JAN) Effects of site-selection bias on estimates of biodiversity change . CONSERVATION BIOLOGY, V35, P11 DOI 10.1111/cobi.13610
4	3	0	Saether, B (2024-JAN) Assessing the sensitivity and resistance of communities in a changing environment . JOURNAL OF ANIMAL ECOLOGY, V93, P13 DOI 10.1111/1365-2656.14003
4	0	0	Paudel, R (2025-JAN) Many plants naturalized as aliens abroad have also become more common within their native regions . NATURE COMMUNICATIONS, V16, P11 DOI 10.1038/s41467-025-63293-6
4	140	0	Chytry, M (2021-JAN) Pladias database of the czech flora and vegetation . PRESLIA, V93, P87 DOI 10.23855/preslia.2021.001
4	4	0	Collart, F (2024-JAN) To what extent can we predict variation of bryophyte and tracheophyte community composition at fine spatial scale along an elevation gradient? . SCIENCE OF THE TOTAL ENVIRONMENT, V926, P13 DOI 10.1016/j.scitotenv.2024.171741
4	0	0	Riedel, S (2025-JAN) Lasting legacies: relicts of historical plant communities in central european grasslands amid a century of biodiversity loss . BIOLOGICAL CONSERVATION, V312, P11 DOI 10.1016/j.biocon.2025.111500
4	0	0	Szymura, TH (2024-JAN) Spatial patterns of vascular plant species richness in poland: relations among species group richness and hot spot distribution . ACTA SOCIETATIS BOTANICORUM POLONIAE, V93, P13 DOI 10.5586/asbp/192897
4	7	0	Happonen, K (2021-JAN) Trait-based responses to land use and canopy dynamics modify long-term diversity changes in forest understories .

			GLOBAL ECOLOGY AND BIOGEOGRAPHY, V30, P13 DOI 10.1111/geb.13351
4	81	0	Eichenberg, D (2021-JAN) Widespread decline in central european plant diversity across six decades . GLOBAL CHANGE BIOLOGY, V27, P14 DOI 10.1111/geb.15447
4	0	0	Mitka, J (2025-JAN) Long-term dynamics of a fir-beech forest released from direct human pressure . FOREST ECOLOGY AND MANAGEMENT, V593, P13 DOI 10.1016/j.foreco.2025.122841
4	0	0	Sabatini, FM (2025-JAN) Using yearly-resolved time series to disentangle interannual variability, directional change, and pseudoturnover in plant community composition . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V36, P12 DOI 10.1111/jvs.70052
4	29	0	Vangansbeke, P (2021-JAN) Climplant: realized climatic niches of vascular plants in european forest understoreys . GLOBAL ECOLOGY AND BIOGEOGRAPHY DOI 10.1111/geb.13303
4	0	0	Goury, R (2025-JAN) Recent vegetation shifts in the french alps with winners outnumbering losers . JOURNAL OF ECOLOGY DOI 10.1111/1365-2745.70159
4	2	0	Triquet, C (2024-JAN) Undestroyed winter cover crop strips support wild bee abundance and diversity in intensive cropping systems . BIODIVERSITY AND CONSERVATION, V33, P26 DOI 10.1007/s10531-023-02741-5
4	14	0	Verrall, B (2021-JAN) Dynamics in plant diversity and composition on australian alpine summits over time . BIODIVERSITY AND CONSERVATION, V30, P26 DOI 10.1007/s10531-021-02171-1
4	23	0	Nielsen, TF (2021-JAN) Drier, darker and more fertile: 140 years of plant habitat change driven by land-use intensification . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V32, P16 DOI 10.1111/jvs.13066
4	4	0	Kirk, DA (2021-JAN) Changes in beta diversity and species functional traits differ between saplings and mature trees in an old-growth forest . ECOLOGY AND EVOLUTION, V11, P31 DOI 10.1002/ece3.6913
4	0	0	Holestova, A (2025-JAN) From past diversity to present decline: age heterogeneity and plant composition shifts in central european floodplain forests . FOREST ECOLOGY AND MANAGEMENT, V587, P10 DOI 10.1016/j.foreco.2025.122732
4	4	0	Siebert, F (2024-JAN) Past, present, and future of forbs in old-growth tropical and subtropical grasslands . ANNUAL REVIEW OF ECOLOGY EVOLUTION AND SYSTEMATICS, V55, P27 DOI 10.1146/annurev-ecolsys-102722-022331
4	11	0	Gaia, sperandii M (2022-JAN) Lotvs: a global collection of permanent vegetation plots . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V33, P11 DOI 10.1111/jvs.13115
4	0	0	Tichy, L (2025-JAN) Assessing the future of pulsatilla grandis in the czech republic: long-term population trends, site conditions and management . PRESLIA, V97, P14 DOI 10.23855/preslia.2025.115

3	11	0	Wronska-pilarek, D (2023-JAN) Temperate forest understory vegetation shifts after 40 years of conservation . SCIENCE OF THE TOTAL ENVIRONMENT, V895, P13 DOI 10.1016/j.scitotenv.2023.165164
3	15	0	Mendes, SB (2024-JAN) Evidence of a european seed dispersal crisis . SCIENCE DOI 10.1126/science.ado1464
3	1	0	Camila, pacheco-riano L (2024-JAN) Reliability of presence-only data for assessing plant community responses to climate warming . ECOGRAPHY, V2024, P11 DOI 10.1111/ecog.07213
3	4	0	Bakker, JDD (2023-JAN) Compositional variation in grassland plant communities . ECOSPHERE, V14, P17 DOI 10.1002/ecs2.4542
3	7	0	Pan, K (2024-JAN) Dutch landscapes have lost insect-pollinated plants over the past 87 years . JOURNAL OF APPLIED ECOLOGY, V61, P11 DOI 10.1111/1365-2664.14649
3	13	0	Kotrik, M (2023-JAN) Half a century of herb layer changes in quercus-dominated forests of the western carpathians . FOREST ECOLOGY AND MANAGEMENT, V544, P14 DOI 10.1016/j.foreco.2023.121151
3	4	0	Lelli, C (2023-JAN) Temporal beta diversity patterns reveal global change impacts in closed mountain grasslands . PLANT BIOSYSTEMS, V157, P10 DOI 10.1080/11263504.2022.2100498
3	4	0	Lodetti, S (2024-JAN) A new approach for assessing winning and losing plant species facing climate change on the gloria alpine summits . FLORA, V310, P12 DOI 10.1016/j.flora.2023.152441
3	84	0	Sabatini, FM (2021-JAN) Splotopen - an environmentally balanced, open-access, global dataset of vegetation plots . GLOBAL ECOLOGY AND BIOGEOGRAPHY, V30, P25 DOI 10.1111/geb.13346
3	5	0	Alessi, N (2021-JAN) Surface tradeoffs and elevational shifts at the largest italian glacier: a thirty-years time series of remotely-sensed images . REMOTE SENSING, V13, P14 DOI 10.3390/rs13010134
3	4	0	Carroll, T (2023-JAN) Correlated biodiversity change between plant and insect assemblages resurveyed after 80 years across a dynamic habitat mosaic . ECOLOGY AND EVOLUTION, V13, P13 DOI 10.1002/ece3.10168
3	8	0	Uribe, S (2021-JAN) Effect of land use history on biodiversity of pine plantations . FRONTIERS IN ECOLOGY AND EVOLUTION, V09, P15 DOI 10.3389/fevo.2021.609627
3	1	0	Heuel, KC (2024-JAN) Bee-diverse habitats positively affect seed set in wild plant species . FRONTIERS IN ECOLOGY AND EVOLUTION, V12, P13 DOI 10.3389/fevo.2024.1343885
3	1	0	Vantarova, KH (2024-JAN) Plant communities in changing environment . BIOLOGIA DOI 10.1007/s11756-024-01661-1
3	8	0	Mosoh, DA (2024-JAN) Preserving earth's flora in the 21st century: climate, biodiversity, and global change factors since the mid-1940s . FRONTIERS IN CONSERVATION SCIENCE DOI 10.3389/fcsc.2024.1383370
3	3	0	Sanczuk, P (2024-JAN) Embracing plant-plant interactions-rethinking predictions of species range shifts . JOURNAL OF ECOLOGY, V112, P17 DOI 10.1111/1365-2745.14415

3	7	0	Glaser, M (2024-JAN) Pronounced turnover of vascular plant species in central european arable fields over 90 years . AGRICULTURE ECOSYSTEMS & ENVIRONMENT, V361, P11 DOI 10.1016/j.agee.2023.108798
3	0	0	Fabsicova, M (2024-JAN) The importance of soil seed banks for biodiversity restoration in degraded grasslands . FOLIA GEOBOTANICA, V59, P21 DOI 10.1007/s12224-024-09452-x
3	0	0	Rijal, DP (2025-JAN) Millennia of metacommunity diversification and homogenization captured by sedimentary ancient dna . ECOLOGY LETTERS, V28, P12 DOI 10.1111/ele.70218
3	1	0	Bauer, M (2024-JAN) Beta diversity of restored river dike grasslands is strongly influenced by uncontrolled spatio-temporal variability . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V35, P12 DOI 10.1111/jvs.13293
3	17	0	Midolo, G (2024-JAN) Diversity and distribution of raunkiaer's life forms in european vegetation . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V35, P15 DOI 10.1111/jvs.13229
3	6	0	Diekmann, M (2023-JAN) Resurvey studies of terricolous bryophytes and lichens indicate a widespread nutrient enrichment in german forests . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V34, P12 DOI 10.1111/jvs.13201
3	1	0	Liu, Y (2024-JAN) Shufflenetv2unet: an improved neural network model for grassland sample coverage extraction . GRASS AND FORAGE SCIENCE, V79, P14 DOI 10.1111/gfs.12697
3	15	0	Hertzog, LR (2023-JAN) Associations between farmland birds and fallow area at large scales: consistently positive over three periods of the eu common agricultural policy but moderated by landscape complexity . JOURNAL OF APPLIED ECOLOGY, V60, P12 DOI 10.1111/1365-2664.14400
3	2	0	Janisova, M (2024-JAN) Mid-term changes of dry grasslands with conservation management in the hainburger berge mountains . BIOLOGIA, V79, P22 DOI 10.1007/s11756-023-01566-5
3	10	0	Collart, F (2023-JAN) Ecological and biological indicators of the accuracy of species distribution models: lessons from european bryophytes . ECOGEOGRAPHY, V2023, P13 DOI 10.1111/ecog.06721
3	23	0	Nicklas, L (2021-JAN) Climate change affects vegetation differently on siliceous and calcareous summits of the european alps . FRONTIERS IN ECOLOGY AND EVOLUTION DOI 10.3389/fevo.2021.642309
3	5	0	Kermavnar, J (2024-JAN) Habitat degradation facilitates the invasion of neophytes: a resurvey study based on permanent vegetation plots in oak forests in slovenia (europe) . PLANTS-BASEL, V13, P19 DOI 10.3390/plants13070962
3	5	0	Kissling, WD (2024-JAN) Towards consistently measuring and monitoring habitat condition with airborne laser scanning and unmanned aerial vehicles . ECOLOGICAL INDICATORS, V169, P19 DOI 10.1016/j.ecolind.2024.112970

3	4	0	Ejrmaes, DD (2024-JAN) Vegetation dynamics following three decades of trophic rewilding in the mesic grasslands of oostvaardersplassen . APPLIED VEGETATION SCIENCE, V27, P13 DOI 10.1111/avsc.12805
3	18	0	Mahecha, MD (2021-JAN) Crowd-sourced plant occurrence data provide a reliable description of macroecological gradients . ECOGRAPHY, V44, P12 DOI 10.1111/ecog.05492
3	3	0	Pironon, S (2022-JAN) Living at the limit in the pyrenees: peripheral and endemic plants are rare but underrepresented in protection lists . DIVERSITY AND DISTRIBUTIONS, V28, P13 DOI 10.1111/ddi.13487
3	2	0	McLellan, RC (2022-JAN) The living dead: demography of australian sandalwood in australia's western rangelands . AUSTRAL ECOLOGY, V47, P25 DOI 10.1111/aec.13243
3	0	0	Kermavnar, J (2025-JAN) Plant diversity decrease and directional species turnover induced by shifting overstory dominance in the oak-hornbeam forest reserve over 50 years . FLORA, V327, P12 DOI 10.1016/j.flora.2025.152742
3	3	0	Lososova, Z (2024-JAN) Flora of the city of brno, czech republic . PRESLIA, V96, P25 DOI 10.23855/preslia.2024.123
3	22	0	Hajek, M (2020-JAN) Towards the pan-european bioindication system: assessing and testing updated hydrological indicator values for vascular plants and bryophytes in mires . ECOLOGICAL INDICATORS, V116, P10 DOI 10.1016/j.ecolind.2020.106527
3	1	0	Fernandez, RD (2023-JAN) Preliminary analysis of native and non-native species of terrestrial national parks of argentina with emphasis on vascular plants . BOLETIN DE LA SOCIEDAD ARGENTINA DE BOTANICA, V58, P16 DOI 10.31055/1851.2372.v58.n1.38523
3	6	0	Olsoy, PJ (2024-JAN) Demography with drones: detecting growth and survival of shrubs with unoccupied aerial systems . RESTORATION ECOLOGY, V32, P12 DOI 10.1111/rec.14106
3	4	0	Becker-scarpitta, A (2022-JAN) Different temporal trends in vascular plant and bryophyte communities along elevational gradients over four decades . ECOLOGY AND EVOLUTION, V12, P12 DOI 10.1002/ece3.9102
3	8	0	Alessi, N (2023-JAN) Probabilistic and preferential sampling approaches offer integrated perspectives of italian forest diversity . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V34, P13 DOI 10.1111/jvs.13175
3	0	0	Nevermann, S (2025-JAN) Metabarcoding assessment of arthropod diversity on green roofs in the metropolitan city of hamburg . JOURNAL OF URBAN ECOLOGY, V11, P11 DOI 10.1093/jue/juaf003
3	5	0	Krapf, P (2023-JAN) Contribution of the public to the modelling of the distributions of species: occurrence and current and potential distribution of the ant manica rubida (hymenoptera: formicidae) . EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF ENTOMOLOGY, V120, P12 DOI 10.14411/eje.2023.017
3	1	0	Joelson, NZ (2025-JAN) A 50-year perspective on conservation challenges and legacy effects in temperate patagonian forests . BIOLOGICAL CONSERVATION, V306, P10 DOI 10.1016/j.biocon.2025.111124

3	3	0	Moret, P (2021-JAN) Resurvey of vascular plants and soil arthropods on the summit of mount corazon (andes of ecuador) after 140 years. NEOTROPICAL BIODIVERSITY DOI 10.1080/23766808.2021.1940056
3	16	0	Depauw, L (2022-JAN) The use of photos to investigate ecological change. JOURNAL OF ECOLOGY, V110, P17 DOI 10.1111/1365-2745.13876
3	7	0	Maliniemi, T (2021-JAN) Anthropogenic disturbance modifies long-term changes of boreal mountain vegetation under contemporary climate warming. APPLIED VEGETATION SCIENCE, V24, P13 DOI 10.1111/avsc.12587
3	2	0	Klinkovska, K (2024-JAN) Floristic classification of geranium sanguinei in south moravia (czech republic). BIOLOGIA, V79, P15 DOI 10.1007/s11756-023-01464-w
2	17	0	Hooftman, D (2021-JAN) Dispersal limitation, eutrophication and propagule pressure constrain the conservation value of grassland green infrastructure. BIOLOGICAL CONSERVATION, V258, P11 DOI 10.1016/j.biocon.2021.109152
2	31	0	Rathore, N (2023-JAN) Species phylogeny, ecology, and root traits as predictors of root exudate composition. NEW PHYTOLOGIST, V239, P13 DOI 10.1111/nph.19060
2	0	0	Neaca, A-Maria (2024-JAN) Intensive pasture management alters the composition and structure of plant-pollinator interactions in sibi, romania. PEERJ, V12, P27 DOI 10.7717/peerj.16900
2	4	0	Fanfarillo, E (2023-JAN) Chronicle of a death foretold: the vanishing of an emblematic cultural landscape results in the loss of its unique plant communities. GLOBAL ECOLOGY AND CONSERVATION, V47, P13 DOI 10.1016/j.gecco.2023.e02655
2	2	0	Morrison, LW (2023-JAN) Observer error in grassland vegetation surveys: effects on species diversity metrics and species-abundance relationships. JOURNAL OF PLANT ECOLOGY, V16, P13 DOI 10.1093/jpe/rtad002
2	0	0	Peppler-lisbach, C (2025-JAN) Synopsis of nardus grassland resurveys across germany: is eutrophication driven by a recovery of soil ph after acidification?. JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V36, P15 DOI 10.1111/jvs.70040
2	44	0	Boyd, RJ (2022-JAN) Robitt: a tool for assessing the risk-of-bias in studies of temporal trends in ecology. METHODS IN ECOLOGY AND EVOLUTION, V13, P11 DOI 10.1111/2041-210X.13857
2	0	0	Kovacevic, J (2025-JAN) Vascular plant nano-hotspots in the central balkan peninsula - a novel gis-based approach for identifying centres of species richness. GLOBAL ECOLOGY AND CONSERVATION, V60, P23 DOI 10.1016/j.gecco.2025.e03630
2	4	0	Kumpli, J (2021-JAN) Vegetation changes in urban grasslands over 25 years in the city of zurich, switzerland. TUEXENIA DOI 10.14471/2021.41.018
2	0	0	Yang, Z (2024-JAN) Multi-taxon species richness representation within national nature reserves is associated with spatial features, human disturbance and environmental factors in mountains region. GLOBAL

			ECOLOGY AND CONSERVATION, V54, P13 DOI 10.1016/j.gecco.2024.e03042
2	0	0	Siccardi, E (2025-JAN) Revisiting a small mediterranean island: how vegetation has changed in the last 15 years . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V36, P12 DOI 10.1111/jvs.70038
2	4	0	Maliniemi, T (2023-JAN) Temporal changes in boreal vegetation under 70 years of conservation . BIODIVERSITY AND CONSERVATION, V32, P19 DOI 10.1007/s10531-023-02723-7
2	11	0	Rybar, J (2023-JAN) Effects of tree canopy on herbaceous understorey throughout the developmental cycle of a temperate mountain primary forest . FOREST ECOLOGY AND MANAGEMENT, V546, P12 DOI 10.1016/j.foreco.2023.121353
2	2	0	Angst, S (2025-JAN) Un(der)explored links between plant diversity and particulate and mineral-associated organic matter in soil . NATURE COMMUNICATIONS DOI 10.1038/s41467-025-60712-6
2	2	0	Poniatowski, D (2024-JAN) Grassland nature reserves safeguard a high species richness and biomass of grasshoppers . JOURNAL OF APPLIED ECOLOGY, V61, P12 DOI 10.1111/1365-2664.14774
2	0	0	Marshall, Z (2025-JAN) A national vegetation plot database for great britain . VEGETATION CLASSIFICATION AND SURVEY DOI 10.3897/VCS.160378
2	5	0	Kalusova, V (2023-JAN) Neophyte invasions in european heathlands and scrub . BIOLOGICAL INVASIONS, V25, P27 DOI 10.1007/s10530-023-03005-7
2	2	0	Novak, J (2024-JAN) Relationship between extreme species richness and holocene persistence of forest-steppe grasslands in transylvania, romania . HOLOCENE, V34, P11 DOI 10.1177/09596836241266428
2	0	0	Miholcsa, Z (2025-JAN) In the footsteps of sheep herds: the neonative xeranthemum cylindraceum has no impact but indicates ruderalisation of overgrazed pastures in the new range . APPLIED VEGETATION SCIENCE, V28, P10 DOI 10.1111/avsc.70041
2	2	0	Daniela, F (2023-JAN) Rapid vegetation responses over the last seven decades revealed by an alpine ice core and land-cover patterns . LANDSCAPE ECOLOGY, V38, P15 DOI 10.1007/s10980-023-01661-7

Appendix 2 Table 9 Cluster 7

Coverage	GCS	LCS	Bibliography
13	138	0	Birks, HJB (2019-JAN) Contributions of quaternary botany to modern ecology and biogeography . PLANT ECOLOGY & DIVERSITY, V12, P197 DOI 10.1080/17550874.2019.1646831
11	96	0	Kopecky, M (2015-JAN) Vegetation resurvey is robust to plot location uncertainty . DIVERSITY AND DISTRIBUTIONS DOI 10.1111/ddi.12299
11	21	0	Czortek, P (2018-JAN) Effects of grazing abandonment and climate change on mountain summits flora: a case study in the tatra mts . PLANT ECOLOGY, V219, P16 DOI 10.1007/s11258-018-0794-6
11	68	0	Verheyen, K (2018-JAN) Observer and relocation errors matter in resurveys of historical vegetation plots . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V29, P12 DOI 10.1111/jvs.12673
11	172	0	Kapfer, J (2017-JAN) Resurveying historical vegetation data-opportunities and challenges . APPLIED VEGETATION SCIENCE DOI 10.1111/avsc.12269
11	31	0	Prach, J (2018-JAN) Landscape-scale vegetation homogenization in central european sub-montane forests over the past 50years . APPLIED VEGETATION SCIENCE, V21, P12 DOI 10.1111/avsc.12372
10	75	0	Vanneste, T (2017-JAN) Impact of climate change on alpine vegetation of mountain summits in norway . ECOLOGICAL RESEARCH, V32, P15 DOI 10.1007/s11284-017-1472-1
10	10	0	Dittmann, T (2018-JAN) The forests of magdeburgerforth (flaming, ne germany) - a resurvey study after six decades . TUEXENIA DOI 10.14471/2018.38.009
10	93	0	Verheyen, K (2017-JAN) Combining biodiversity resurveys across regions to advance global change research . BIOSCIENCE, V67, P11 DOI 10.1093/biosci/biw150
9	26	0	Becker-scarpitta, A (2019-JAN) Four decades of plant community change along a continental gradient of warming . GLOBAL CHANGE BIOLOGY, V25, P13 DOI 10.1111/gcb.14568
9	16	0	Lelli, C (2021-JAN) Long-term changes in italian mountain forests detected by resurvey of historical vegetation data . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V32, P11 DOI 10.1111/jvs.12939
8	25	0	Czortek, P (2018-JAN) Plant species composition shifts in the tatra mts as a response to environmental change: a resurvey study after 90 years . FOLIA GEOBOTANICA, V53, P16 DOI 10.1007/s12224-018-9312-9
8	18	0	Hedl, R (2020-JAN) Understanding the dynamics of forest understorey: combination of monitoring and legacy data reveals patterns across temporal scales . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V31, P11 DOI 10.1111/jvs.12882
8	4	0	Prausova, R (2020-JAN) Nine decades of major compositional changes in a central european beech forest protected area . PLANT ECOLOGY, V221, P12 DOI 10.1007/s11258-020-01057-6
7	35	0	Frate, L (2018-JAN) Climate and land use change impacts on mediterranean high-mountain vegetation in the apennines since the 1950s .

			PLANT ECOLOGY & DIVERSITY, V11, P12 DOI 10.1080/17550874.2018.1473521
7	76	0	Depauw, L (2020-JAN) Light availability and land-use history drive biodiversity and functional changes in forest herb layer communities. JOURNAL OF ECOLOGY, V108, P15 DOI 10.1111/1365-2745.13339
7	140	0	Muellerova, J (2015-JAN) Coppice abandonment and its implications for species diversity in forest vegetation. FOREST ECOLOGY AND MANAGEMENT, V343, P13 DOI 10.1016/j.foreco.2015.02.003
7	7	0	Maliniemi, T (2019-JAN) Site fertility drives temporal turnover of vegetation at high latitudes. ECOLOGY AND EVOLUTION DOI 10.1002/ece3.5778
7	51	0	Kulonen, A (2018-JAN) Enough space in a warmer world? microhabitat diversity and small-scale distribution of alpine plants on mountain summits. DIVERSITY AND DISTRIBUTIONS, V24, P10 DOI 10.1111/ddi.12673
7	14	0	Czortek, P (2018-JAN) Cessation of livestock grazing and windthrow drive a shift in plant species composition in the western tatra mts. TUEXENIA DOI 10.14471/2018.38.008
6	3	0	Standovar, T (2017-JAN) Temporal changes in vegetation of a virgin beech woodland remnant: stand-scale stability with intensive fine-scale dynamics governed by stand dynamic events. NATURE CONSERVATION-BULGARIA DOI 10.3897/natureconservation.17.12251
6	14	0	De, lombærde E (2018-JAN) Responses of competitive understorey species to spatial environmental gradients inaccurately explain temporal changes. BASIC AND APPLIED ECOLOGY, V30, P13 DOI 10.1016/j.baae.2018.05.013
6	28	0	Czortek, P (2018-JAN) Climate change, tourism and historical grazing influence the distribution of carex lachenalii schkuhr - a rare arctic-alpine species in the tatra mts. SCIENCE OF THE TOTAL ENVIRONMENT, V618, P10 DOI 10.1016/j.scitotenv.2017.10.001
6	25	0	Vojik, M (2018-JAN) Fear of the dark: decline in plant diversity and invasion of alien species due to increased tree canopy density and eutrophication in lowland woodlands. PLANT ECOLOGY, V219, P10 DOI 10.1007/s11258-018-0831-5
6	27	0	Rixen, C (2017-JAN) Non-equilibrium in alpine plant assemblages: shifts in europe's summit floras. HIGH MOUNTAIN CONSERVATION IN A CHANGING WORLD, V62, P19 DOI 10.1007/978-3-319-55982-7_12
6	24	0	Closset-kopp, D (2019-JAN) Do drivers of forestry vehicles also drive herb layer changes (1970-2015) in a temperate forest with contrasting habitat and management conditions?. JOURNAL OF ECOLOGY, V107, P18 DOI 10.1111/1365-2745.13118
6	649	0	Steinbauer, MJ (2018-JAN) Accelerated increase in plant species richness on mountain summits is linked to warming. NATURE, V556, P16 DOI 10.1038/s41586-018-0005-6
6	25	0	Pakeman, RJ (2016-JAN) Long-term impacts of nitrogen deposition on coastal plant communities. ENVIRONMENTAL POLLUTION, V212, P11 DOI 10.1016/j.envpol.2016.01.084

6	26	0	Malis, F (2021-JAN) Historical charcoal burning and coppicing suppressed beech and increased forest vegetation heterogeneity . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V32, P14 DOI 10.1111/jvs.12923
6	122	0	Savage, J (2015-JAN) Elevational shifts, biotic homogenization and time lags in vegetation change during 40 years of climate warming . ECOGRAPHY, V38, P10 DOI 10.1111/ecog.01131
6	13	0	Calabrese, V (2018-JAN) Long-term changes in the composition, ecology, and structure of pinus mugo scrubs in the apennines (italy) . DIVERSITY-BASEL, V10, P15 DOI 10.3390/d10030070
6	5	0	Dierschke, H (2020-JAN) 37 years of permanent plot research within a calcareous beech forest a time series 1980-2001-2016 . TUEXENIA DOI 10.14471/2020.40.003
5	27	0	Foerster, A (2017-JAN) Long-term change in understorey plant communities of conventionally managed temperate deciduous forests: effects of nitrogen deposition and forest management . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V28, P15 DOI 10.1111/jvs.12537
5	2	0	Vandekerkhove, K (2021-JAN) Enjoying tranquility - development of ground vegetation after cessation of management in forests on loamy soils in flanders (belgium) . APPLIED VEGETATION SCIENCE, V24, P15 DOI 10.1111/avsc.12593
5	98	0	Staude, IR (2020-JAN) Replacements of small- by large-ranged species scale up to diversity loss in europe's temperate forest biome . NATURE ECOLOGY & EVOLUTION DOI 10.1038/s41559-020-1176-8
5	45	0	Scarpitta, AB (2017-JAN) Long-term community change: bryophytes are more responsive than vascular plants to nitrogen deposition and warming . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V28, P10 DOI 10.1111/jvs.12579
5	6	0	Woerz, A (2015-JAN) The temporal dynamics of a regional flora-the effects of global and local impacts . FLORA, V217, P10 DOI 10.1016/j.flora.2015.09.013
5	6	0	Beck, JJ (2018-JAN) Phantom species: adjusting estimates of colonization and extinction for pseudo-turnover . OIKOS, V127, P14 DOI 10.1111/oik.05114
5	20	0	Van, den berge S (2019-JAN) Contrasting vegetation change (1974-2015) in hedgerows and forests in an intensively used agricultural landscape . APPLIED VEGETATION SCIENCE, V22, P13 DOI 10.1111/avsc.12424
4	11	0	Alfonsi, E (2017-JAN) Addressing species turnover and community changes in vegetation resurvey studies . APPLIED VEGETATION SCIENCE, V20, P11 DOI 10.1111/avsc.12258
4	44	0	Helm, A (2015-JAN) Characteristic and derived diversity: implementing the species pool concept to quantify conservation condition of habitats . DIVERSITY AND DISTRIBUTIONS, V21, P11 DOI 10.1111/ddi.12285
4	23	0	Ewald, J (2017-JAN) Giving meaning to ellenberg nutrient values: national forest soil inventory yields frequency-based scaling . APPLIED VEGETATION SCIENCE DOI 10.1111/avsc.12278

4	19	0	Kunes, P (2019-JAN) Changing disturbance-diversity relationships in temperate ecosystems over the past 12000 years . JOURNAL OF ECOLOGY, V107, P11 DOI 10.1111/1365-2745.13136
4	5	0	Barker, BS (2018-JAN) An introduction and practical guide to use of the soil-vegetation inventory method (svim) data . RANGELAND ECOLOGY & MANAGEMENT, V71, P10 DOI 10.1016/j.rama.2018.06.003
4	13	0	Czortek, P (2020-JAN) River regulation drives shifts in urban riparian vegetation over three decades . URBAN FORESTRY & URBAN GREENING, V47, P11 DOI 10.1016/j.ufug.2019.126524
4	3	0	Primack, RB (2022-JAN) Was henry david thoreau a good naturalist? an approach for assessing data from historical natural history records . BIOSCIENCE, V72, P10 DOI 10.1093/biosci/biac063
4	31	0	Hedwall, P (2017-JAN) Peatland plant communities under global change: negative feedback loops counteract shifts in species composition . ECOLOGY, V98, P12 DOI 10.1002/ecy.1627
4	9	0	Boch, S (2022-JAN) Observer-driven pseudoturnover in vegetation monitoring is context-dependent but does not affect ecological inference . APPLIED VEGETATION SCIENCE, V25, P11 DOI 10.1111/avsc.12669
4	31	0	Meyer, S (2015-JAN) Detecting long-term losses at the plant community level - arable fields in germany revisited . APPLIED VEGETATION SCIENCE, V18, P11 DOI 10.1111/avsc.12168
4	2	0	Zaniewski, PT (2019-JAN) Application of cluster analysis to distinguish the tendencies of vegetation changes on the example of the dynamics of communities affected by surface fire in the peucedano-pinetum community in the kampinoski national park . SYLWAN, V163, P12 DOI 10.26202/sylwan.2019063
4	1	0	Bhatta, KP (2019-JAN) Weighted average regression and environmental calibration as a tool for quantifying climate-driven changes in vegetation . JOURNAL OF PLANT ECOLOGY, V12, P14 DOI 10.1093/jpe/rty039
4	24	0	Vild, O (2017-JAN) The paradox of long-term ungulate impact: increase of plant species richness in a temperate forest . APPLIED VEGETATION SCIENCE, V20, P11 DOI 10.1111/avsc.12289
4	82	0	Diekmann, M (2019-JAN) Patterns of long-term vegetation change vary between different types of semi-natural grasslands in western and central europe . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V30, P16 DOI 10.1111/jvs.12727
4	34	0	Koch, M (2015-JAN) Four decades of vegetation development in a percolation mire complex following intensive drainage and abandonment . PLANT ECOLOGY & DIVERSITY DOI 10.1080/17550874.2013.862752
4	18	0	Cholewinska, O (2020-JAN) Homogenization of temperate mixed deciduous forests in bialowie(z) over dota forest: similar communities are becoming more similar . FORESTS, V11, P14 DOI 10.3390/f11050545
4	14	0	Seidling, W (2020-JAN) Comparing observer performance in vegetation records by efficiency graphs derived from rarefaction curves . ECOLOGICAL INDICATORS, V109, P11 DOI 10.1016/j.ecolind.2019.105790

3	5	0	Tingstad, L (2020-JAN) Using red list species in designating protection status to forest areas: a case study on the problem of spatio-temporal dynamics . BIODIVERSITY AND CONSERVATION, V29, P15 DOI 10.1007/s10531-020-02031-4
3	15	0	Lanta, V (2020-JAN) Restoring diversity of thermophilous oak forests: connectivity and proximity to existing habitats matter . BIODIVERSITY AND CONSERVATION, V29, P17 DOI 10.1007/s10531-020-02030-5
3	5	0	Silc, U (2015-JAN) Biotic homogenization and differentiation in weed vegetation over the last 70 years . OPEN LIFE SCIENCES DOI 10.1515/biol-2015-0056
3	26	0	Boch, S (2019-JAN) Mean indicator values suggest decreasing habitat quality in swiss dry grasslands and are robust to relocation error . TUEXENIA DOI 10.14471/2019.39.010
3	33	0	Mitchell, RJ (2017-JAN) Forty years of change in scottish grassland vegetation: increased richness, decreased diversity and increased dominance . BIOLOGICAL CONSERVATION, V212, P10 DOI 10.1016/j.biocon.2017.06.027
3	26	0	Peppler-lisbach, C (2020-JAN) Long-term vegetation changes innardusgrasslands indicate eutrophication, recovery from acidification, and management change as the main drivers . APPLIED VEGETATION SCIENCE, V23, P14 DOI 10.1111/avsc.12513
3	11	0	Baumann, M (2021-JAN) Temporal changes in the ground vegetation in spruce forests in the erzgebirge (ore mountains) - bryophytes are better indicators of the impact of liming and of sulphur and nitrogen deposition than the herb layer . APPLIED VEGETATION SCIENCE, V24, P15 DOI 10.1111/avsc.12598
3	39	0	van, dobbe HF (2017-JAN) The contribution of nitrogen deposition to the eutrophication signal in understory plant communities of european forests . ECOLOGY AND EVOLUTION DOI 10.1002/ece3.2485
3	10	0	Caron, MM (2021-JAN) Thermal differences between juveniles and adults increased over time in european forest trees . JOURNAL OF ECOLOGY, V109, P14 DOI 10.1111/1365-2745.13773
3	21	0	Sperandii, MG (2019-JAN) Back into the past: resurveying random plots to track community changes in italian coastal dunes . ECOLOGICAL INDICATORS DOI 10.1016/j.ecolind.2018.09.039
3	2	0	Smith, RJ (2019-JAN) Combining potentially incompatible community datasets when harmonizing forest inventories in subarctic alaska, usa . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V30, P12 DOI 10.1111/jvs.12694
3	25	0	Kolk, J (2017-JAN) Paying the colonization credit: converging plant species richness in ancient and post-agricultural forests in ne germany over five decades . BIODIVERSITY AND CONSERVATION, V26, P21 DOI 10.1007/s10531-016-1271-y
3	18	0	Granger, V (2015-JAN) Mapping diversity indices: not a trivial issue . METHODS IN ECOLOGY AND EVOLUTION DOI 10.1111/2041-210X.12357

3	29	0	Wang, L (2019-JAN) Potential distribution shifts of plant species under climate change in changbai mountains, china . FORESTS, V10, P15 DOI 10.3390/f10060498
3	28	0	Pasquet, S (2015-JAN) Three decades of vegetation changes in peatlands isolated in an agricultural landscape . APPLIED VEGETATION SCIENCE, V18, P10 DOI 10.1111/avsc.12142
3	17	0	Lubek, A (2018-JAN) Changes in the epiphytic lichen biota of bialowieza primeval forest are not explained by climate warming . SCIENCE OF THE TOTAL ENVIRONMENT, V643, P11 DOI 10.1016/j.scitotenv.2018.06.222
3	17	0	Krause, B (2015-JAN) Historical and recent fragmentation of temperate floodplain grasslands: do patch size and distance affect the richness of characteristic wet meadow plant species? . FOLIA GEOBOTANICA, V50, P14 DOI 10.1007/s12224-015-9220-1
3	59	0	Hedl, R (2017-JAN) Resurvey of historical vegetation plots: a tool for understanding long-term dynamics of plant communities . APPLIED VEGETATION SCIENCE DOI 10.1111/avsc.12307
3	42	0	Jimenez-alfaro, B (2014-JAN) Biogeographic deconstruction of alpine plant communities along altitudinal and topographic gradients . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V25, P12 DOI 10.1111/jvs.12060
3	3	0	Pielech, R (2018-JAN) Changes in species composition in alder swamp forest following forest dieback . FORESTS DOI 10.3390/f9060316
3	14	0	Roth, M (2022-JAN) Vegetation changes in the understory of nitrogen-sensitive temperate forests over the past 70 years . FOREST ECOLOGY AND MANAGEMENT, V503, P10 DOI 10.1016/j.foreco.2021.119754
3	24	0	Durak, T (2015-JAN) Biotic homogenisation and differentiation along a habitat gradient resulting from the ageing of managed beech stands . FOREST ECOLOGY AND MANAGEMENT, V351, P10 DOI 10.1016/j.foreco.2015.05.001
3	8	0	Lelli, C (2018-JAN) Are available vegetation data suitable for assessing plant diversity? a study case in the foreste casentinesi national park (italy) . RENDICONTI LINCEI-SCIENZE FISICHE E NATURALI DOI 10.1007/s12210-018-0681-z
3	20	0	Kapfer, J (2017-JAN) Large climate change, large effect? vegetation changes over the past century in the european high arctic . APPLIED VEGETATION SCIENCE, V20, P11 DOI 10.1111/avsc.12280
3	21	0	Barker, BS (2019-JAN) Pre-fire vegetation drives post-fire outcomes in sagebrush ecosystems: evidence from field and remote sensing data . ECOSPHERE, V10, P29 DOI 10.1002/ecs2.2929
3	11	0	Yannelli, FA (2022-JAN) Fifteen emerging challenges and opportunities for vegetation science: a horizon scan by early career researchers . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V33, P18 DOI 10.1111/jvs.13119
3	72	0	Evangelista, A (2016-JAN) Changes in composition, ecology and structure of high-mountain vegetation: a re-visitation study over 42 years . AOB PLANTS DOI 10.1093/aobpla/plw004

3	440	0	Blowes, SA (2019-JAN) The geography of biodiversity change in marine and terrestrial assemblages . SCIENCE, V366, P86 DOI 10.1126/science.aaw1620
3	8	0	Bugno-pogoda, A (2021-JAN) Impact of forest management on the temporal dynamics of herbaceous plant diversity in the carpathian beech forests over 40 years . BIOLOGY-BASEL, V10, P20 DOI 10.3390/biology10050406
3	31	0	Navratilova, J (2017-JAN) Convergence and impoverishment of fen communities in a eutrophicated agricultural landscape of the czech republic . APPLIED VEGETATION SCIENCE, V20, P11 DOI 10.1111/avsc.12298
3	4	0	Schei, FH (2015-JAN) Stability of alpine vegetation over 50 years in central norway . FOLIA GEOBOTANICA, V50, P10 DOI 10.1007/s12224-015-9209-9
3	8	0	Meier, T (2022-JAN) Are recent climate change and airborne nitrogen deposition responsible for vegetation changes in a central german dry grassland between 1995 and 2019? . TUEXENIA, V42, P39 DOI 10.14471/2022.42.011
3	1	0	Stix, S (2018-JAN) Increase of species diversity in fens in the central alps . TUEXENIA DOI 10.14471/2017.38.002
2	21	0	Mazalla, L (2022-JAN) Regression to the mean in vegetation science . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE DOI 10.1111/jvs.13117
2	30	0	Ridding, LE (2020-JAN) Long-term change in calcareous grassland vegetation and drivers over three time periods between 1970 and 2016 . PLANT ECOLOGY, V221, P18 DOI 10.1007/s11258-020-01016-1
2	49	0	Hedwall, P (2019-JAN) Half a century of multiple anthropogenic stressors has altered northern forest understory plant communities . ECOLOGICAL APPLICATIONS, V29, P11 DOI 10.1002/eap.1874
2	8	0	Durak, T (2015-JAN) The impact of changes in species richness and species replacement on patterns of taxonomic homogenization in the carpathian forest ecosystems . FORESTS DOI 10.3390/f6124376
2	11	0	Morrison, LW (2016-JAN) Observer error in sampling a rare plant population . PLANT ECOLOGY & DIVERSITY DOI 10.1080/17550874.2016.1220989
2	11	0	Rawat, B (2021-JAN) Long-term forest vegetation dynamics in nanda devi biosphere reserve, indian west himalaya: evidence from repeat studies on compositional patterns . ENVIRONMENTAL MONITORING AND ASSESSMENT, V193, P17 DOI 10.1007/s10661-021-09227-3
2	59	0	Staude, IR (2022-JAN) Directional turnover towards larger-ranged plants over time and across habitats . ECOLOGY LETTERS, V25, P17 DOI 10.1111/ele.13937
2	7	0	Rowe, EC (2015-JAN) Field survey based models for exploring nitrogen and acidity effects on plant species diversity and assessing long-term critical loads . CRITICAL LOADS AND DYNAMIC RISK ASSESSMENTS: NITROGEN, ACIDITY AND METALS IN TERRESTRIAL AND AQUATIC ECOSYSTEMS, V25, P30 DOI 10.1007/978-94-017-9508-1_11

2	6	0	Reczynska, K (2020-JAN) Does protection really matter? a case study from central european oak forests. DIVERSITY-BASEL, V12, P11 DOI 10.3390/d12010006
2	10	0	Pakeman, RJ (2017-JAN) Linking functional traits and species preferences to species' abundance and occupancy trends through time to identify habitat changes in coastal. PERSPECTIVES IN PLANT ECOLOGY EVOLUTION AND SYSTEMATICS, V27, P10 DOI 10.1016/j.ppees.2017.06.002
2	51	0	Scherrer, D (2017-JAN) Assessing and predicting shifts in mountain forest composition across 25years of climate change. DIVERSITY AND DISTRIBUTIONS, V23, P12 DOI 10.1111/ddi.12548
2	26	0	Kutnar, L (2019-JAN) Effects of disturbance on understory vegetation across slovenian forest ecosystems. FORESTS, V10, P16 DOI 10.3390/f10111048
2	16	0	Lisner, A (2020-JAN) Everyone makes mistakes: sampling errors in vegetation analysis - the effect of different sampling methods, abundance estimates, experimental manipulations, and data transformation. ACTA OECOLOGICA-INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ECOLOGY, V109, P10 DOI 10.1016/j.actao.2020.103667
2	34	0	Diez, J (2020-JAN) Altitudinal upwards shifts in fungal fruiting in the alps. PROCEEDINGS OF THE ROYAL SOCIETY B-BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES DOI 10.1098/rspb.2019.2348
2	4	0	Kirk, DA (2021-JAN) Changes in beta diversity and species functional traits differ between saplings and mature trees in an old-growth forest. ECOLOGY AND EVOLUTION, V11, P31 DOI 10.1002/ece3.6913
2	16	0	Gauzere, P (2021-JAN) Mismatches between birds' spatial and temporal dynamics reflect their delayed response to global changes. OIKOS, V130, P13 DOI 10.1111/oik.08289
2	4	0	Kearney, MR (2021-JAN) Grasshopper country before and after: a resurvey of ken key's collecting expeditions in new south wales, australia, 70 years on. AUSTRAL ENTOMOLOGY, V60, P14 DOI 10.1111/aen.12515

Appendix 2 Table 10 Cluster 8

Coverage	GCS	LCS	Bibliography
23	234	0	Hajek, M (2006-JAN) Habitat diversity of central european fens in relation to environmental gradients and an effort to standardise fen terminology in ecological studies . PERSPECTIVES IN PLANT ECOLOGY EVOLUTION AND SYSTEMATICS DOI 10.1016/j.ppees.2006.08.002
20	86	0	Opravilova, V (2006-JAN) The variation of testacean assemblages (rhizopoda) along the complete base-richness gradient in fens:: a case study from the western carpathians. ACTA PROTOZOOLOGICA, V45, P14
16	87	0	Hajkova, P (2006-JAN) Diversity of wetland vegetation in the bulgarian high mountains, main gradients and context-dependence of the ph role . PLANT ECOLOGY, V184, P20 DOI 10.1007/s11258-005-9056-5
12	105	0	Schuster, B (2003-JAN) Changes in species density along the soil ph gradient - evidence from german plant communities . FOLIA GEOBOTANICA, V38, P13 DOI 10.1007/BF02803245
9	42	0	Hajek, M (2007-JAN) Testing the species pool hypothesis for mire vegetation:: exploring the influence of ph specialists and habitat history . OIKOS, V116, P12 DOI 10.1111/j.2007.0030-1299.15637.x
9	17	0	Feldmeyer-christe, E (2007-JAN) Improving predictive mapping in swiss mire ecosystems through re-calibration of indicator values . APPLIED VEGETATION SCIENCE, V10, P10 DOI 10.1658/1402-2001(2007)10[183:IPMISM]2.0.CO;2
8	12	0	Dite, D (2006-JAN) Habitat variability and classification of utricularia communities:: comparison of peat depressions in slovakia and the trebon basin. PRESLIA, V78, P13
8	150	0	Chytry, M (2003-JAN) Local and regional patterns of species richness in central european vegetation types along the ph/calcium gradient . FOLIA GEOBOTANICA, V38, P14 DOI 10.1007/BF02803250
8	13	0	Ecker, K (2008-JAN) Predictive mapping of floristic site conditions across mire habitats: evaluating data requirements . COMMUNITY ECOLOGY DOI 10.1556/ComEc.9.2008.2.2
8	23	0	Hajek, M (2008-JAN) The balkan wet grassland vegetation:: a prerequisite to better understanding of european habitat diversity . PLANT ECOLOGY, V195, P17 DOI 10.1007/s11258-007-9315-8
7	66	0	Schmidtlein, S (2005-JAN) Imaging spectroscopy as a tool for mapping ellenberg indicator values . JOURNAL OF APPLIED ECOLOGY DOI 10.1111/j.1365-2664.2005.01064.x
7	57	0	Hajkova, P (2008-JAN) Shifts in the ecological behaviour of plant species between two distant regions:: evidence from the base richness gradient in mires . JOURNAL OF BIOGEOGRAPHY, V35, P13 DOI 10.1111/j.1365-2699.2007.01793.x
7	24	0	Huelber, K (2008-JAN) Long-term impacts of nitrogen and sulphur deposition on forest floor vegetation in the northern limestone alps, austria . APPLIED VEGETATION SCIENCE, V11, P10 DOI 10.3170/2008-7-18489

7	61	0	Bartha, S (2008-JAN) Changes of vascular plant diversity along a chronosequence of beech coppice stands, central apennines, italy . PLANT BIOSYSTEMS, V142, P12 DOI 10.1080/11263500802410926
6	39	0	Smart, SM (2004-JAN) Bias in ellenberg indicator values - problems with detection of the effect of vegetation type . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE DOI 10.1111/j.1654-1103.2004.tb02327.x
6	9	0	Hrivnak, R (2008-JAN) Mire vegetation of the muranska planina mts -: formalised classification, ecology, main environmental gradient and influence of geographical position . BIOLOGIA, V63, P10 DOI 10.2478/s11756-008-0059-2
6	86	0	Wamelink, GWW (2005-JAN) Plant species as predictors of soil ph: replacing expert judgement with measurements . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V16, P10 DOI 10.1658/1100-9233(2005)016[0461:PSAPOS]2.0.CO;2
6	672	0	Diekmann, M (2003-JAN) Species indicator values as an important tool in applied plant ecology - a review . BASIC AND APPLIED ECOLOGY DOI 10.1078/1439-1791-00185
6	7	0	Bergfur, J (2004-JAN) Phenological changes within a growth season in two semi-natural pastures in southern sweden. ANNALES BOTANICI FENNICI, V41, P11
5	8	0	Wamelink, GWW (2004-JAN) Measurement errors and regression to the mean cannot explain bias in average ellenberg indicator values . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE DOI 10.1111/j.1654-1103.2004.tb02328.x
5	46	0	Wagner, M (2007-JAN) Prediction of herbage yield in grassland: how well do ellenberg n-values perform? . APPLIED VEGETATION SCIENCE, V10, P10 DOI 10.1658/1402-2001(2007)10[15:POHYIG]2.0.CO;2
5	17	0	Chiarucci, A (2008-JAN) Quantifying species richness at multiple spatial scales in a natura 2000 network . COMMUNITY ECOLOGY DOI 10.1556/ComEc.9.2008.2.7
5	25	0	Dite, D (2007-JAN) Formal definitions of slovakian mire plant associations and their application in regional research . BIOLOGIA DOI 10.2478/s11756-007-0082-8
5	41	0	Lajer, K (2007-JAN) Statistical tests as inappropriate tools for data analysis performed on non-random samples of plant communities . FOLIA GEOBOTANICA DOI 10.1007/BF02893878
4	28	0	Ewald, J (2008-JAN) Plant species richness in mountain forests of the bavarian alps . PLANT BIOSYSTEMS, V142, P10 DOI 10.1080/11263500802410942
4	38	0	Symstad, AJ (2008-JAN) Precision, repeatability, and efficiency of two canopy-cover estimate methods in northern great plains vegetation . RANGELAND ECOLOGY & MANAGEMENT, V61, P11 DOI 10.2111/08-010.1
4	25	0	Seidling, W (2005-JAN) Ground floor vegetation assessment within the intensive (level ii) monitoring of forest ecosystems in germany: chances and challenges . EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF FOREST RESEARCH, V124, P12 DOI 10.1007/s10342-005-0087-1

4	40	0	Zelnik, I (2008-JAN) Distribution of plant communities, ecological strategy types and diversity along a moisture gradient . COMMUNITY ECOLOGY DOI 10.1556/ComEc.9.2008.1.1
3	119	0	Sadlo, J (2007-JAN) Regional species pools of vascular plants in habitats of the czech republic. PRESLIA, V79, P19
3	30	0	Huebner, CD (2007-JAN) Detection and monitoring of invasive exotic plants: a comparison of four sampling methods . NORTHEASTERN NATURALIST, V14, P24 DOI 10.1656/1092-6194(2007)14[183:DAMOIE]2.0.CO;2
3	49	0	Samonil, P (2007-JAN) Trends and cyclical changes in natural fir-beech forests at the north-western edge of the carpathians . FOLIA GEOBOTANICA, V42, P25 DOI 10.1007/BF02861699
3	30	0	Samonil, P (2008-JAN) Long-term vegetation dynamics in the sumava mts. natural spruce-fir-beech forests . PLANT ECOLOGY, V196, P18 DOI 10.1007/s11258-007-9345-2
3	133	0	Vittoz, P (2007-JAN) How reliable is the monitoring of permanent vegetation plots? a test with multiple observers . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V18, P10 DOI 10.1111/j.1654-1103.2007.tb02553.x

Appendix 2 Table 11 Cluster 9

Coverage	GCS	LCS	Bibliography
29	310	0	Pysek, P (2012-JAN) Catalogue of alien plants of the czech republic (2nd edition): checklist update, taxonomic diversity and invasion patterns. PRESLIA, V84, P101
24	134	0	Pysek, P (2012-JAN) Plant invasions in the czech republic: current state, introduction dynamics, invasive species and invaded habitats. PRESLIA, V84, P55
21	0	0	Machar, I (2012-JAN) Ochrana prirody a krajiny v ceske republice, vols i and ii. OCHRANA PRIRODY A KRAJINY V CESKE REPUBLICE, VOLS I AND II
11	237	0	Danihelka, J (2012-JAN) Checklist of vascular plants of the czech republic. PRESLIA, V84, P165
8	124	0	Chytry, M (2012-JAN) Vegetation of the czech republic: diversity, ecology, history and dynamics. PRESLIA, V84, P78
8	203	0	Grulich, V (2012-JAN) Red list of vascular plants of the czech republic: 3rd edition. PRESLIA, V84, P15
6	97	0	Pysek, P (2013-JAN) Hitting the right target: taxonomic challenges for, and of, plant invasions . AOB PLANTS DOI 10.1093/aobpla/plt042
6	11	0	Mikulaskova, E (2012-JAN) Invasion of central-european habitats by the moss campylopus introflexus. PRESLIA, V84, P24
6	33	0	Campos, JA (2013-JAN) Assessing the level of plant invasion: a multi-scale approach based on vegetation plots . PLANT BIOSYSTEMS, V147, P15 DOI 10.1080/11263504.2013.861538
5	36	0	Pysek, P (2014-JAN) Habitat invasion research: where vegetation science and invasion ecology meet . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE DOI 10.1111/jvs.12146
5	12	0	Krahulec, F (2012-JAN) History of the studies on the flora and vegetation in the czech republic. PRESLIA, V84, P30
4	44	0	Tomasetto, F (2013-JAN) Environmental gradients shift the direction of the relationship between native and alien plant species richness . DIVERSITY AND DISTRIBUTIONS, V19, P11 DOI 10.1111/j.1472-4642.2012.00939.x
3	23	0	Barwell, LJ (2014-JAN) Can coarse-grain patterns in insect atlas data predict local occupancy? . DIVERSITY AND DISTRIBUTIONS, V20, P13 DOI 10.1111/ddi.12203
3	53	0	Kacki, Z (2012-JAN) The polish vegetation database: structure, resources and development . ACTA SOCIETATIS BOTANICORUM POLONIAE DOI 10.5586/asbp.2012.014
3	48	0	Dostal, P (2013-JAN) Central european plant species from more productive habitats are more invasive at a global scale . GLOBAL ECOLOGY AND BIOGEOGRAPHY DOI 10.1111/j.1466-8238.2011.00754.x
3	59	0	Wilson, JRU (2014-JAN) A standardized set of metrics to assess and monitor tree invasions . BIOLOGICAL INVASIONS, V16, P17 DOI 10.1007/s10530-013-0605-x

3	10	0	Kalwij, JM (2014-JAN) Spatially-explicit estimation of geographical representation in large-scale species distribution datasets . PLOS ONE DOI 10.1371/journal.pone.0085306
3	12	0	Velebil, J (2012-JAN) Sorbus omissa, a new endemic hybridogenous species from the lower vltava river valley. PRESLIA, V84, P16
3	2	0	Pysek, P (2014-JAN) Preslia: hundred years of exploring central-european flora and vegetation. PRESLIA, V86, P11
3	40	0	Cuda, J (2014-JAN) Habitat requirements, short-term population dynamics and coexistence of native and invasive impatiens species: a field study . BIOLOGICAL INVASIONS, V16, P14 DOI 10.1007/s10530-013-0512-1

Appendix 2 Table 12 Cluster 10

Coverage	GCS	LCS	Bibliography
11	170	0	Birks, HJB (2016-JAN) Does pollen-assemblage richness reflect floristic richness? a review of recent developments and future challenges . REVIEW OF PALAEOBOTANY AND PALYNOLOGY, V228, P25 DOI 10.1016/j.revpalbo.2015.12.011
8	22	0	Roth, T (2018-JAN) Functional ecology and imperfect detection of species . METHODS IN ECOLOGY AND EVOLUTION DOI 10.1111/2041-210X.12950
5	27	0	Molina-venegas, R (2018-JAN) Assessing among-lineage variability in phylogenetic imputation of functional trait datasets . ECOGRAPHY, V41, P10 DOI 10.1111/ecog.03480
4	14	0	Dennett, JM (2018-JAN) Investigating detection success: lessons from trials using decoy rare plants . PLANT ECOLOGY, V219, P13 DOI 10.1007/s11258-018-0819-1
4	22	0	Mcneillie, MJ (2019-JAN) Species abundance distributions should underpin ordinal cover-abundance transformations . APPLIED VEGETATION SCIENCE, V22, P12 DOI 10.1111/avsc.12437
4	8	0	Ellis, CJ (2017-JAN) Taxonomic survey compared to ecological sampling: are the results consistent for woodland epiphytes? . LICHENOLOGIST, V49, P15 DOI 10.1017/S0024282917000056
4	19	0	Poyatos, R (2018-JAN) Gap-filling a spatially explicit plant trait database: comparing imputation methods and different levels of environmental information . BIOGEOSCIENCES, V15, P17 DOI 10.5194/bg-15-2601-2018
4	17	0	Maginel, CJ (2016-JAN) Floristic quality index for woodland ground flora restoration: utility and effectiveness in a fire-managed landscape . ECOLOGICAL INDICATORS, V67, P10 DOI 10.1016/j.ecolind.2016.02.035
4	9	0	Bried, JT (2018-JAN) Experts and models can agree on species sensitivity values for conservation assessments . BIOLOGICAL CONSERVATION DOI 10.1016/j.biocon.2018.07.013
4	35	0	Kim, SW (2018-JAN) Transcending data gaps: a framework to reduce inferential errors in ecological analyses . ECOLOGY LETTERS, V21, P11 DOI 10.1111/ele.13089
4	30	0	Magee, TK (2019-JAN) A national-scale vegetation multimetric index (vmmi) as an indicator of wetland condition across the conterminous united states . ENVIRONMENTAL MONITORING AND ASSESSMENT, V191, P28 DOI 10.1007/s10661-019-7324-4
3	0	0	Kolarova, M (2016-JAN) Data collection. ATLAS OF WEED MAPPING
3	9	0	Irvine, KM (2019-JAN) Cohesive framework for modelling plant cover class data . METHODS IN ECOLOGY AND EVOLUTION, V10, P12 DOI 10.1111/2041-210X.13262
3	4	0	Libala, N (2021-JAN) The evaluation of biological indices to assess the condition of hillslope seep wetlands in the tsitsa river catchment, south africa . PLOS ONE, V16, P19 DOI 10.1371/journal.pone.0251370

3	291	0	Jetz, W (2016-JAN) Monitoring plant functional diversity from space . NATURE PLANTS DOI 10.1038/NPLANTS.2016.24
3	31	0	Barbosa, JM (2016-JAN) Determining subcanopy psidium cattleianum invasion in hawaiian forests using imaging spectroscopy . REMOTE SENSING DOI 10.3390/rs8010033
3	0	0	Stern, JL (2020-JAN) Coefficients of conservatism for the flora of the middle rio grande floodplain . SOUTHWESTERN NATURALIST, V65, P11 DOI 10.1894/0038-4909-65.2.141
3	19	0	Ficken, CD (2020-JAN) Linking plant conservatism scores to plant functional traits . ECOLOGICAL INDICATORS DOI 10.1016/j.ecolind.2020.106376
3	19	0	Miller, JED (2020-JAN) Using lichen communities as indicators of forest stand age and conservation value . FOREST ECOLOGY AND MANAGEMENT DOI 10.1016/j.foreco.2020.118436
3	16	0	Mason, NWH (2018-JAN) Incorporating measurement error in testing for changes in biodiversity . METHODS IN ECOLOGY AND EVOLUTION DOI 10.1111/2041-210X.12976
3	23	0	Kutcher, TE (2018-JAN) Evaluating how variants of floristic quality assessment indicate wetland condition . JOURNAL OF ENVIRONMENTAL MANAGEMENT DOI 10.1016/j.jenvman.2018.03.093
3	4	0	Suir, GM (2021-JAN) Evaluating the use of hyperspectral imagery to calculate raster-based wetland vegetation condition indicator . AQUATIC ECOSYSTEM HEALTH & MANAGEMENT, V24, P12 DOI 10.14321/ae hm.024.04.13
3	1	0	Kolarova, M (2016-JAN) Approaches to the analysis of weed distribution. ATLAS OF WEED MAPPING
3	0	0	Ito, H (2020-JAN) State-space modeling of the dynamics of temporal plant cover using visually determined class data . PEERJ DOI 10.7717/peerj.9383
3	9	0	Damgaard, C (2016-JAN) Arctic resilience: no evidence of vegetation change in response to grazing and climate changes in south greenland . ARCTIC ANTARCTIC AND ALPINE RESEARCH, V48, P19 DOI 10.1657/AAAR0016-005
3	46	0	Taddeo, S (2018-JAN) Indicators of vegetation development in restored wetlands . ECOLOGICAL INDICATORS, V94, P14 DOI 10.1016/j.ecolind.2018.07.010
3	12	0	Cancellieri, L (2017-JAN) In and out: effects of shoot- vs. rooted-presence sampling methods on plant diversity measures in mountain grasslands . ECOLOGICAL INDICATORS DOI 10.1016/j.ecolind.2016.08.029
3	14	0	Zinnen, J (2021-JAN) Expert-based measures of human impact to vegetation . APPLIED VEGETATION SCIENCE, V24, P13 DOI 10.1111/avsc.12523
3	6	0	Sanders, S (2014-JAN) Alternative metrics for evaluating forest integrity and assessing change at four northern-tier us national parks . AMERICAN MIDLAND NATURALIST, V171, P19 DOI 10.1674/0003-0031-171.2.185

3	18	0	Wright, WJ (2017-JAN) Statistical design and analysis for plant cover studies with multiple sources of observation errors . METHODS IN ECOLOGY AND EVOLUTION DOI 10.1111/2041-210X.12825
3	30	0	De, lombarder E (2019-JAN) Tree regeneration responds more to shade casting by the overstorey and competition in the understorey than to abundance per se . FOREST ECOLOGY AND MANAGEMENT, V450, P12 DOI 10.1016/j.foreco.2019.117492
2	11	0	Doebert, TF (2015-JAN) Can leaf area index and biomass be estimated from braun-blauquet cover scores in tropical forests? . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V26, P11 DOI 10.1111/jvs.12310
2	19	0	Spyreas, G (2016-JAN) Scale and sampling effects on floristic quality . PLOS ONE, V11, P16 DOI 10.1371/journal.pone.0160693
2	4	0	Bried, JT (2019-JAN) Enhanced indicator species performance with increasing contextualization . CONSERVATION SCIENCE AND PRACTICE DOI 10.1111/csp2.127
2	13	0	Wen, Z (2017-JAN) Estimating seasonal aboveground biomass of a riparian pioneer plant community: an exploratory analysis by canopy structural data . ECOLOGICAL INDICATORS, V83, P10 DOI 10.1016/j.ecolind.2017.07.048
2	2	0	Begley-miller, DR (2018-JAN) Evaluating inter-rater reliability and statistical power of vegetation measures assessing deer impact . FORESTS DOI 10.3390/f9110669
2	9	0	Alemu, T (2018-JAN) Development of a plant based riparian index of biotic integrity (ribi) for assessing the ecological condition of highland streams in east africa . ECOLOGICAL INDICATORS DOI 10.1016/j.ecolind.2017.12.032
2	49	0	Yepsen, M (2014-JAN) Agricultural wetland restorations on the usa atlantic coastal plain achieve diverse native wetland plant communities but differ from natural wetlands . AGRICULTURE ECOSYSTEMS & ENVIRONMENT, V197, P10 DOI 10.1016/j.agee.2014.07.007
2	23	0	Halmy, MWA (2019-JAN) Assessing the impact of anthropogenic activities on the ecological quality of arid mediterranean ecosystems (case study from the northwestern coast of egypt) . ECOLOGICAL INDICATORS, V101, P12 DOI 10.1016/j.ecolind.2019.02.005
2	7	0	Perles, SJ (2014-JAN) Evaluation of a regional monitoring program's statistical power to detect temporal trends in forest health indicators . ENVIRONMENTAL MANAGEMENT, V54, P15 DOI 10.1007/s00267-014-0313-z
2	1	0	Bried, JT (2021-JAN) Searching for indicator species of high floristic quality depressional wetlands in the us southern plains . WETLANDS DOI 10.1007/s13157-021-01492-9
2	5	0	Safont, E (2016-JAN) Plant communities and environmental factors in the guayana highlands: monitoring for conservation under future climate change . SYSTEMATICS AND BIODIVERSITY, V14, P18 DOI 10.1080/14772000.2015.1134700

2	16	0	Bried, JT (2014-JAN) Potential vegetation criteria for identifying reference-quality wetlands in the south-central united states . WETLANDS, V34, P11 DOI 10.1007/s13157-014-0575-5
2	4	0	Gautam, H (2017-JAN) Using visual estimation of cover for rapid assessment of graminoid abundance in forest and grassland habitats in studies of animal foraging . PHYTOCOENOLOGIA, V47, P13 DOI 10.1127/phyto/2017/0146
2	8	0	Pincheira-ulbrich, J (2016-JAN) Assessing the completeness of inventories of vascular epiphytes and climbing plants in chilean swamp forest remnants . NEW ZEALAND JOURNAL OF BOTANY, V54, P17 DOI 10.1080/0028825X.2016.1218899
2	2	0	Stern, JL (2021-JAN) Determining vegetation metric robustness to environmental and methodological variables . ENVIRONMENTAL MONITORING AND ASSESSMENT, V193, P14 DOI 10.1007/s10661-021-09445-9
2	6	0	Maciejewski, L (2020-JAN) Vegetation unit assignments: phytosociology experts and classification programs show similar performance but low convergence . APPLIED VEGETATION SCIENCE, V23, P12 DOI 10.1111/avsc.12516
2	7	0	Bolding, MT (2020-JAN) Improvements in multi-metric index development using a whole-index approach . ECOLOGICAL INDICATORS, V113, P12 DOI 10.1016/j.ecolind.2020.106191
2	6	0	Rodhouse, TJ (2020-JAN) Post-fire vegetation response in a repeatedly burned low-elevation sagebrush steppe protected area provides insights about resilience and invasion resistance . FRONTIERS IN ECOLOGY AND EVOLUTION DOI 10.3389/fevo.2020.584726
2	326	0	Franklin, J (2016-JAN) Global change and terrestrial plant community dynamics . PROCEEDINGS OF THE NATIONAL ACADEMY OF SCIENCES OF THE UNITED STATES OF AMERICA, V113, P10 DOI 10.1073/pnas.1519911113
2	13	0	Zinnen, J (2021-JAN) Niche ecology in floristic quality assessment: are species with higher conservatism more specialized? . ECOLOGICAL INDICATORS, V121, P10 DOI 10.1016/j.ecolind.2020.107078
2	4	0	Mabry, C (2018-JAN) Validating the use of coefficients of conservatism to assess forest herbaceous layer quality in upland mesic forests . NATURAL AREAS JOURNAL DOI 10.3375/043.038.0103
2	9	0	Morrison, LW (2017-JAN) Insular plant turnover across a 22-year interval: a critical retrospective of the roles of pseudoturnover and cryptoturnover . JOURNAL OF BIOGEOGRAPHY, V44, P11 DOI 10.1111/jbi.12866
2	35	0	Ullerud, HA (2018-JAN) Consistency in land-cover mapping: influence of field workers, spatial scale and classification system . APPLIED VEGETATION SCIENCE, V21, P11 DOI 10.1111/avsc.12368
2	4	0	Hackett, RA (2016-JAN) Evaluating a sampling protocol for assessing plant diversity in prairie fens . WETLANDS ECOLOGY AND MANAGEMENT, V24, P14 DOI 10.1007/s11273-016-9491-1

2	25	0	Chamberlain, SJ (2016-JAN) Testing a rapid floristic quality index on headwater wetlands in central pennsylvania, usa. ECOLOGICAL INDICATORS DOI 10.1016/j.ecolind.2015.09.004
2	164	0	Lawley, V (2016-JAN) Site-based and remote sensing methods for monitoring indicators of vegetation condition: an australian review. ECOLOGICAL INDICATORS, V60, P11 DOI 10.1016/j.ecolind.2015.03.021
2	6	0	Sandino, JD (2016-JAN) Method for estimating leaf coverage in strawberry plants using digital image processing. REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE ENGENHARIA AGRICOLA E AMBIENTAL DOI 10.1590/1807-1929/agriambi.v20n8p716-721

Appendix 2 Table 13 Cluster 11

Coverage	GCS	LCS	Bibliography
11	22	0	Trindade, DPF (2020-JAN) Temporal lags in observed and dark diversity in the anthropocene . GLOBAL CHANGE BIOLOGY DOI 10.1111/gcb.15093
11	22	0	Flojgaard, C (2020-JAN) Dark diversity reveals importance of biotic resources and competition for plant diversity across habitats . ECOLOGY AND EVOLUTION, V10, P11 DOI 10.1002/ece3.6351
8	78	0	Lewis, RJ (2016-JAN) Estimating dark diversity and species pools: an empirical assessment of two methods . METHODS IN ECOLOGY AND EVOLUTION DOI 10.1111/2041-210X.12443
8	36	0	de, bello F (2016-JAN) Measuring size and composition of species pools: a comparison of dark diversity estimates . ECOLOGY AND EVOLUTION DOI 10.1002/ece3.2169
8	13	0	Belinchon, R (2020-JAN) Functional traits determine why species belong to the dark diversity in a dry grassland fragmented landscape . OIKOS, V129, P13 DOI 10.1111/oik.07308
8	36	0	Lewis, RJ (2017-JAN) Applying the dark diversity concept to nature conservation . CONSERVATION BIOLOGY DOI 10.1111/cobi.12723
8	20	0	Ronk, A (2016-JAN) Large-scale dark diversity estimates: new perspectives with combined methods . ECOLOGY AND EVOLUTION DOI 10.1002/ece3.2371
8	64	0	Partel, M (2016-JAN) Macroecology of biodiversity: disentangling local and regional effects . NEW PHYTOLOGIST DOI 10.1111/nph.13943
7	12	0	Partel, M (2017-JAN) Global patterns in local and dark diversity, species pool size and community completeness in ectomycorrhizal fungi . BIOGEOGRAPHY OF MYCORRHIZAL SYMBIOSIS, V230, P12 DOI 10.1007/978-3-319-56363-3_18
6	51	0	Moeslund, JE (2017-JAN) Using dark diversity and plant characteristics to guide conservation and restoration . JOURNAL OF APPLIED ECOLOGY, V54, P12 DOI 10.1111/1365-2664.12867
6	24	0	Noreika, N (2020-JAN) Community completeness as a measure of restoration success: multiple-study comparisons across ecosystems and ecological groups . BIODIVERSITY AND CONSERVATION, V29, P21 DOI 10.1007/s10531-020-02050-1
6	6	0	Chozas, S (2017-JAN) Trait dynamics of mediterranean xerophytic shrub communities growing on stabilised inland dunes respond to nutrient and aridity gradients . PLANT ECOLOGY & DIVERSITY, V10, P12 DOI 10.1080/17550874.2017.1345997
6	17	0	Brown, JJ (2019-JAN) A novel method to predict dark diversity using unconstrained ordination analysis . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V30, P10 DOI 10.1111/jvs.12757
6	170	0	Birks, HJB (2016-JAN) Does pollen-assemblage richness reflect floristic richness? a review of recent developments and future challenges . REVIEW OF PALAEOBOTANY AND PALYNOLOGY, V228, P25 DOI 10.1016/j.revpalbo.2015.12.011

6	63	0	Partel, M (2017-JAN) Historical biome distribution and recent human disturbance shape the diversity of arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi . NEW PHYTOLOGIST, V216, P12 DOI 10.1111/nph.14695
5	11	0	Svamberkova, E (2017-JAN) The role of biotic interactions in plant community assembly: what is the community species pool? . ACTA OECOLOGICA-INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ECOLOGY DOI 10.1016/j.actao.2017.10.011
5	44	0	Carmona, CP (2021-JAN) Estimating probabilistic site-specific species pools and dark diversity from co-occurrence data . GLOBAL ECOLOGY AND BIOGEOGRAPHY, V30, P11 DOI 10.1111/geb.13203
5	15	0	Bruehlheide, H (2020-JAN) Deriving site-specific species pools from large databases . ECOGRAPHY, V43, P14 DOI 10.1111/ecog.05172
5	21	0	Ronk, A (2017-JAN) Observed and dark diversity of alien plant species in europe: estimating future invasion risk . BIODIVERSITY AND CONSERVATION, V26, P18 DOI 10.1007/s10531-016-1278-4
5	16	0	Riibak, K (2017-JAN) Dispersal limitation determines large-scale dark diversity in central and northern europe . JOURNAL OF BIOGEOGRAPHY, V44, P11 DOI 10.1111/jbi.13000
5	15	0	Bennett, JA (2017-JAN) Predicting species establishment using absent species and functional neighborhoods . ECOLOGY AND EVOLUTION DOI 10.1002/ece3.2804
5	36	0	Bennett, JA (2016-JAN) Species pools, community completeness and invasion: disentangling diversity effects on the establishment of native and alien species . ECOLOGY LETTERS, V19, P10 DOI 10.1111/ele.12702
4	15	0	Riibak, K (2020-JAN) Drivers of plant community completeness differ at regional and landscape scales . AGRICULTURE ECOSYSTEMS & ENVIRONMENT DOI 10.1016/j.agee.2020.107004
4	16	0	Janeckova, P (2017-JAN) The plant functional traits that explain species occurrence across fragmented grasslands differ according to patch management, isolation, and wetness . LANDSCAPE ECOLOGY, V32, P15 DOI 10.1007/s10980-017-0486-y
4	12	0	Partel, M (2019-JAN) Darkdivnet - a global research collaboration to explore the dark diversity of plant communities . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE DOI 10.1111/jvs.12798
4	11	0	Svamberkova, E (2020-JAN) Experimental assessment of biotic and abiotic filters driving community composition . ECOLOGY AND EVOLUTION, V10, P13 DOI 10.1002/ece3.6461
4	11	0	Kasari, L (2016-JAN) Hybrid ecosystems can contribute to local biodiversity conservation . BIODIVERSITY AND CONSERVATION, V25, P19 DOI 10.1007/s10531-016-1218-3
4	192	0	Bruehlheide, H (2019-JAN) Splot - a new tool for global vegetation analyses . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V30, P26 DOI 10.1111/jvs.12710

Appendix 2 Table 14 Cluster 12

Coverage	GCS	LCS	Bibliography
10	4	0	Chollet, S (2025-JAN) Dark diversity and habitat conservation status: two sides of the same coin for conservation and restoration? . ECOLOGICAL INDICATORS DOI 10.1016/j.ecolind.2024.112990
7	0	0	Huang, X (2025-JAN) Multiple dimensions of biodiversity jointly drive community completeness in baima snow mountain typical forest. ECOLOGICAL INDICATORS, V179, P12 DOI 10.1016/j.ecolind.2025.114197
6	0	0	Wan, J (2025-JAN) Environmental heterogeneity drives the dark diversity of global plant communities. JOURNAL OF BIOGEOGRAPHY DOI 10.1111/jbi.70043
6	0	0	Boet, O (2025-JAN) The latitudinal gradient in european ant dark diversity: patterns and potential mechanisms. OIKOS DOI 10.1002/oik.10656
6	0	0	Di, lorenzo G (2025-JAN) Robotic monitoring of european habitats: a labeled dataset for plant detection in annex i habitats of italy. SCIENTIFIC DATA, V12, P24 DOI 10.1038/s41597-025-05182-7
5	0	0	Wan, J (2025-JAN) Linking forest coverage and fragmentation to the dark diversity of plant communities under different forest management practices. JOURNAL OF ENVIRONMENTAL MANAGEMENT, V392, P11 DOI 10.1016/j.jenvman.2025.126408
5	3	0	Gavriel, T (2025-JAN) Using dark diversity to disentangle the effects of protection and habitat quality on species diversity. BIOLOGICAL CONSERVATION, V305, P10 DOI 10.1016/j.biocon.2025.111096
4	2	0	Bakr, J (2024-JAN) Plant species and functional diversity of novel forests growing on coal mine heaps compared with managed coniferous and deciduous mixed forests. FORESTS, V15, P20 DOI 10.3390/f15040730
4	1	0	Anibaba, QA (2024-JAN) Remote sensing for site selection in vegetation survey along a successional gradient in post-industrial vegetation. ECOLOGY AND EVOLUTION, V14, P18 DOI 10.1002/ece3.70200
4	0	0	Feng, X (2025-JAN) Integrating dark diversity perspective into species conservation: a novel regional species protection index (rspi) for identifying priority areas. ECOLOGICAL INDICATORS, V179, P15 DOI 10.1016/j.ecolind.2025.114173
4	3	0	Fanfarillo, E (2025-JAN) Drivers and patterns of community completeness suggest that tuscan fagus sylvatica forests can naturally have a low plant diversity. FOREST ECOSYSTEMS, V12, P11 DOI 10.1016/j.fecs.2024.100276
4	2	0	Bakr, J (2024-JAN) Taxonomic and functional diversity along successional stages on post-coalmine spoil heaps. FRONTIERS IN ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCE, V12, P13 DOI 10.3389/fenvs.2024.1412631
3	0	0	Fanfarillo, E (2025-JAN) Different control strategies of the invasive plant arundo donax l. have taxon-specific effects on above-and belowground biodiversity. JOURNAL OF ENVIRONMENTAL MANAGEMENT, V392, P11 DOI 10.1016/j.jenvman.2025.126833

3	4	0	Hostens, L (2023-JAN) The drivers of dark diversity in the scandinavian mountains are metric-dependent . JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V34, P16 DOI 10.1111/jvs.13212
3	0	0	Dubinska, AM (2025-JAN) How does non-native robinia pseudoacacia l. affect urban forest biodiversity? . URBAN FORESTRY & URBAN GREENING, V113, P12 DOI 10.1016/j.ufug.2025.129079
3	0	0	Baba, W (2024-JAN) Photosynthetic response of solidago gigantea aition and calamagrostis epigejos l. (roth) to complex environmental stress on heavy metal contaminated sites . SCIENTIFIC REPORTS, V14, P20 DOI 10.1038/s41598-024-82952-0
3	0	0	Fahs, N (2025-JAN) Parasitic plants in europe: ecological niches and spatial patterns . PLANT BIOLOGY DOI 10.1111/plb.70099
3	3	0	Krasnov, BR (2022-JAN) Identification of the missing links in parasite-host networks using the dark diversity concept: a case study with two taxonomic groups of ectoparasitic arthropods and small mammalian hosts . ECOLOGICAL ENTOMOLOGY, V47, P15 DOI 10.1111/een.13128
3	14	0	Anibaba, QA (2023-JAN) Native plant community characteristics explain alien species success in post-industrial vegetation . NEOBIOTA, V85, P22 DOI 10.3897/neobiota.85.97269
3	0	0	Akatov, VV (2025-JAN) On local species saturation of synanthropic plant communities in the western caucasus and the role of alien species in its achievement . ZHURNAL OBSHCHEI BIOLOGII, V86, P17 DOI 10.31857/S0044459625010026
3	0	0	Blakemore, RJ (2025-JAN) Biodiversity restated: > 99.9% of global species in soil biota . ZOOKEYS DOI 10.3897/zookeys.1224.131153
3	0	0	Dano, M (2025-JAN) Fifty years of regional-scale vegetation change on atlantic heathlands . BIOLOGICAL CONSERVATION, V308, P10 DOI 10.1016/j.biocon.2025.111210
3	1	0	Bakr, J (2024-JAN) Borrow pit disposal of coal mining byproducts improves soil physicochemical properties and vegetation succession . AGRONOMY-BASEL, V14, P17 DOI 10.3390/agronomy14081638
3	0	0	Tolomei, S (2025-JAN) Harnessing robotics for european union forest habitats monitoring: toward a robotic-assisted framework for standardized field surveys . IEEE ROBOTICS & AUTOMATION MAGAZINE DOI 10.1109/MRA.2025.3584343
3	9	0	Krasnov, BR (2022-JAN) Dark diversity of flea assemblages of small mammalian hosts: effects of environment, host traits and host phylogeny . INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL FOR PARASITOLOGY, V52, P11 DOI 10.1016/j.ijpara.2021.08.003
2	3	0	Praeg, N (2025-JAN) Biodiversity in mountain soils above the treeline . BIOLOGICAL REVIEWS, V100, P73 DOI 10.1111/brv.70028
2	4	0	Krasnov, BR (2022-JAN) Dark host specificity in two ectoparasite taxa: repeatability, parasite traits, and environmental effects . PARASITOLOGY RESEARCH, V121, P16 DOI 10.1007/s00436-022-07461-3
2	0	0	Zhao, S (2025-JAN) Spatial mismatch between in-situ conservation and diversity hotspots of chinese native useful vascular plants . GEOGRAPHY AND SUSTAINABILITY DOI 10.1016/j.geosus.2024.100252

2	2	0	Junker, K (2023-JAN) Nestedness and beta diversity of gastrointestinal helminth communities in common warthogs, phacochoerus africanus (suidae), at 2 localities in south africa. PARASITOLOGY, V150, P11 DOI 10.1017/S0031182023000719
2	1	0	da, silva SR (2024-JAN) Assessment of the dark diversity's ability to predict the absence of zygoptera (odonata) species sensitive to anthropogenic disturbance in human-altered amazonian ecosystems. ENVIRONMENTAL MONITORING AND ASSESSMENT, V196, P14 DOI 10.1007/s10661-024-13291-w

Appendix 2 Table 14 Cluster 13

Coverage	GCS	LCS	Bibliography
8	10	0	Herman-brunson, KM (2009-JAN) Nesting ecology of greater sage-grouse centrocerus urophasianus at the eastern edge of their historic distribution. WILDLIFE BIOLOGY, V15, P10 DOI 10.2981/09-005
8	6	0	Herman-brunson, KM (2009-JAN) Nesting ecology of greater sage-grouse centrocerus urophasianus at the eastern edge of their historic distribution. WILDLIFE BIOLOGY, V15, P10 DOI 10.2981/09-005
5	36	0	Chen, Z (2010-JAN) Digital photograph analysis for measuring percent plant cover in the arctic. ARCTIC, V63, P12
4	19	0	Fehmi, JS (2010-JAN) Confusion among three common plant cover definitions may result in data unsuited for comparison. JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE DOI 10.1111/j.1654-1103.2009.01141.x
4	3336	0	Blaschke, T (2010-JAN) Object based image analysis for remote sensing. ISPRS JOURNAL OF PHOTOGRAMMETRY AND REMOTE SENSING, V65, P15 DOI 10.1016/j.isprsjprs.2009.06.004
4	662	0	Dragut, L (2010-JAN) Esp: a tool to estimate scale parameter for multiresolution image segmentation of remotely sensed data. INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF GEOGRAPHICAL INFORMATION SCIENCE, V24, P13 DOI 10.1080/13658810903174803
3	115	0	Crimmins, MA (2008-JAN) Monitoring plant phenology using digital repeat photography. ENVIRONMENTAL MANAGEMENT, V41, P10 DOI 10.1007/s00267-008-9086-6
3	16	0	von, wehrden H (2009-JAN) Predictive mapping of plant species and communities using gis and landsat data in a southern mongolian mountain range. FOLIA GEOBOTANICA, V44, P15 DOI 10.1007/s12224-009-9042-0
3	7	0	Bold, KC (2010-JAN) Using photographic image analysis to assess ground cover: a case study of forest road cutbanks. ENVIRONMENTAL MONITORING AND ASSESSMENT, V163, P14 DOI 10.1007/s10661-009-0868-y
3	56	0	Wilson, JB (2011-JAN) Cover plus: ways of measuring plant canopies and the terms used for them. JOURNAL OF VEGETATION SCIENCE, V22, P10 DOI 10.1111/j.1654-1103.2010.01238.x
3	40	0	Karl, JW (2010-JAN) Multivariate correlations between imagery and field measurements across scales: comparing pixel aggregation and image segmentation. LANDSCAPE ECOLOGY, V25, P15 DOI 10.1007/s10980-009-9439-4
2	22	0	Laliberte, AS (2010-JAN) Hierarchical object-based classification of ultra-high-resolution digital mapping camera (dmc) imagery for rangeland mapping and assessment. JOURNAL OF SPATIAL SCIENCE, V55, P15 DOI 10.1080/14498596.2010.487853